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Salahaddin University – Erbil

The Impact of Some Economic Variables on Terrorism in Selected Countries with Special Reference to Iraq for the Period 2000-2021

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A VERSE FROM HOLY QURAN

بِسْمِ اللَّهِ الرَّحْمَنِ الرَّحِيمِ

أَمْ نَجْعَلُ الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا وَعَمِلُوا الصَّالِحَاتِ كَالْمُفْسِدِينَ فِي الْأَرْضِ أَمْ نَجْعَلُ

الْمُتَّقِينَ كَالْفُجَّارِ ۝

{سورة ص الآية 28}

**In the Name of Allah, the Most Compassionate, the
Most Merciful**

Shall We treat those who believe and do good works
as those who spread corruption in the earth or shall
We treat the pious as the wicked ۝

{Surah Sād verse 28}

DECLARATION

I declare that the PhD dissertation entitled: **‘The Impact of Some Economic Variables on Terrorism in Selected Countries with Special Reference to Iraq for the Period 2000-2021’** is my own original work. Hereby I certify that all work contained within this dissertation is my own independent research and has not been submitted to any party before to obtain an academic degree at any institution. Also, I declare that I have mentioned the sources honestly wherever I quoted them¹.

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DEDICATION

This effort is dedicated to:

- *My parents.*
- *My husband and our two sons.*
- *My siblings.*
- *To everyone who strives for security, peace, and disseminate knowledge that benefits society.*

Sarah

September 7, 2023

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the impact of some economic and non-economic variables on terrorism in seven selected countries, with special emphasis on Iraq, over the period 2000 to 2021. It includes three main topics: 1) economic theories and concepts related to terrorism. 2) Panel data analysis to investigate the impact of some economic, political and demographic variables on terrorism. 3) Estimated ARDL time series model, and estimated ARMA model for forecasting Iraq terrorism index.

Autoregressive distributed lag ARDL models, including pooled mean group PMG, mean group MG, and dynamic fixed effect DFE, were used in panel data analysis. The selected PMG model for the economic variables reveals a long-run negative relationship between the GDP growth rate and terrorism, while there is a positive relationship between the inflation rate and terrorism. On the other hand, the PMG model for various variables showed that political stability, foreign interventions, and GDP growth have a negative long-term relationship with terrorism. However, inflation and demographic pressure have a positive long-term relationship. In the short run, economic globalization has an inverse relationship with terrorism. The study reveals that economic variables alone have a long-term effect on terrorism in selected countries, lasting approximately 9 years, while the mixed variables, which include economic and non-economic factors, have a medium effect of approximately 4 years.

This study reveals that inflation has a positive effect on terrorism in Iraq, while GDP growth, unemployment, income inequality and political stability have long-term negative effects. The average speed of adjustment from prior-year imbalance to current-year balance is 81.9%, indicating a 1.2-year effect. The predictions of the ARMA model forecasts a slow and continuous decline in Iraq terrorism indicis in the future.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
GTD	Global Terrorism Database
IEP	Institute for Economics and Peace
GTI	Global Terrorism Index
DV	Dependent Variable
IV	Independent Variable
TI	Terrorism Index
GDPG	Gross Domestic Product Growth Rate
INF	Inflation Rate
UEM	Unemployment Rate
GINI	GINI Coefficient
G	Economic Globalization Index
PS	Political Stability Index
EXI	External Interventions Index
DP	Demographic Pressures Index
POLS	Pooled Ordinary Least Squares
FEM	Fixed Effect Model
REM	Random Effect Model
ARDL	Auto Regressive Distributed Lags
ECM	Error Correction Model
ECT	Error Correction Term
MG	Mean Group
PMG	Pooled Mean Group
DFE	Dynamic Fixed Effect
GMM	Generalized Method of Moments

Abbreviation	Definition
G2SLS	Generalized Two Stages Least Square
ADF	Augmented Dicky Fuller
LLC	Levin Lin and Chu
PP	Philips Perron
CIPS	Cross Im Pesaran and Shin
CADF	Cross Augmented Dicky Fuller
BP	Bruch Pagan
LM	Lagrange Multiplier
CSD	Cross Section Dependence
CD	Cross Dependence
VD	Variance Decomposition
IRA	Impulse Response Analysis
DKW	Ditzen, Karavias & Westerlund Test of Break Dates
KT	Karavias and Tzavalis Unit Root Test
DH	Dumitrescu and Hurlin's Granger Causality Test
SE	Standard Error
SD	Standard Deviation

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION, AND LITERATURE REVIEW

1.1 Introduction

Terrorist operations have witnessed an increase in frequency across many countries over the past decade, leading to significant human and economic losses, as well as profound psychological traumas. Terrorism transcends mental, geographical, and political boundaries, and has intensified in some Asian countries such as Iraq, Levant, Pakistan, Afghanistan, and Middle East and Northern Africa MENA (Global Terrorism Index 2020). While there have been recent efforts to understand the causes and consequences of terrorism and propose solutions, a comprehensive examination of the subject remains incomplete. Terrorism is often associated with political objectives pursued by certain groups to achieve specific gains, though it encompasses a broader scope than just political violence. Scholars like Okeke (2005) and Nacos (2006) argue that terrorism, in the long run, is driven by political objectives regardless of short-term tenets and beliefs held by terrorists. However, the literature has not yet reached a definitive and precise definition of terrorism. In 2004, the UN Resolution 1566 did find common ground on certain components of the concept of terrorism. It identifies terrorists as members of specific religious or ethnic groups, predominantly non-state actors.

The effects of terrorist attacks are expected to be most severe in unorganized and low-level economies confronting continuous operations. The emergence of new terrorist groups in to Sub-Saharan Africa, particularly in Sahil, escorted with poor economy and poverty, made suitable environment to enter more people into these groups (USAID 2017).

Terrorism imposes both direct and indirect costs on the affected regions. The direct costs include immeasurable losses of human lives, pain, and psychological harm. Indirect costs, on the other hand, consist of expenses

related to damaged buildings, equipment, inventories, property damages, and a decline in investment returns (Enders and Sandler 2011). For example, the US Bureau of Labor Statistics (2003) reported that approximately 145,000 workers were laid off for about thirty days following the 9/11 attacks in New York in 2001. Moreover, the rate of unemployment rose by one percentage point in the first quarter immediately after the incident, leading to a total output loss of \$47 billion. A study by Ito and Lee (2005) showed that a quick increase in terror, albeit temporary, reduced the demand for air travel by over 30%. However, factors such as increased passenger screening and security checks resulted in a permanent decrease in airline demand by about 7.4%. Throughout the preceding decade, there was an average of 26,000 fatalities annually, although significant variation occurred from year to year. The worldwide mortality toll fluctuated from 8,200 in 2011 to its highest 44,600 in 2014, then start declining, where in 2020 terrorism caused an estimated 22,847 deaths worldwide (Herre et al. 2023).

Much attention has been devoted by scholars to study terrorism since the 1960's till the time being, as per; Long (1990), and Rice (1988), is because of the high costs of both World Wars, and on suing cold war. The beneficiaries of conflicts prefer alternative warfare, introduced through creating conflicts via terrorist organizations. Iraq, with its essential geopolitical position in the Middle East and membership in OPIC, was not immune to terrorist actions. The country's Human Development Indicator was 71.2% in 1990, but decreased to 62.2% in 2013 as a result of terrorism and political instability (Mahmud 2020).

On the macroeconomic aspect, Goldstein (2005) argues that the unemployment factor has a significant relationship with terrorism across 105 countries. Piazza (2006) believes that the root causes of terrorism are related to poverty, inequality, and poor economic development in ninety-six states from 1986 to

2002. Bren, Zeman, and Urban (2019) claim that social inequality, GDP, ongoing war conflicts, corruption, and political instability increase terrorism.

In this dissertation the researcher attempts to determine the most significant economic, political, and demographic causes of terrorism in the most vulnerable seven countries on one side, and Iraq on the other, over the past two decades.

1.2 Problem Statement and Research Questions

A number of countries, particularly some Asian countries, and MENA experienced increases in terrorism-related repercussions during the years 2000 - 2021. Many economic, political, and social interpretations have attempted to show the causes of these rapid increases in terrorist incidents, nevertheless, no empirically validated studies have identified the most significant economic, political, and demographic factors that prompt terrorism in the aforementioned time period. Therefore, this study attempts to expose the most significant economic, political, and demographic factors that trigger terrorism in the seven most impacted countries all over the world during the past decade, via answering the following questions:

- i. Do the economic, political, and demographic variables determine terrorism in the selected countries under study? Which one of them is most influential, in term of parameter size, on terrorism? And what kind of models are best suited for this purpose, static or dynamic?
- ii. To what extent do economic and political variables explain terrorism in Iraq over the long and short run time frame? How would be the annual and average growth rates in Iraq's; GDP, inflation, unemployment, income inequality, and political stability, with the changes in Terrorism Index? How would shocks to the independent variables affect the terrorism index of Iraq?

And how would be the forecasted trend of Iraq's terrorism index in the short and long run?

1.3 Significance of The Study

This study emphasizes on the importance of identifying the main socioeconomic factors for policymakers and counterterrorism organizations to carry out necessary procedures to minimize terrorism. It also might serve as a helpful guide for the investigated countries as if they implement strategic economic, political, and demographic reforms, in order to provide more secure environment for their people, and hence a sustainable economic growth.

1.4 The Objectives

In this study, the researcher selects two certain groups of objectives for:

A. The Selected Countries

- i. Construction linear panel models to demonstrate the type of relationship, and the extent of the impact of some economic, political, and demographic factors on terrorism, which measured by the Global Terrorism Index (TI).
- ii. Revealing the long and short run effects, and the speed of adjustment for each autoregressive model that will be developed.
- iii. Determining the regressors that Granger cause terrorism in the selected countries.

B. The State of Iraq

- i. Finding annual growth rates and average growth rates of Iraq's GDP, inflation, unemployment, income inequality, and political stability index associated with changes in Terrorism Index growth rates.
- ii. Constructing an ARDL model using time series data of some economic determinants as independent variables and terrorism index as the dependent variable. And estimating the short-run and long-run effects of economic variables on terrorism in Iraq.

- iii. Revealing the impact of shocks to economic variables on terrorism volatility in Iraq through variance decomposition technique, in the VAR system.
- iv. Forecasting annual terrorism index using the ARMA model.

1.5 Methodologies and Approaches

The methodologies followed are:

- i. The deductive; to diagnose the key variables that might affect terrorism, explain the nature of relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables through theoretical and applied studies related to the economics of terrorism.
- ii. The inductive; through construction of two types of econometric modeling by using the soft-wares of EViews and STATA. The first type modeling is panel data analysis for the seven selected countries, and the second is a time series analysis for the state of Iraq.

The approaches followed:

- i. Two sets of linear models will be constructed for the seven selected countries. The first model specifies some economic determinants that affect terrorism, while the second model delves into the combined impact of macroeconomic, political, and demographic factors on terrorism. The analysis covers; descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, cross-section dependency tests, unit root tests for exploring data stationarity, long-run model cointegration tests, and several panel data modeling, such as; Pooled OLS, Random Effect, Fixed Effect, Pooled Mean Group, Mean Group, and Dynamic Fixed Effect models.
- ii. Iraq's time series data analysis covers; descriptive statistics, annual growth rates and average growth rates of the studied variables. Then

constructing an ARDL model, employing the variance decomposition approach to investigate how a one standard deviation shock to each economic factor affects Iraq's terrorism index TI. And, applying the ARMA model for forecasting annual terrorism index in Iraq.

1.6 The Hypotheses

i. Panel data analysis hypotheses comprise of:

1. The first model, hypothesizes an inverse relationship between GDP growth and economic globalization with terrorism. While, inflation and unemployment are expected to be positively correlated with terrorism.
2. The second model, assumes that GDP growth, economic globalization, and political stability exhibit an inverse relationship with terrorism. On the other hand, inflation, demographic pressures, and external interventions are expected to have a positive relationship with terrorism.

ii. The hypotheses of the time series study of Iraq

3. Considering the time series ARDL model of Iraq, the researcher hypothesizes that increase in inflation rate, income inequality, and unemployment rate, increase terrorism. While increase in GDP growth rate, and political stability lead to decrease terrorism threats in Iraq.
4. One standard deviation innovation to the predictor may have substantial impacts on terrorism index in the short run, but the impact will decline and be steady in the long run.
5. Iraq Terrorism index may decline within the long run future time frame Forecasting's.

1.7 The Scope and the Samples

This study has been carried out on two different data samples as follows:

- i. Annual balanced panel data for seven selected countries, from year 2000 to 2021. The countries included in the study are coded as follows: 1. Iraq, 2. Afghanistan, 3. Democratic Republic of the Congo, 4. Nigeria, 5. Pakistan, 6. Syria, and 7. Yemen.
- ii. Annual time series data of the state of Iraq during 2000-2020.

1.8 Structure of the Study

This study consists of five chapters, the first chapter involves an introduction and a review of various literatures about terrorism economics. The second chapter deliberates the concepts, theories, the studied variables, and facts concerning terrorism across the world. The third chapter is about panel data analysis of the selected countries under investigation, the fourth chapter displays the empirical findings of time series models related to terrorism in Iraq, and the fifth chapter entails conclusions, recommendation, and suggested further studies in the field.

1.9 Data Sources

1.9.1 Data Sources for the Seven Selected Countries

- Terrorism Index (TI) (dependent variable): The Institute for Economics and Peace (IEP). Annual GTD reports, available via: <https://www.economicsandpeace.org/?s=terrorism>
- Inflation Rate (INF): World Bank, available via: <https://data.worldbank.org>
- Gross Domestic Product Growth Rate (GDPG): World Bank, available via: <https://data.worldbank.org>
- Economic Globalization Index (G): “KOF Swiss Economic Institute”, available via: <https://kof.ethz.ch/en/forecasts-and-indicators/indicators/kof-globalisation-index.html>

- Unemployment Rate (UEM): World Bank, available via:
<https://data.worldbank.org>
- Political Stability Index (PS): World Bank, available via:
<https://www.theglobaleconomy.com>
- Demographic Pressures Index (DP): The Fund for Peace FFP, available via: <https://www.theglobaleconomy.com>
- External Intervention Index (EXI): The Fund for Peace FFP, available via: <https://www.theglobaleconomy.com>

1.9.2 Data Sources for Iraq-Related Time Series Variables:

- Terrorism Index (TI) (dependent variable): The Institute for Economics and peace (IEP), Annual GTD reports, available via:
<https://www.economicsandpeace.org/?s=terrorism>
- Inflation Rate INF: World Bank, available via:
<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/FP.CPI.TOTL.ZG?end=2021&locations=IQ&start=2001>
- Gross Domestic Product Growth Rate GDPG: World Bank, available via:
<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.MKTP.KD.ZG?locations=IQ>
- Income inequality index GINI , available via:
1) <https://tradingeconomics.com/iraq/gini-index-world-bank-estimate-wb-data.html> And, 2)
<https://www.statista.com/forecasts/1165124/gini-index-forecast-in-iraq>
- Unemployment Rate UEM: World Bank, available via:
<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SL.UEM.TOTL.NE.ZS?locations=IQ> and;
<https://www.macrotrends.net/countries/IRQ/iraq/unemployment-rate#>

- Political Stability Index PS: World Bank, available via:

https://www.theglobaleconomy.com/Iraq/wb_political_stability/

1.10 Literature Review

The science of economic terrorism is relatively new in the field of academic studies. The term ‘terroriste’, which means ‘terrorist,’ is used by the French philosopher François-Nol Babeuf in 1794, when he criticizes Maximilien Robespierre's Jacobin governance as a dictatorship. While the first scholar who applied the costs of crime and punishment was Gary Becker (1968). Many other scholars adopted economic style analysis to show the impact of terrorism on the economy and to examine the most economic indicators that might cause terrorism, such as; Sandler et al. 1983, Enders et al. 1992, Enders and Sandler 1993, 1995, 1999, 2000, 2001.

This study's literature review is divided into panel data studies and time series studies relating to terrorism economics, as follows:

1.10.1 Panel Data Studies

Goldstein (2005) had aims close to this study, as he employed relatively different approaches and factors. He studied the effect of several economic and social factors on terrorism in 105 countries. The findings show that unemployment has a significant correlation with terrorist risk. In addition to the factors mentioned earlier, political freedom, population fractionalization, and geography are also identified as determinants contributing to terrorism. Goldstein (2005) further asserts that an increase in the Gini coefficient is linked to a reduction in terrorism risk. However, no significant relationship has been found between GDP per capita and terrorism.

Crain and Crain (2006) estimated OLS regression models to show the impact of terrorism on GDP, GDP growth, investment, consumer expenditure,

and tourism for 147 countries during the period 1968–2002. The findings show that the potential benefits to a country from lowering terrorism are substantial, albeit particular estimates vary depending on a country's population, base level of output, and investment.

Piazza (2006) assesses the common belief that the root causes of terrorism are due to poverty, injustice, and poor economic development. He adopted multiple regression analyses for the casualties in ninety-six states, from 1986 to 2002. The results showed the significance of the variables of poverty, hunger, inequality, unemployment, inflation, and weak economic growth, as predictors of terrorism.

Abadie (2006) examined the effect of economic variables on terrorist attacks in 186 countries, in 2003–2004 and found that economic variables do not have significant effects on terrorism as political variables do. Therefore, Political freedom explains changes in terrorism attacks, but in a non-monotonic way. The analysis showed that terrorism threats are more in countries of middle ranges of political freedom, than countries with high levels of political freedom, or countries with extremely strict rules. During the periods of ruling shift from autocracy to democracy the country may go through temporary increases in terrorism, as occurred in Spain, Iraq, and Russia. The results also showed that geographic aspects are substantial to continue the terrorist activities. And each of human development index and GINI index have a negative relationship with terrorism index.

Sandler (2009) suggests that there are compelling reasons to explore the economic consequences of terrorism when considering the influence of terrorism on economic growth. First, the potential of terrorists to create public harm must be examined. This adversity might take the form of fatalities or economic losses. Second, GDP losses from terrorism are an important aspect to what is rescued by countering terrorism, which decreases attacks and so

raises growth. Third, the economic costs of terrorism must be calculated if compensatory economic stimulus programs or foreign aid to terrorist-affected states are to be assessed.

Kis-Katos, Liebert, and Schulze (2011) showed that terror is not rooted from economic deprivation. Powerful autocratic regimes do not produce more terror, while the source of terrorism comes from failing states, also, past conflicts. The likelihood of terrorism incidents increases with the increases in the level of GDP per capita, and is higher for more democratic states than for strongly authoritarian regimes. also agree on underlying reasons of local and transnational terrorism are identical. In general, the factors that play a part to increase the origins of terrorism are; domestic conflict, anarchy and regime transitions.

Richardson (2011) examined the interaction effect of unemployment and higher education, and their correlation with terrorist attacks, during 1980-2008, across 56 countries. The results propose that interaction is rather significant in countries of previous terrorist attacks. Increases in unemployment rates, and population, are correlated positively with number of terrorist incidents, while higher education relationship with terrorism is insignificant.

Caruso and Schneider (2011) studied the impact of Socio-Economic causes of terrorism, and political violence, in a sample of 12 countries in Western Europe, during 1994-2007. Their findings showed; 1) Lowering the set of current economic opportunities is increasing people's willingness to perform terrorism. 2) Increase in economic growth might increase terrorism, which supports the Immiserizing Modernization Theory. 3) With increase of GDP per capita by 1% the change in the anticipated number of terrorist incidents decreases by 5.5%. But if 1% increase in youth unemployment increase terrorist activities by 0.5%, this finding supports the economic deprivation theory.

Nasir, Ali, and Rehman (2011) argue that income inequality is the primary cause of terrorism. Based to their study, those who are denied their political rights are more likely to engage in terrorist acts.

Gaibulloev and Sandler (2011) conducted a study that confirmed the negative and significant effect of transnational terrorism on per capita income growth. However, they found that the minor impact on per capita growth caused by domestic terrorism is not substantial.

Meierrieks and Gries (2013) proposed that economic growth had an impact on terrorism in Latin American countries, particularly those experiencing political instability, leading to significant terrorist activity during the Cold War era. On the other hand, African and Islamic countries with low levels of political openness and high levels of political instability faced heightened terrorist activities in the post-Cold War era. The study also found that a higher level of international economic and social integration resulted in a reduction in terrorist events. Specifically, when there is a negative relationship between economic globalization and terrorism, while social and political globalization showed no significant correlation.

Santifort-Jordan and Sandler (2014) proved that Economic, political, and military variables, influence the suicide terrorism. As GNI per worker, unemployment, counterterrorism expenditures, and democracy are being the main determinants that affect terrorism.

Saha and Yap (2014) conducted a study that revealed how a country's political conflicts and terrorism can negatively impact its tourism industry. They found that the effect of political instability on tourism is more severe than the impact of a single terrorist attack. Surprisingly, without prior notice, they revealed that terrorist attacks increase tourism demand in low- to moderate-political-risk countries. However, countries with high levels of political risk

might experience significant reductions in their tourism businesses. Furthermore, the combination of political instability and terrorism could lead to the eradication of the tourism industry.

Bezich, Galovich, and Mishevich (2016) conclude that terrorism and several other economic factors reduce the inflows of FDI, due to loosing investors' confidence, safety, and security.

Chuku, Abang, and Isip (2017) conducted a study to examine the growth pace and fiscal costs of terrorism in Nigeria during the years 2012 and 2013. The findings revealed an inverse relationship between terrorism and economic growth in the country. The estimated cost of terrorism in terms of annual GDP losses amounted to 0.82%. Moreover, terrorism led to a shift in economic activity from private investment to government spending. As a result, the structure of government spending underwent changes, with the defense component of government expenditure increasing compared to other items. The study also highlighted the significance of dynamic interactions between terrorism and macroeconomic determinants.

In their study Ilyas, Mehmood, and Aslam (2017), investigated the contributions of poverty and terrorism to stifling economic development in 22 African countries. Their findings confirmed that both poverty and terrorism have a long-term negative impact on economic growth.

Çinar (2017) found that terrorist attacks cause a negative impact on the economic growth, particularly in low-income countries, about three times more than high income countries.

Rizvi, and Végazonès-Varoudakis (2019) studied 58 fragile countries during the years 2004 and 2017 to determine the institutional, social, and economic factors that influence internal conflicts, including terrorism, using the Fixed Effect Poisson Regression FEPR. The results show that increased

incomes and effective institutions might lessen conflict in these countries. While, democracy increases conflicts in fragile countries. Also, human development factor doesn't aid conflict and terrorism lessening. The study concluded that fragile countries priority is to improve the social, economic, and institutional settings before they can obtain political and educational improvements. The same is true for globalization, economic-related changes, which likewise don't seem to contribute to a decrease in violence and terrorism in fragile countries.

The main objective of Bren, Zeman and, Urban (2019) is to show the status of correlation between terrorism and many social, economic, and security-political factors throughout Spearman correlation coefficient as a statistical technique, for 162 countries in 2017. Their study concluded that social inequality, GDP, current war conflict, corruption and political instability have increased terrorism in the world in 2017. Inflation, which was measured by the changes in CPI over time, showed that there was no correlation between terrorism and CPI.

Korotayev, Vaskin and Tsirel (2019) agree that GDP development in medium and higher-income countries following some procedures to controls for unemployment, inequality, regime type, education, and so forth, are the increasing factors of the intensities of terrorist activities.

Saddiq, et al. (2020) analyzed a panel data for selected south Asian countries during the period of 1985-2018. They adopted Fixed Effect Model estimation to examine the key determinants of Terrorism and its Impact on economic growth. The results showed that higher literacy rate determines terrorism, unemployment is not leading terrorism. A terrorist act destroys the infrastructure; people are afraid to move for their work in a terrorized society these results in low production and makes demand greater than supply consequently high inflation rate.

Tahir (2020) found that high literacy rates, per capita GDP and political instability are the primary factors influencing terrorism. He observed that physical and human capital development have a decreasing effect on terrorism, whereas government consumption and inflation positively impact terrorism. The role of military expenditure is two-sided, with an inverse relationship with terrorism in Muslim countries and a direct relationship in non-Muslim countries. Regarding corruption, its impact on terrorism was found to be insignificant in the overall sample. However, when the sample was divided between Muslim and non-Muslim countries, a negative association between decreasing corruption and terrorism was observed. The study also identified bidirectional Granger causality relationships between several factors, one of which is between political instability and terrorism.

Bardwell and Iqbal (2020) found that the highest rate of global terrorism recorded in 2014, with 33,555 deaths, and economic impact of \$US 111 billion. Terrorism related deaths increased by 353% during 2011 to 2014, and terrorist incidents rose by 190%. They also agree that Iraq is the most affected country by terrorism over the period of 2003 and 2018. The incident of September 11, 2001 in the United States had the highest economic impact accounting for deaths and injuries of \$US 40.6 billion, this is followed by the Sinjar mass extermination in Sinjar-Iraq at \$US 4.3 billion. The economic impact of terrorism was \$US 33 billion in 2018, since 2000. In general, terrorism has cost the world economy by about \$US 855 billion.

Cruz, De Alessio, and Stolzenberg (2020) revealed that labor force participation was a significant predictor of a country's frequency of terror attacks.

Adelaja and George (2020) Used a cross-country panel data in USA covering the years 1996–2015. They found a direct relationship between youth unemployment, and domestic terrorism, given some factors of economic

growth such as; administration ineffectiveness and the absenteeism of law, and corruption. In the meantime, they found youth unemployment does not have a crucial impact on transnational terrorism.

Tejkal, Odehnal, and Michálek (2020) found that opportunity costs prompting people's behavior and decision-making regarding perpetration for terrorist attacks. Also, they concluded that the positive economic growth of a country naturally leads to a higher demand for work, a lower unemployment rate, and to a higher cost of labor, all of these reduce motivation for violent behavior.

Rajput, et al. (2021) estimated a Negative binomial regression model for the data of 195 countries during the years 1990 to 2017, to show the impact of economic, social and political globalizations on global terrorism incidents. they found that higher level of international economic and social integrations leads to a reduction in terrorist events. So, as per them there is a negative relationship between economic globalization and terrorism, while social and political globalization were insignificant. These results support the results of Meierrieks and Gries (2013).

Cross countries studies show that the level of economic development is very significant for causing political violence or terrorism (MacCulloch 2004). The growth in real GDP is adversely affects the likelihood of a revolt, and reduces poverty rates.

Countries of liberalism characteristics such as; export-oriented production, free trade, and foreign investment, have robust economies, which leads to democracy, and peace (Hegre, et al. 2003, 253). likewise, if there isn't democracy, the economic growth might go through short term peace due to the higher levels of welfare, which in turn gain the population support and state's legitimacy (Lipset 1963; Firebaugh and Beck 1994). Thus, the economic

development and growth have adverse relationship with political violence and terrorism.

1.10.2 Time Series Studies of Terrorism

Shahbaz and Shabbir (2011) investigated the effect of inflation on terrorist attacks in Pakistan, with occurrence of economic growth during the years 1970-2010, using ARDL, and moving average methods. The results revealed cointegration between terrorism, inflation, and the economic growth. At the meantime economic indicators of inflation, and economic growth are positively related with terrorist attacks. Furthermore, VECM of Granger-causality test shows a bidirectional causality between inflation and terrorism.

Shabaz (2013) applied the econometrics approaches of ARDL, rolling window to cointegration, and VECM of Granger-causality to examine the presence of cointegration between each of inflation, and economic growth with terrorism, in Pakistan during 1971-2010. The results showed bidirectional relationship between inflation and terrorism. However, in the short run terrorism causes the economic growth.

Malik and Zaman (2013) adopted the approaches of; Granger causality test, Cointegration theory, and variance analyses, to specify the factors that cause terrorism actions in Pakistan during the period 1975-2011. Relying on these approaches, the results of their study show that price levels, political instability, population growth, and poverty are the most significant factors causing terrorism in Pakistan. While other factors haven't any long- run relationship with terrorism, such as; unemployment, foreign trade, and income inequality. the Granger causality test of all macroeconomic indicators had unidirectional causality with terrorist actions except for unemployment, which had a bi-directional causality.

Ismail and Amjad (2014) adopted the Error Correction Model (ECM) via Johansen Cointegration technique, and impulse response IR, to analyze the impact of various socio-economic variables on terrorism in Pakistan. The variables involved are; GDP per capita, unemployment, political rights, inflation, poverty, inequality and literacy level. The results showed that inflation, depression, per capita GDP, and poverty have a significant effect on terrorism. In the short run, some factors such as; inequality, unemployment, and literacy were insignificant. Concerning the long run, the factors of; per capita GDP, Literacy, poverty, and inflation, have a significant impact on terrorism. Whereas depression, income inequality and unemployment are insignificant in long run.

Bukhari and Masih (2016) applied ARDL bounds test, and variance decomposition VDC and impulse response IR function to show the causal relationship of the variables of; economic growth, trade, unemployment, military spending, and education spending, with terrorist attacks in Pakistan for the period of 1970–2014. The results assert the Deprivation and Modernization concept, which states that each of poverty and underdevelopment facilitate terrorists' job for new recruits, meanwhile unequal economic growth might equally facilitate terrorism. In the short run trade and GDP affect terrorism significantly. The results of long-run model show positive and significant relationships between terrorism and each of GDP growth, and military spending, which suggest that augmented economic growth, and military spending increase terrorism.

Nurunnabi, and Sghaier (2018) adopted the ARDL model, and ECM to perceive the impact of some socioeconomic factors on terrorism, and examine the stability of long-term relationship between them in Tunisia for the period 1979–2015. They found that unemployment rate, political instability, and higher school enrollment rates positively and significantly affect terrorism. But,

per capita GDP and foreign direct investment FDI, have a negative and significant impact on terrorism.

Yaseen (2019) studied the performance of Iraqi labor market as the dependent variable with the presence of terrorism as the key independent variable, accompanied with several socioeconomic variables as controlling independent variables, in year 2007. She used OLS approach for the cross-section data, while fixed effect, random effect, and Probit models for the panel data part. The findings demonstrate that rising terrorism-related risks and expenses deter people from working fewer hours per week, earning lower salaries, and less job securities.

Mahmud (2020) studied the impact of terrorism on human development in Iraq through the indicators of education, health and income. He settles on the idea that terrorism is having a negative impact on education throughout increasing illiteracy rate in years 2005, 2010, 2011 to 10%, 21.9%, and 22.4 % respectively. The health system also affected badly where doctors became defenseless to murder and abduction; 1243 physicians left the country in 2004 this number decreased to 1166 in 2007, representing 94% and, 78% respectively. The value of Human development indicator of Iraq in year 1990 was at its highest 71.2%, while this rate declined to 62.2% in 2013 due to terrorism and political instability.

Omelicheva and Webb (2020) attempted to show the effect of some socio-economic determinants at the Federal Russia's individual and group levels, during the period 2008-2016. They adopted the methods of Negative Binomial Regression, and Probit Regression. The results show increases in the rates of unemployment and inflation, at the individual level, led to increases in terrorist activities. While at the group level, the economic crises induce terrorism. In addition, an increase in the amount of accessible financial

resources increases the rate of terrorism, which is consistent with opportunity-based theories of political violence.

Sanso-Navarro, Gracia, and Cabello (2021) studied the determinants of terrorism in Colombia during 2001–2014. They adopted the Bayesian Model Averaging BMA technique to deal with the uncertainty over the control variables by the robustness tests. The findings showed that the variables of more robust relationship with terrorism are; employment rate, percentage of urban population, and income inequality. The determinates of employment rate, percentage of urban population, and business sector importance, are related to terrorism inversely, while the regions of high-income inequality are positively impacted by terrorism.

1.11 The Study's Contribution

The literature presented about the role of the factors influencing terrorism are appreciated efforts undertaken in the field of studying economics of terrorism. However, this dissertation presents a new contribution in this field by studying the economic factors affecting terrorism in those countries most vulnerable to it, during the most difficult period, which is the past two decades, that is, from the years 2000 to 2021. Due to the emergence of multiple types of terrorist groups that have interests in creating panic through political, economic and social instability in many countries, especially the countries selected for this study through panel data analysis. By taking the terrorism index as a dependent variable the impact of some economic factors like GDP growth, inflation rate, unemployment rate, and economic globalization index, are examined in both the long-run and the short-run time span, via construction panel data linear models. And other extra political and demographic factors are added to the economic factors to another constructed model, such as the

indicators of; political stability, external interventions, and demographic pressures. The results are shown in chapter 3 of this dissertation.

To the best of the researcher's knowledge, no econometric analysis was undertaken prior to this current study in order to highlight the most important economic and political elements that create terrorism in Iraq throughout the last two decades from 2000 to 2020. Iraq was the country most exposed to the risks of terrorist operations, according to data from the Global Terrorism Index (GTI). For this purpose, a linear ARDL model constructed to reveal the short and long-run impact of; GDP growth rate, inflation rate, unemployment rate, GINI coefficient, and the political stability index, on Iraq's terrorism index. Then, impulse response analysis conducted in the VAR system to understand how would be the effects of the shocks in these variables on Iraq's terrorism index in short and long-run time span. And finally, to predict what will be the index of terrorism in Iraq in the short and long-run future trends, using the ARMA model. The findings regarding Iraq's models are presented in Chapter four of this study.

Table 1.1 Sum mary of Relevant Literatures to Panel Data Studies

Authors	Method	Place and Time	The Studied Factors	Conclusions
Goldstein (2005)	POLS	186 countries in 2003.	Specifying the determinants of terrorism like poverty, political freedom, population division, and other country features.	Unemployment, political freedom, population division, geography, and GINI coefficient have significant relationship with terrorism, while GDP per capita doesn't.
Piazza (2006)	A series of multiple regression analyses.	96 states from 1986 to 2002.	Assesses poverty, injustice, and poor economic development as causes of terrorism.	Approved the significance of the variables of poverty, hunger, inequality, unemployment, inflation, and weak economic growth as predictors of terrorism.
Crain and Crain, 2006	OLS	147 countries for the period 1968–2002.	Terrorism's impact on GDP, GDP growth, investment, consumer expenditure, and tourism is estimated.	The findings show that the potential benefits to a country from lowering terrorism are substantial, albeit particular estimates vary depending on a country's population, base level of output, and investment.
Abadie (2006)	OLS	186 countries, in 2003–2004	GTI and GDP per capita, Human Development Index (HDI), country Gini Index. Political Rights index PRI, geographic, ethnic and linguistic factors.	Changes in terrorist incidents are explained by political independence and geographical factors, but not in a regular way. While GDP per capita, human development index and GINI are not having a significant effect on terrorism index.
Gaibullov and Sandler, 2011	Fixed-effects estimation of panel estimation.	51 African countries for 1970–2007	To examine the adverse effects of domestic and transnational terrorism on income per capita growth.	The findings suggest that transnational terrorism has a significant, but uncertain, marginal impact on per capita income growth. But, domestic terrorist actions haven't significant impact on income per capita growth.
Richardson (2011)	POLS	56 countries 1980-2008	Inspected terrorist attacks to show how interaction between unemployment and higher	This interaction is rather significant in countries where there have been facing terrorist attacks in past. Unemployment and the size of population are

Authors	Method	Place and Time	The Studied Factors	Conclusions
			education is affecting the number of terrorist attacks.	strongly correlated with terrorism, while higher education hasn't.
Piazza (2011)	Negative binomial regression.	172 countries from 1970 to 2006.	Poverty and domestic terrorism.	Domestic terrorist attacks are more likely to occur in countries with more economic discrimination against minority groups and is a powerful and practical predictor of domestic terrorism.
Nasir, Ali, and Rehman (2011)	The negative binomial regression.	5 countries during 1972 to 2006.	To show the impact of some socioeconomic determinants on terrorism.	Income inequality, and high literacy rate are the major causes of terrorism. Deprivation of political rights increases terrorist activities.
Kis-Katos, Liebert, and Schulze (2011)	Negative binomial approach.	159 countries during the years 1970 to 2007	To analyze the determinants of the origin of domestic and international terrorism.	The factors that may participate to increase the origins of terrorism are; domestic conflict, anarchy and regime transitions.
Caruso and Schneider (2011)	Panel negative binomial regression	12 countries in Western Europe, during 1994-2007.	Socio-economic factors influence terrorism, with dependent variables including victims and incidents, and independent variables like GDP, unemployment, and inflation.	1% investment share increases terrorist occurrences by 3%, and victims per accident positively correlate with real GDP per capita. 2) A 1% increase in GDP per capita changes the anticipated number of terrorist incidents - by 5.5%, and 1% increase in youth unemployment explains a 0.5% increase in terrorist activities.
Meierrieks, and Gries (2013)	Granger non-causality method.	160 countries during the years 1970 to 2007.	to examine the relationship between terrorism and economic growth.	economic growth affected terrorism in Latin American countries, while the African and Islamic countries had strong terrorist activity in post-Cold war era.
Santifort-Jordan and Sandler, 2014	Zero-inflated negative binomial, negative binomial,	1998–2010 Applied on 2448 suicide terrorist incidents	Economic, political, and military variables, at times, differentially influence suicide terrorism.	GNI per worker, unemployment, counterterrorism expenditures, and democracy are the main determinants that affect terrorism significantly which are executed by suicide missions.

Authors	Method	Place and Time	The Studied Factors	Conclusions
	and, linear regression.	around the world.		
Saha and Yap (2014)	POLS, FEM, and REM.	139 countries for the period 1999–2009	To reveal how a country's political conflicts and terrorism can negatively impact its tourism industry.	Terrorist attacks increased tourism demand in low-to moderate-political-risk countries. However, countries with high levels of political risk might experience significant reductions in their tourism businesses.
Bezhich, Galovich, and Mishevich (2016)	dynamic panel analysis GMM	A sample of 29 European countries during 2000-2013	Terrorism and several other economic factors on the inflows of FDI.	Terrorism and terrorist movements affect the inflow of Foreign Direct Investment FDI adversely, due to losing the investors' confidence, safety, and security.
Ilyas, Mehmood, and Aslam (2017)	DFE, MG, and PMG.	22 African countries from 1970 to 2013.	To explore the roles of poverty and terrorism in hindering the economic growth.	Both of poverty and terrorism have a long-term negative impact on economic growth.
Çinar (2017)	FEM, and REM.	115 countries during years 2000-2015.	examined the effects of terrorism on economic growth.	The finding show that terrorist attacks are causing a negative impact on the economic growth, particularly in low-income countries, about three times more than high income countries.
Cruz et al., 2018	POLS	2011-2016 in 127 countries.	To investigate the causal relationships between numerous labor market indicators and reported terrorist.	Labor force participation was a significant predictor of the number of terror attacks. There is no indication that young unemployment or the unemployment rate has an influence on terrorism.
Asmara Yaseen 2019	POLS, FEM, REM. and, a Probit model.	Iraq, monthly data in 2007.	Terrorist activities on survey respondents' employment status, throughout 12 months in 2007.	Negative significant relationship between the survey respondent's employment status and terrorist occurrences across all different specifications.

Authors	Method	Place and Time	The Studied Factors	Conclusions
Bren, Zeman and, Urban (2019)	Spearman correlation coefficient.	for 162 countries in 2017	To show the status of correlation between terrorism and many social, economic, and security-political factors	Social inequality, GDP, current war conflict, corruption and political instability have increased terrorism in the world in 2017. There is no significant correlation between terrorism and CPI.
Rizvi, and Véganzonès-Varoudakis (2019)	Fixed Effect Poisson Regression FEPR	58 fragile countries during the years 2004 and 2017	To determine the institutional, social, and economic factors that influence internal conflict including terrorism.	Increased incomes and effective institutions might lessen conflict, while, democracy increases conflicts. The factors of Human development, globalization, economic-related changes don't aid conflict and terrorism lessening.
Tahir (2020)	FEM, and REM.	94 countries from 2005 to 2016.	Examining terrorism's relationship with income, instability, corruption, and military spending.	High literacy rates, per capita GDP, and political instability are key factors influencing terrorism. Military expenditure has a two-sided relationship with terrorism in Muslim and non-Muslim countries, with bidirectional Granger causality.
Tejkal1, Odehnal, and Michálek1, 2020	Factor analysis is HCA, And correlation analysis	selected 16 European countries during 1960–2017	To measure the connection between terrorist attacks and socioeconomic and political.	Opportunity costs drive people's decision-making on terrorist attacks, as economic expansion leads to increased demand for work, lower unemployment, and higher labor costs, influencing economic deprivation and motivation.
Adelaja and George (2020)	Negative binomial regression	Used a cross-country panel data in USA covering the 1996–2015.	Youth unemployment and domestic terrorism through using a cross-country panel database.	Positive relationship between youth unemployment and domestic terrorism. Also, they found youth unemployment is not having a crucial impact on transnational terrorism.
Saddiq, Parveen, Ali,	Fixed Effect Model estimation	Panel data is used for the period of 1985-	To examine the key determinants of Terrorism and its Impact on economic growth.	Higher literacy rate determines terrorism, unemployment is not leading terrorism.

Authors	Method	Place and Time	The Studied Factors	Conclusions
and Ahmed (2020)		2018 for selected south Asian countries.		A terrorist act destroys the infrastructure; people are afraid to move for their work in a terrorized society these results in low production and makes demand greater than supply consequently high inflation rate.
Rajput, et al. (2021)	Negative binomial regression.	195 countries during the years 1990 to 2017.	To show the impact of economic, social and political globalizations on global terrorism incidents.	The higher level of international economic and social integrations leads to a reduction in terrorist events. There is a negative relationship between economic globalization and terrorism, while social and political globalization were insignificant.

Table 1.2 Summary of Relevant Literatures to Iraq Time Series Study

Authors	Method	Place and Time	The Studied Factors	Conclusions
Shahbaz and Shabbir (2011)	ARDL, and moving average, and VECM Granger-causality test.	Pakistan during the years 1970-2010.	Investigated the effect of inflation on terrorist attacks with occurrence of economic growth.	The findings approved cointegration between inflation, economic growth and terrorism. Inflation and economic growth are having positive relationships with terrorist attacks. And a bidirectional causality between inflation and terrorism exists.
Shahbaz (2013)	ARDL bounds tests, cointegration, and VECM Granger causality.	Pakistan during 1971-2010.	To show robust cointegration between inflation, economic growth and terrorism.	Increase in inflation, and economic growth are major factors of terrorism. Bidirectional relationship found between inflation and terrorism, and terrorism unidirectional ganger causes the economic growth.
Malik and Zaman (2013)	Granger causality test, Cointegration, and variance analyses	Pakistan during the period 1975-2011	To specify the factors that cause terrorism actions in Pakistan.	Price levels, political instability, population growth, and poverty are the most significant factors causing terrorism in Pakistan. Granger causality test shows unidirectional causality for the studied indicators, except for unemployment, which had bidirectional causality.
Ismail and Amjad, 2014	Error Correction model ECM, and impulse response analysis IRA.	Pakistan, during 1972-2011.	Terrorism and various socio-economic variables like GDP per capita, unemployment, political rights, inflation, poverty, inequality and literacy level.	Inflation, repression, GDP per capita, and poverty significantly impact terrorism in the short run, while inequality, literacy, and unemployment are insignificant. Long-term factors like literacy, GDP, poverty, and inflation significantly impact terrorism, while repression, inequality, and unemployment are insignificant.

Authors	Method	Place and Time	The Studied Factors	Conclusions
Gulzar and Zhaohua, 2016	The NLS and ARMA (least square regression).	Annual time series from 2001 to 2014.	To show the role of economic factors on terrorism in Pakistan.	The economic factors of unemployment, income inequality, GDP per capita, literacy rate, population density and inflation rate show positive and significant impacts on terrorism.
Bukhari and Masih, 2016	ARDL bounds tests, variance decomposition VD, impulse response IR.	Pakistan for the period of 1970–2014	To determine the causal relationship of the variables of economic growth, trade, military spending, education spending and unemployment on the onslaught of terrorism in Pakistan.	Underdevelopment, poverty, and income inequality contribute to terrorism recruitment. Trade and GDP impact terrorism in the short run, while GDP growth and military spending have positive long-term relationships. The first relationship is due to income inequality and modernization, while the second is due to government asymmetric military spending.
Nurunnabi, and Sghaier, 2018	ARDL, error correction model, bound testing.	Tunisia for the period 1979–2015.	Some socioeconomic factors and terrorism, also to check for stability of any long-term relationship between them.	Factors of unemployment, political instability, the private sector and higher school enrollment rates positively and significantly affect terrorism. However, per capita GDP and FDI have a negative and significant impact on terrorism.
Asmara Yaseen 2019	OLS Estimation with Probit models.	Iraq, weekly worked hours in 2007.	To show the impact of per week working hours on terrorist attacks, and civilian fatalities.	The number of hours worked per week drops as endangerment costs rise, and the quantity of the household's previous paycheck lowers.
Farhani, and Sekrafi, 2019	ARDL	Tunisia from 1979 to 2015	Some socio-economic variables such as per capita GDP, unemployment, political stability, poverty, the informal sector and higher levels of education	Unemployment, political instability, informal sector, and higher education enrollment significantly impact terrorism, while GDP per capita and foreign direct investment negatively impact it.
Mahmud (2020)	Descriptive study	Iraq during 2003 to 2014	Studied the impact of terrorism on human development in Iraq through the indicators of education, health and income.	Terrorism negatively impacts education, health systems, and human development indicators in Iraq. Illiteracy rates have increased to 10%, 21.9%, and 22.4% in 2005, 2010, and 2011 respectively. The

Authors	Method	Place and Time	The Studied Factors	Conclusions
				country's human development indicator has declined from 71.2% in 1990 to 62.2% in 2013.
Naz, Jabeen, and Nasir, 2021	ARDL and error correction model ECM	Pakistan during 1970 to 2019	Three types of Instabilities such as Political instability, macroeconomic instability, economic growth, and terrorism.	Political instability, macroeconomic instability, and unemployment contribute to terrorism, with inflation. Meanwhile inflation affects investment and purchasing power. Long-term relationships exist between inflation, GDP, and other macroeconomic factors.
Khokhlov and Korotayev, 2022	Negative binomial regression models.	time-series cross-sectional data from 1970 to 2018.	To investigate the relationship between the total number of internet access and the severity of terrorist attacks.	Internet access negatively impacts terrorist attacks in democracies, but not in autocracies; Its impact depends on political system and socioeconomic development.

CHAPTER TWO: CONCEPTS, THEORIES, AND WORLDWIDE TERRORISM

2.1 Preface

Terrorism is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon that has been studied extensively by scholars, policymakers, and analysts around the world. Understanding terrorism requires a nuanced exploration of various concepts and theories that attempt to explain its origins, motivations, tactics, and impacts. This chapter provides an overview of some key concepts and theories in the study of terrorism. It introduces the fundamental principles, theories, and economics of terrorism, depending on case studies and some scholar viewpoints. A light has been shed on various facts, information, and data regarding terrorism in the seven chosen countries. It also demonstrates the impact of terrorism on the global economy with its humanitarian costs. By examining these concepts and theories, scholars and practitioners seek to deepen our understanding of terrorism and develop more effective strategies for preventing and mitigating its destructive impacts on societies worldwide.

2.2 Violence and Conflict

Violence and conflict are inherent features of human society, often arising from a multitude of factors such as competition over resources, ideological differences, political grievances, ethnic or religious tensions, and social inequality. Understanding the dynamics of violence and conflict is essential for fostering peace, stability, and social cohesion. Violence conflicts frequently occur in three modes: terrorism, guerrilla war, and military war; Table 2.1 illustrates the characteristics of each.

Table 2. 1 Characteristics and Modes of Violent Conflict

Characteristics	Conventional Military	Guerrilla	Terrorism
Unit size in battels	Large (armies, corps, division).	Medium (platoons, companies, battalions)	Small (usually less than 10 persons)
Weapons	Full range of military hardware, (air force, armor, artillery, etc.)	Mostly infantry-type weapons but sometimes artillery pieces as well.	Hand guns, hand grenades, assault rifles, and specialized weapons e.g.; Car bombs, remote-control bombs, barometric pressure bombs.
Tactic	Usually, joint operation involving kidnapping, several militaries' branches.	Commando-type tactics.	Specialized tactics: kidnapping, assassinations, car bombings, hijacking, barricade-hostage, etc.
Targets	Mostly military units, industrial and transportation infrastructure.	Mostly military, police, and administration staff, as well political Opponents.	State symbols, political opponents, and the public at large.
Intended impact	Physical destruction	Mainly physical attrition of the enemy.	Psychological Intimidation.
Control Of territory	Yes	Yes	No
Uniform	Wear uniform	Often wear uniform	Do not wear uniform
Recognition of war zones	War limited to recognized geographical zones.	War limited to the country in strife.	No recognized war zones. Operations carried out worldwide.
International legality	Yes, if conducted by rules.	Yes, if conducted by rules.	No
Domestic legality	Yes	No	No
* Economic and financial resources	State	State opposition allies.	Illegal acquisition and confiscation of human and financial resources.

Source: Ariel Merari, Terrorism, in 4 Encyclopedia of Human Behavior 399, 401 (V.S. Ramachandran ed., 1994). Cited from: Schmid, Alex. "Terrorism - the Definitional Problem." Case Western Reserve University School of Law Scholarly Commons, n.d. <https://scholarlycommons.law.case.edu/jil/vol36/iss2/8>. pp. 383-384.

* Added by the researcher, 2023.

The characteristics presented in Table 2.1 are too general, yet they may interact in certain situations. For example, in 2014, ISIS occupied Mosul and

Sinjar. These two territories had been occupied for almost four years. Also, the military and guerrilla forces sometimes perform terrorist operations, such as exploding automobiles or assassinating particular people. However there exists a legal threshold that separates these types of actions.

2.3 Concepts Related to Terrorism

The concepts related to terrorism, including definition of terrorism, locations of terrorism, classification of terrorism, types of terrorism tactics and victims, the nexus of economic inequality – political conflicts, and terrorist attack vulnerability evaluation TAVE, are all explained in the following sections.

2.3.1 Definition of Terrorism

Terrorism is exceptionally hard to describe, yet most terrorism researchers agree on its basic characteristics in common. Although not all of these characteristics apply in every case, terrorism is distinguished from other forms of violence in that it targets unarmed civilians and/or noncombatants, employs extra-normal violence, seeks to instill fear in the target population, and seeks to achieve political objectives by trying to influence more people beyond those who are directly impacted of the attack (Berger Hobson and Moghadam 2023, 2).

There are different definitions of terrorism concept. Each organization or researcher defines terrorism as it sees fit with his thinking about the behavior of the perpetrator of the operation. Thus, according to many literatures' terrorism is a very problematic concept to define.

In a terrorism related resolution, the United Nation (2004) defines terrorism as:

“Criminal acts, including against civilians, committed with the intent to cause death or serious bodily injury, or taking of hostages, with the purpose to provoke a state of terror in the general public or in a group of

persons or particular persons, intimidate a population or compel a government or an international organization to do or to abstain from doing any act”².

Global Terrorism Database (GTD), adopts La Free et al. (2015) definition of terrorism, as;

“Terrorism is the threat or use of violence to intimidate or coerce in the pursuit of political or ideological goals. It is usually understood to be done by non-state actors — individuals or organizations not part of the government.”³

Enders and Sandler (2011) defines terrorism as;

“Terrorism is the premeditated use or threat to use violence by individuals or subnational groups to obtain a political or social objective through the intimidation of a large audience beyond that of the immediate victims.”⁴

According to terrorism studies specialist Jessica Stern;

"The student of terrorism is confronted with hundreds of definitions in the literature."⁵

During this period, however, scientists focused on the economics of terrorism, which led to the formation of an accepted definition that is now frequently used in economic research. It is based on the US State Department's definition and is generally utilized because it employs precise language and eliminates terms that generate uncertainty in classification, such as "often" and "especially" (Sandler 2013). So, the United States Department of State defines terrorism as:

² UN, Resolution 1566, 2004.

³ Bastian Herre, “Terrorism,” Our World in Data, December 28, 2023, <https://ourworldindata.org/terrorism#:~:text=The%20GTD%20defines%20a%20terrorist,technical%20article%20on%20the%20GTD>.

⁴ Walter Enders, and Todd Sandler. “The Political Economy of Terrorism”. Cambridge University Press, 2011.

⁵ Stern, Jessica. 2004. Terror in the Name of God: Why Religious Militants Kill. <https://www.amazon.com/Terror-Name-God-Religious-Militants/dp/0060505338>

“Terrorism means premeditated, politically motivated violence perpetrated against noncombatant targets by subnational groups or clandestine agents, usually intended to influence an audience.”⁶

The Arab agreement on terrorism, defines terrorism as:

“Any act or threat of violence, whatever its motives or purposes, that occurs in the advancement of an individual or collective criminal agenda and seeking to sow panic among people, causing fear by harming them, or placing their lives, liberty or security in danger, or seeking to cause damage to the environment or to public or private installations or property or to occupying or seizing them, or seeking to jeopardize national resources.”⁷

Glaeser (2002) created supply and demand models for hatred, which is a major element in terrorism and crime. Believing that political leaders create hatred because it helps them achieve their policy goals. That is, if we want to eliminate hatred, we must try to change the incentives that both suppliers and consumers of hatred face.

Because there are no specific standards for terrorism, scholars are free to create a general definition and apply it to all countries throughout the world (LaFree and Schwarzenbach 2021b, 192). Therefore, after considering the aforementioned concepts, the researcher defines terrorism as:

Act of generating fear, intimidation, and inflicting physical, psychological, and economic harm to civilians in order to obtain illegal gains and positions.

⁶ “22 U.S. Code § 2656f - Annual Country Reports on Terrorism,” LII / Legal Information Institute, n.d., <https://www.law.cornell.edu/uscode/text/22/2656f>.

⁷ The Arab Convention for the Suppression of Terrorism, Cairo, Egypt, 1998.

2.3.2 Locations of Terrorism

In general, terrorism locations can be categorized into two main types, as defined by Enders and Sandler (2012):

i. Domestic terrorism

This type of terrorism is rooted within the country itself and primarily affects the host country. It involves attacks on the country's establishments, inhabitants, properties, and governance. The perpetrators, victims, and residents involved in domestic terrorism are all from the same country. The consequences of domestic terrorism are confined within the borders of the source country.

ii. Transnational terrorism

This form of terrorism begins in one country but has repercussions in another country. It involves incidents that cross national borders and affect multiple countries. For examples airplane hijackings in country X with intentions to reach country Y, or the blast of an explosive device that causes casualties or injuries to people from two or more countries.

The origins of the two types of terrorism, discussed above, might arise from different causes, such as instabilities in the prices of food items which influence domestic terrorism rather than transnational terrorism. In fact, each type of terrorism might affect a country's GDP growth differently. The transnational terrorism is probably having a higher marginal effect on any country's GDP growth because this type of terrorism reduces the foreign direct investment, which is considered as crucial source of income growth (Gaibulloev and Sandler 2008). Therefore, given the fact that our study is done at the level of seven countries, we also used the GDP growth rate and the globalization index as macroeconomic indicators.

Domestic terrorism is limiting and reducing financial returns, may be due to political instability and local protests. But transnational terrorism abroad has fewer damaging effects on financial markets (Kollias, Papadamou, and Arvanitis 2013).

The dynamic characteristics of these two types of terrorism are quite different. As per Enders, Sandler, and Gaibullov (2011) domestic terrorism causes transnational terrorism, but the reverse is not likewise.

2.3.3 Classification of Terrorism

Terrorism is a sort of expensive messaging that is intended to alter minds by executing bodies. Terrorists use five basic expensive signaling strategies: attrition, intimidation, provocation, spoiling, and outbidding. According to Davis and Cragin (2009, p.53), terrorism could be classified to:

- i- Criminal terrorism.
- ii- Ethno-nationalist.
- iii- Religious, or ideological.
- iv- Generic secular.
- v- Single issue.
- vi- Personal/idiosyncratic.
- vii- State-sponsored.

Mainly there are three types of ideological terrorism such as left-wing terrorism, right-wing terrorism, and religious terrorism, described as follows:

A. Left-Wing terrorism

Left wing terrorism origins was detected in the 19th and early 20th century which worked like radical terrorism. Later known as modern left-wing terrorism, established in the basis of the political conflict of 1968. Many groups of left-wing terrorism organized in Western Europe such as Red Army Faction RAF in Germany, Red Brigades in Italy, Action Direct (AD) in France, the

Communist Combatant Cells (CCC) of Belgium. Also other terrorist groups developed in Europe such as The First of October Anti-Fascist Resistance Groups (GRAPO) which was a Maoist terrorist group in Spain. Irish National Liberation Army (INLA) was a communist follower that attempted to remove north Ireland from British authority. Also, the Popular Forces 25 April (FP-25) was another left-wing group organized in Portugal.

The Asian terrorist groups comprises of the Japanese Red Army, Liberation Tigers of Tamil Eelam, communist party of India and Nepal (Maoist). Pakhtoon Zalmay, Al-Zulfiqar (AZO), and Muhajir Qaiumi Movement (MQM) were left-wing terrorism groups in Pakistan.

The Latin America's terrorist groups were active during 1970s to 1980s included Sandinistas in Nicaragua, the Shining Path in Peru, and 19th April Movement in Colombia. The United States of America's left-wing terrorist groups drawn-up from Weather Underground and Students for a Democratic Society in 1973-1975 known as Symbionese Liberation Army. In 1980s movements like May 19th Communist Organization and United Freedom Front were active. The activities of left-wing terrorism almost all finished by the end of the Cold War.

B. Right-Wing or Far Right terrorism

This type of terrorism performed by groups that are involving in dangerous crimes for their political or ideological purposes. The forms of Right-Wing terrorism are; racialism, nationalism, fascism, anti-Semitism, and Neo-Nazism (Auger 2020).

Western Europe has shown a noticeable wave of modern right-wing terrorism in 1970s and after 1991 dissolution of Soviet Union.

Falk (2011) stated that right-wing terrorism causes or accompanied with Unemployment rate in a direct relationship. Also, Falk (2014) shows that economic growth encourages right-wing terrorism. Because the majority of right-wing terrorist operations take place in developed countries, and since the

standard of living there is high and secure and people have more freedom to express their opinions, and because of the role of human rights in those countries, terrorism is rising by right-wing extremist groups. And in another study Falk (2019) concluded that immigrants increase right-wing terrorism in Europe rather than economic factors do.

Greven (2016) sees that right-wing people are ethnocentrism and are against immigrants, and believe in the idea of “us versus them” that might creates terrorism. Moghadam and Eubank (2006) stating that white skinhead groups and their supporters are involving with right-wing terrorism. These kinds of groups are inspired in mass murders, that might use this technique to undertake future attacks. Such as the Australian named Tarrant who killed 51 people and injured 49 in a mosque, whom was influenced by Breivik, who did the 2011 attacks in Norway, and Roof who killed nine people in Charleston church in Australia.

C. Religion or Ideological Terrorism

Although religion is adopted to appreciate humanity principals, yet, many organizations exploit religion for their political, economic, and social advantages. Some of these organizations don't hesitate in using terrorism to achieve their aims.

If religion neglects love, friendliness, and kindness as its core, its droplets into the terrible twister of ideological view, for instance, the so called ISIS and Boko Haram, the two main ideas of today's terrorism. Therefore, any explanation that declares violence and acts of killing would be a meagre local reading of the religious texts, disturbed by determined intents pointing to political objectives (Masaeli and Sneller 2017, 9). This could be a misunderstanding of religion and an interpretation of it the way the perpetrators want it.

2.3.4 Types of Terrorism Tactics

Terrorist organizations have the ability to employ a wide range of terrorism tactics built on the conditions and anticipated chance of success. Some of the tactics are more conventional and broadly employed in the terrorism events. The following points are the more adopted types of terrorism tactics around the world, according to The Global Terrorism Trends and Analysis Center (GTTAC) classifications, (Annex of Statistical Information 2020, 44):

i- Suicide Attack

A suicide attack occurs when the attacker wants to die during the attack. These incidents frequently, but not always, include the deployment of a bomb or other explosives devices.

ii- Shooting

Shootings can also take the form of mass shootings, which are less targeted but significantly more lethal. Terrorists frequently utilize this approach to instill terror since the targets are either civilian or military and receive extensive media coverage. These mass shootings are frequently carried out by a single terrorist or a small group, although they typically require less manpower for greater harm.

Figure 2.1 Top 10 Tactics of Perpetrators in 2018-2020.

Source: 2020 Annex of Statistical Information, p.44.

Figure 2.1 shows that terrorist perpetrators who used shooting, bombing, planted mines, unclear, kidnaping, extortion, property damage, ambush, assault storming, and multiple location as tactics of terrorism. Shooting had the highest frequency during 2018 - 2020.

iii- Hostage-taking

In a hostage-taking, unlike a kidnapping, the victims are normally imprisoned at the location where they are abducted until the hostage-takers' terms are satisfied. Hostage-takers are frequently random persons who are caught at the scene of the incident.

iv- Kidnapping

The location and selection of the victims are the key distinctions between an abduction and a hostage-taking. Kidnapping tends to be more targeted, with offenders picking certain victims in advance, seizing control of them, and

transporting them to a new location. In a hostage situation, the victims might be random people who happen to be at the attack location.

v- Bombing

A bomb or munitions is used to destroy a targeted place or target. This category contains commercial explosives such as TNT, but it also includes vehicle bombs, postal bombs, and pipe explosives, as well as various sorts of Improvised explosive devices (IEDs) and suicide bombers.

vi- Mines/IEDs

Mines and Improvised Explosive Devices (IEDs) are antipersonnel explosives and antivehicle mines or IEDs carefully placed to limit access to an area, path, or structure.

2.3.5 Warfare Modes of Terrorist Organizations

Generally, there are three main sorts of militant attacks; terrorism, guerrilla, and hybrid. According to Berger Hobson and Moghadam (2023, p.6) the term "terrorist" refers to assaults against non-combatants and private institutions, as well as other targets through which the group intends to influence a larger audience than the immediate victims. Similarly, and in agreement with current scholarly ideas on guerrilla warfare and insurgencies, attacks on military and police targets classified as "guerrilla" tactics. Attacks against non-state militant and political actors with whom the armed organizations under consideration compete for support and influence are also included in the "guerrilla" category. Because the difference between terrorist and guerrilla targets is flexible, a "hybrid" target category classified for any strikes that potentially suit both a terrorist and a guerrilla goal.

Berger Hobson and Moghadam (2023) examined the occurrence of terrorism in 1,013 organizations as compared to guerrilla or hybrid tactics. Terrorism, as seen in Figure 2.2, is the most popular method, yet it is utilized

in just 40% of the almost 95,000 incidents in their database. To put it another way, in 60% of the attacks, militant groups favored guerrilla and hybrid tactics over terrorist techniques.

Figure 2. 2 Warfare Modes for all Terrorist organizations During 1970–2019

Source: Berger Hobson and Moghadam (2023, p. 9)

2.3.6 Types of Terrorism Victims

According to Annex of Statistical Information (2020, p.45), there are six recognized types of terrorism victims as the following:

- i- General Population or Unknown

This category includes peoples when there is little information on those who were harmed or when they appeared to have been attacked for no obvious reason regardless of the fact that they were present at the scene of the occurrence.

- ii- Identified by Gender

This classification involves circumstances when men or women make up a vast majority of the intended victims, such as assaults against women's schools.

iii- Identified by Race or Ethnicity

This category is employed in incidents when a single racial or ethnic community made up a significant proportion of the casualties and may become targeted because of their group identification.

iv- Perpetrators

This category documents any deaths or injuries among the attackers.

v- Pro-Government Forces

This category includes forces that support the government that operate within a country, regardless of whether they are paid or otherwise backed by the government, as long as they are not official forces of a national government.

vi- Other Violent Nonstate Actors

Members of rival groups, factions, persons in the perpetrator's group who are judged disloyal, or members of the perpetrator's own group who were accidental victims are all included in this category.

2.3.7 Economic Inequality – Political Conflicts Nexus

Studying economic inequality and political conflict (EI-PC) dated back to political theorists such as Aristotle, Plato, Machiavelli, de Tocqueville, Marx, and Madison attracted, for solving the (EI-PC) puzzle. This puzzle has been inspected by some of the main figures in modern political science such as Dahl, Lipset, and Huntington too. More recently Lichbach (1989) wrote on the Economic Inequality - Political Conflicts Nexus by asking a sample of his students, "Why Economic Inequality and Political Conflict, EI-PC, have been focused on their nexus and became a vital problem? And why are income and

wealth distribution explained as causes of political opposition that need close inspection?"⁸ their responses were as follows:

- i- Polarization of any community parts around prearranged staff has the main role in political competitions.
- ii- Unusual, unpredictable, and indecisive results deliver resources for theoretical and empirical reformations of the basic EI-PC problem formation.
- iii- Economic inequality is associated with; 1- social schism between regions, religions, classes, generations, genders, educational and job-related layers. 2- Ethnic, linguistic, and public clusters.
- iv- All main incidents of conflicts involved the issue of inequality, like the three extremism ideas of the socialism, nationalism, liberalism all of them produced revolutionary actions built on thoughts of equality.
- v- The EI-PC nexus studies escalate great constructive or normative questions such as; who is the winner and who is the loser? Why do society back up the authority entities? What limits the stability and change of these organizations? Specialists think that it is crucial to consider the great normative connections that humanities have to consider such as: effectiveness for equity, instruction for justice, or, political conflict due to income inequality. The normative measurement of the EI-PC question, furthermore, requests the range of thinking of political scholars such as: the left, the right, and the center. The left stands for the societies of fair distribution in income or equity which means economic equality. The right stands for politically diplomatic or societies prevailing peace efficiently. And the center stands for both fair or economic equality in income and peaceful societies, meaning equity and efficiency.

⁸ Lichbach, Mark Irving. "An Evaluation of 'Does Economic Inequality Breed Political Conflict?' Studies." *World Politics* 41, no. 4 (1989): 431–70. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2010526>.

2.3.8 Terrorist Attack Vulnerability Evaluation (TAVE)

Terrorist Attack Vulnerability Evaluation (TAVE) model was developed to specify three diverse segments of terrorism: the origins, the attacking procedure, and the post-attack impacts. As Estrada (2014) showed that TAVE-Model introduces a number of indicators, including economic growth, terrorist activity intensity, terrorist attack losses, economic wear under a potential terrorist attack, level of terrorist attack tension, level of terrorist attack monitoring, and total economic leaking under a potential terrorist attack. The origin of terrorist attacks detected through four issues such as; 1. historical, 2. religion and ideological, 3. economic decline, 4. civil society control. These four factors are affecting the level of terrorist attack tension of the TAVE-model.

Many irregular economic events might take place around the world which makes it go through a permanent disorder and has various levels of vulnerability with varied magnitudes. The factor of economic decline imposes arbitrary intervals, so as to analyze unanticipated shocks. The attack intensity affects the economic leaking, economic decline, and the losses, which will be directed to the same trend. According to Estrada et. al., (2015), there are nine important variables adopted to measure the intensity of terrorist attack:

- i- External military assistance.
- ii- Technological systems for anti-terrorist attack.
- iii- Army magnitude.
- iv- Strategy, information, and logistic systems.
- v- Natural and geographical environments.
- vi- Society backup.
- vii- Terrorist group experience.
- viii- Transportation, communications, and IT systems.
- ix- Industrial constructions.

Therefore, a strong economy, military and civilian intelligence, poverty reduction plans, and neutral system of justice, all of these are strong treatments for terrorism (Estrada et al., 2015).

2.4 Terrorism in Macroeconomic Theories

2.4.1 Immiserizing Modernization Theory in Terrorism

Political violence and social disorders are common when there is great wealth inequality as a result of rapid economic expansion, which creates numerous imbalances in any society. As Olson (1963) stated;

“[...] Economic growth – especially rapid economic growth – involves vast changes in the methods of production. It involves vast changes in the importance of different industries, in the types of labor demanded, in the geographical configuration of production. It means vast changes in the ways and places in which people live and work. Above all, economic growth means vast changes in the distribution of income [...]”⁹

Depending on Olson’s theory, there are two forces at work during a rapid economic growth: (1) Prices increase faster than earnings. That is to say, while the demand increases, the prices are expected to increase in the short run. In reverse, earnings are inflexible and do not change at the similar speediness. This inflexibility of earnings yields an extensive breakdown of a purchasing power of individuals. (2) Technological progress in some sectors shifts the labor demand towards more skilled workers. Consequently, the unskilled workers become a destabilizing force, which makes the process of economic growth irregular or uneven. Therefore, both factors lead to increase violence activities at least in the short-run.

The proposal of Shahbaz and Shabbir (2011) is; “Immiserizing modernization theory indicates that economic growth can fuel terrorist activities if fruits of

⁹ The American Interest LLC, “Growing Pains - the American Interest,” The American Interest, June 14, 2017, <https://www.the-american-interest.com/2006/09/01/growing-pains/>.

economic development could not be trickle-down to poor segments of population. The uneven economic growth raises income inequality and hence poverty. High level of poverty lowers the opportunity cost for poor individuals. Such an environment favors the terrorist organizations to recruit poor individuals for terrorist incidents”¹⁰. Therefore, economic growth causes decline in political violence and enhances terrorism.

2.4.2 The Rational Choice of Terrorism

Rational choice concept arose from Scottish and neoclassical economics. It elaborates what performers value to achieve by individual or collective actions. This evaluation process is applied to almost any noticeable behavior such as crime, political activities, and drugs addiction. Which, imposed on institutional structures, law, legislative and interest group politics, norms, ...etc. The most common parts of this theory involving; the examination of law, the theory of elections and voting, game theory, and group behavior studies. The power of rational choice concept achieved from the effort to decrease certain incentives to some fewer set of incentives, frequently to benefits, which is moderately sound, assessed by a large variety of backgrounds, and activities (Hardin, 2001).

The incentives to perform terrorism through perspectives of rational choice factors, show terrorism as a logical political choice among other choices (Crenshaw 1990). This choice assists terrorists to select violence. For instance, global mass media exposure of terrorist violence and its aims can be advantageous to the terrorist groups. Timing is another aspect of rational thinking of terrorist rational choices, such as an enemy’s national holiday, or anniversary of some specific event. Another example of the timing aspect is the blew up of the Alfred P. Murrah Federal Building, in Oklahoma City, on the

¹⁰ Shahbaz, Muhammad. 2011. “Is Hike in Inflation Responsible for Rise in Terrorism in Pakistan?” May 29, 2011. <https://econpapers.repec.org/RePEc:pra:mprapa:31236>.

second anniversary of the deaths of the Branch Davidians in Waco, Texas by Timothy McVeigh (Purpura 2013).

2.4.3 Relative Deprivation Theory and Terrorism

The deprivation theory proposes; if economic growth decreases income inequality rises, individual's discrepancy increases, therefore, people are less satisfied and henceforth poverty rises.

Dollard, Miller, et al. (1939) were the first to propose this theory, assuming that frustration leads men to perform violent actions. According to relative deprivation theory a gap between expected and achieved welfare, leads people to political violence as an alternative of an absolute standard of deprivation. Likewise, this theory applies to people who find their personal welfare to be lower to that of others to whom they compare themselves (Richardson 2011).

Ted Robert Gurr (1968) says;

“[...] my basic premise is that the necessary precondition for violent civil conflict is relative deprivation, defined as actors' perception of discrepancy between their value expectations and their environment's apparent value capabilities. Value expectations are the goods and conditions of life to which people believe they are justifiably entitled. The referents of value capabilities are to be found largely in the social and physical environment [...] For purposes of general theoretical specification I assume that perceived discrepancies between expectations and capabilities with respect to any collectively sought value – economic, psychosocial, political – constitute relative deprivation [...]”¹¹

Gurr (1970) also clarifies political violence as the result of people dissatisfaction triggered by a logic of relative deprivation. He inscribes,

¹¹ Gurr, Ted. 1968. “Psychological Factors in Civil Violence.” *World Politics* 20 (2): 245–78. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2009798>.

“Relative deprivation’ is the term... used to denote the tension that develops from a discrepancy between the ‘ought’ and the ‘is’ of collective value satisfaction, and that disposes men to violence.”¹² This break between an individual's predicted and attained welfare outcomes in public dissatisfaction.

Gurr (1970) brings a psychological method to clarify how public dissatisfaction is demonstrated as political violence stating:

“The primary source of the human capacity for violence appears to be the frustration aggression mechanism... the anger induced by frustration... is a motivating force that disposes men to aggression, irrespective of its instrumentalities.”¹³

Frustration is produced by relative deprivation, and the resulting anger is showed as terrorism (Richardson 2011). Levels of terrorism may be clarified partly as reactions of a country conditions stimulated by relative deprivation.

Agbibo (2013) suggests to resolve the Boko Haram dilemma in Nigeria practical considerations must be taken place to reduce poverty and economic deprivation. Because economic deprivation along with the inflated size of population are creating an environment in which radical rebel groups can prosper and legitimizes their activities.

2.4.4 Macroeconomic Determinants of Terrorism

Macroeconomic factors are key drivers of terrorism's opportunity costs. We provide numerous ideas that relate socioeconomic conditions to the creation of terrorism as well, based on the review and theory presented previously. Examples of such relation have been studied by: Krueger and Malečková; 2003, Goldstein; 2005, Abadie; 2006, Gaibulloev, and Sandler; 2011, Nasir, Ali, and Rehman; 2011, Tahir; 2020, Rajput, Khoso, Sial, Dakhan and Syed; 2021, and others. That is what we intend to demonstrate in

¹² Clare Richardson, “Relative Deprivation Theory in Terrorism: A Study of Higher Education and Unemployment as Predictors of Terrorism”, Senior Honors Thesis. 2011, p.5.

¹³ Gurr, Ted. 1970. *Why Men Rebel*. Princeton University Press, Princeton NJ.

our study as well, But in the world's seven most affected countries by terrorism risks. Therefore, the economic determinants have significant correlation with terrorism as political do, irrespective of the overall wealth of a country or region. For instance;

- i- High rates of inflation might have a significant impact on terrorism. As Shahbaz (2013) suggested; increase in inflation, and economic growth are major factors of terrorism.
- ii- Unemployment rate have a significant impact on terrorism; however, it explains a small share of the overall terrorist danger (Goldstein 2005). In many countries' youth raises the concerns about youth participation to terrorism and unrest due to unemployment and corruption and the absence of law. Therefore, youth unemployment has a direct relationship with domestic terrorism (Adelaja and George 2020).
- iii- Poverty is a big dilemma in each country, attempts for reducing its rates remain basic to the development process. Income inequality along with poverty should be taken into more consideration because both of the two factors might facilitate and create the appropriate circumstances for terrorist recruitment (Duffield 2005).
- iv- Due to black market transactions, 16 of 18 African countries have lost US\$97 billion each year (UNDP 2020) leading to increased violent. Therefore, in order to reduce violence, the policy makers must make decisions for sustainable development.
- v- Political independence, geography, and population classification have significant relationship with terrorism (Abadie 2004). In Nigeria political factors which represented by flawed parliamentary role have a significant role for producing terrorism, rather than situations of relative deprivation (Aron 2015).
- vi- The Gini Index of income inequality has a significant correlation with terrorism. The high rates of income inequality cause social instabilities that

in turn lead to violence or terrorism. This topic deals with the theory of relative deprivation, as it deals with the rule of law. Therefore, income inequality's role is more significant than a deterioration of socio-economic determinants (Krieger and Meierrieks 2016).

- vii- Human development has a bidirectional relationship with terrorism. Human development index measures the rate of population wellbeing status in the country. Considering the rate of Human development indicator of Iraq in year 1990, it was at its highest 71.2%, while this rate declined to 62.2% in 2013 due to terrorism and political instability. Terrorism has imposed harmful impact on wide-ranging human development in Iraq throughout: A. Increasing the number of dropouts which led to reduce the levels of education. B. Increasing the rates of illiteracy, Shortages on spending on education, destruction of schools, universities and scientific foundations. C. Falling levels of health services along with the increasing migration of doctors as a result of terrorist threats on their lives (Mahmud 2020).
- viii- Education has a noticeable role in recruiting people in terrorist groups. Looking at both sides of supply and demand of terrorism, however, Krueger and Maleckova (2003) are suggesting that; for some people with high degrees of education terrorism may offer more benefits, such as seeking for leadership positions, get identified with more respect than less educated persons, or they might get more wages than if they work in a legal institution, which is analogous application of occupational choice model of Roy (1951). Another cause is that terrorist groups hire more educated people due to their determination and commitment.

The demand of terrorism isn't paid much attention. The personal economic gains of suicide bombers are not promising, although their families might get some benefit which in turn might increase the willingness to participate in terrorist activities. But their basic passionate support for their program, and organization is more motivating to participate in terrorist activities. Therefore,

to Krueger and Maleckova (2003), poverty and low education levels are not substantial causes of terrorism.

Some literatures confirm that income inequality accompanied with population growth, survival stress, and political instability have positive significant effect on terrorism, particularly in limited geoeconomics countries. Such as, East and South Asia, Middle East and North Africa, and Sub-Saharan Africa. While, in some developed countries other factors related to foreign policy and politics cause terrorism (Coccia 2018). Underdevelopment, poverty, and income inequality provide a suitable environment for new terrorists' recruits (Bukhari and Masih 2016). Political instability reduces the volume of investment, raises unemployment, and inflation which upsurges the terrorist activities through lessening the purchasing power of individuals (Naz, Jabeen, and Nasir 2021).

2.5 Terrorism in Microeconomic Theories

2.5.1 The Opportunity Costs of Terrorism

The opportunity cost is the cost of one item, which is the lost chance to do or consume something else; in other words, opportunity cost is the value of the next best option. This concept might assist in understanding why do someone choose to be a terrorist. Terrorists might fight for what they call 'highest value'. Bernholz (2004) believes that the highest values do not allow for the significance of opportunity costs in understanding terror. A belief like this may explain why several empirical researchers reject the idea that poverty is a key role in people's conversion to terrorists (Krueger and Maleková 2003). Yet, there are some socioeconomic factors that may influence terrorism in societies that are frequently driven by terrorists' fundamental principles (Bravo and Dias 2006). Therefore, Freeman (2008) thinks that deficiency in socioeconomic developments might lead to the growth of extremist terrorist ideology. Taking this factual issue and the likelihood of contribution of

supreme values of terrorism into consideration, the opportunity cost paradigm is more suitable for explaining terrorist aid from the terrorists' 'Umfeld', in German language means the surroundings, i.e., indirectly engagement with terrorism (Freytag et al. 2011).

Terrorist superiors use a trade-off between two commodities to seduce terrorists. The trade-off between independence and unity is a persuasive notion which is inspected by Wintrobe's (2003). Individual wealth on Earth and mental incentives for terrorists are the two items under consideration. The possibility of an enjoyable life soon after death, the respect and glory of a martyr, aid for the family of a suicide bomber, or even the redemption of a person's forfeited reputation are all instances of mental motivations. The terrorist is considered to value mental benefits, support, and group cohesion over life on Earth, especially if this includes the prospect of moving to heaven following an effective suicide attack. We differentiate between two options: supporting und/or even becoming a terrorist, or consuming whatever tangible. In microeconomics, this is similar to the study of income and substitution effects. Consider the initial budget line EA, which is shown in Figure 2.3 by the line along with indifference curves, here in point X, the utility of the person is maximized.

Figure 2. 3 Choosing Between Tangible and Ideological Rewards

Source: (Freytag et al. 2011, p.7) with some alterations.

In any place in the world, if life become more tempting, for instance, if per capita GDP rises due to increased earnings, the budget line swings from EA to EC, in Figure 2.3 (Freytag et al. 2011). Utility is now maximized in Z for given preferences. Moving to point Y establishes the income effect. The new optimum can't be attained at point Z. The captivating part of the figure is the substitution effect of the budget constraint adjustment throughout the conversion from Y to Z. The individual likes to consume more tangible belongings and engage in less terror-related activities. As a result, the opportunity costs of terrorist acts have raised up. However, if the opportunity costs go too much, like in the case of an economic downturn, the budget restriction shifts to EB, and terrorism grows more appealing. In an extreme situation, a corner solution is found and utility is maximized in E. The substitution effect is more relevant now, because E is placed on both the new

EB and the old budget restriction EA. This corner solution might be regarded as an individual's decision to commit suicide or any kind of terrorist risks. Economic enhancements, on the other hand, may minimize the terrorist danger by changing the opportunity costs of the terrorists' Umfeld, even if terrorist behavior is driven by their aims via their radical principals (ibid).

2.6 Terrorists' Labor Market

In a standard labor market, payments compensate employees for the work they do for their employer. In the case of insurgent organizations, this would imply pay for risks undertaken on behalf of the group as well as productivity, leading one to anticipate that fighters working in areas with more conflict would be rewarded more (Bahney et al. 2013). That was clearly not the case for Al-Qaida (AQI). So, how should we interpret the observed pay structure?

One hypothesis is that (AQI) employed pay as a method of identification in a situation where uncommitted individuals caused security threats to the group and there was an abundance of eager fighters. To successfully screen members while yet allowing the organization to function, (AQI) would need to pay high enough that members could survive and assist their family members if they joined, but at a level that only adequately devoted individuals would accept. Those members who were required to incur certain expenditures in the expectation of being repaid may have also played a supervisory work, and in case workers performed poorly, payments may be delayed.

The marginal salary increases for getting married and having children make sense as a manner of integrating the group into local communities, which is in line with a view of insurgency as a type of military state-building (Johnston 2008). This still remains the issue of compensation to families of murdered and arrested members.

2.7 Costs of Terrorism

Mainly there are two categories of costs incurred as a result of terrorist acts, according to Sandler and Enders (2008) they involve:

2.7.1 Direct Costs

Direct costs of terrorism may include the instant losses associated with a terrorist attack, such as damaged possessions, the value of lost lives, the expenses of injuries (counting missed income), destroyed structures, damaged infrastructure, and diminished short-term business.

2.7.2 Indirect or Secondary Costs

These kinds of costs are associated with consequential losses, such as increased insurance premiums, increased security expenses, increased compensation to people in high-risk areas, and costs associated with long-run fluctuations in trade. Reduced GDP growth, lost FDI, increases in inflation, or higher unemployment are all examples of indirect costs.

A decision must be taken on how to distinguish between direct and indirect costs, as any differentiation might appear arbitrary to some researchers. Fortunately, this distinction is not required to characterize the economic impact of terrorism, which may be stated in terms of any well-defined macroeconomic (e.g., real per capita GDP growth) or microeconomic variable (e.g., lower tourist revenues). These variables thus indicate the total or sectoral effects of terrorist actions.

If the amount of lost production, casualties, and destroyed infrastructure is significant enough, it will have an impact on the economy's productive capacity, with macroeconomic or microeconomic consequences. If policy intends to mitigate the economic consequences of terrorism, identifying these effects is more important than just tallying losses. As a result, focus must be put on linking terrorism to macroeconomic and microeconomic characteristics that policy might be tailored to strengthen.

2.8 Theories Related to the Causes of Terrorism

Terrorism's origins give the impression to be diverse, leading people to engage in terrorist acts. Scholars have classified inducements to terrorism as psychological, ideological, and strategic elements. According to Walzer (1977), "one person's freedom fighter is another person's terrorist," where the insights of individuals are implicated, depending on how close they are from the activities of the freedom fighters/terrorists. If the operations are taking place in or near your own yard, or if you are the target of the activity, you consider the assailants to be terrorists. If you are not close to the direct acts and are not experiencing actual conditions, you may regard the perpetrators as freedom heroes (Garner and Hughes 2021).

A number of researchers proposed numerous theories on the motivations and causes of terrorism, the most important of which are presented as the following.

2.8.1 Psychological Causes

Psychological explanations of terrorism delve into individual and group psychology, exploring elements such as personality traits, cognitive processes, and socialization experiences that contribute to radicalization and participation in terrorist activities. These theories underscore the influence of identity, group dynamics, and psychological manipulation in shaping extremist behavior. Reliant on the behavioral studies several researches claim that a terrorist personality is; spoiled, psychotic, distressed, obstinate, awkward, cold, excited by violence, maniac, fanatic, and irrational (Schmid and Jongman 1988). However, Post (1989) gives reasoning to a terrorist to be so, by the logic so called 'terrorist psycho-logic', which says;

“Terrorists are driven to commit acts of violence as a consequence of psychological forces, and that their special psychologic is constructed to rationalize acts they are psychologically compelled to commit”¹⁴

While many other researchers believe that terrorists do not show any kind of abnormalities in personality, or conspicuous psychopathology, on the contrary, the most obvious characteristics of terrorists give the impression to be their psychological normality (Corrado 1981; Turco 1987; Ruby 2002; Weatherstone and Moran 2003; Silk 2004). According to Sprinzak (1995, p.40) the psychopathological factors are hard to eliminate, because the estimation and activity of certain violent groups, specifically small and poorly organized, can't be summarized to sociopolitical factors only. Therefore, Crenshaw (1990c) proposes that psychological factors and environmental factors at various levels, should be collectively considered in order to understand the causes of terrorism. Examples of these factors:

- i. Uneducated parents, a dysfunctional family, the death of a father, mother, or first-degree relative will all have a negative impact on one's emotions.
- ii. Trauma, particularly during the period of childhood of teenager as the traumatic bond creates the spirit of revenge which may leads to violence.
- iii. Individuals may get unappreciated or unfair recompense for their legal work.

In conclusion, psychological problems are not an excuse for committing terrorism, because the perpetrators should not be considered as victims or offenders.

¹⁴ Post, J. M. 1989. “Group and Organizational Dynamics of Political Terrorism: Implications for Counterterrorist Policy.” Edited by P. Wilkinson and A. M. Stewart. Aberdeen: Aberdeen University Press.

2.8.2 Economic Factors

2.8.2.1 Income inequality

Economic inequality is inequality in income and economic opportunity. As the opportunities available to the rich and powerful are not available to the poor Income inequality is one important factor that produce political violence, and consequently terrorism, in both developed also in less developed countries. High levels of income inequality may create disparities in access to education, employment, and social services, making certain segments of the population more vulnerable to recruitment by terrorist groups. Additionally, income inequality may foster corruption and illegal economies that provide funding and logistical support for terrorist activities. Wherever high level of internal inequality occurs, there will be internal armed conflicts (Boswell and Dixon 1990).

Many countries seem like endure income inequality, with less violent incidents, while there is economic growth (Hegre et al. 2003). High socioeconomic inequality, such as ethnic discriminations and demographic pressures, has more significant impact on generating conflicts, and then terrorism, during the reduction phase of economic growth. Lia and Skjolberg (2005) found that political factors have more impact than economic factors, on terrorism in Western Europe. Therefore, we have to remember that socioeconomic inequality aggregated with political nature factors play an important role in generating conflicts and terrorism. Income inequality generates more public hatred than poverty (Nasir, Ali, and Rehman 2011), which agrees with the theory of relative deprivation.

2.8.2.2 Poverty

Many studies approve the fact that terrorism takes place within or between poor or underdeveloped countries rather than developed or rich countries (Gleditsch 2002,12). In order to have a wide-ranging view of how

poverty promotes political violence or terrorism we remind the reader by the so-called ‘Predation theory’ which proposed by Collier and Hoeffler (2001). Their theory argues that as long as it is financially achievable, conflict entrepreneurs driven by greed will always be prepared to use force against a government. Growing welfare drastically limits the economic feasibility of an armed uprising since stronger economic incentives are required in countries with high welfare levels, where the costs of taking part in insurgences are considerably higher than in poorer ones. In contrast, if poverty is severe and pervasive, there is minimal need for economic inducement to persuade young people to risk their lives as guerrillas, even if simply for the financial rewards at stake (ibid.). Yet a study by Kruger and Maleckova (2003) has drawn a lot of interest and is frequently cited as proof that there is no connection between poverty and terrorism by saying;

“A careful review of the evidence provides little reason for optimism that a reduction in poverty or an increase in educational attainment would, by themselves, meaningfully reduce international terrorism. Any connection between poverty, education, and terrorism is indirect, complicated, and probably quite weak.”¹⁵

However, some researchers have discovered solid connections between terrorism and poverty. A quantitative cross-country analysis by Li and Schaub (2004) found the chance of transnational terrorism is decreased by economic growth in a nation and among its main trading cohorts.

The validity of Krueger and Maleckova's study conclusions has been vastly overvalued, but they are correct in pointing out that reducing poverty alone is not the only way to do it. There can be little question that poverty, particularly

¹⁵ Krueger, Alan B., and Jitka Malečková. “Education, Poverty and Terrorism: Is There a Causal Connection?” *The Journal of Economic Perspectives* 17, no. 4 (2003): 119–44. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3216934>.

when it coexists with other conflict-generating factors, plays a significant role in encouraging both civil wars and terrorism in terms of intra-state conflicts.

Fewer conflicts might take place in countries with effective institutions, while, regularly democracy increases conflicts in fragile countries. Besides human development factor doesn't aid decreasing in conflict and terrorist activities (Varoudakis Ange and Rizevi 2019).

2.8.2.3 Natural resources

The natural resources exports, particularly oil, hinders economic growth, makes it more difficult to establish a democratic system, and raises the possibility of civil war, according to the literature on modernization theories, rentier states, and resource conflicts (Ross 2001, 2004). The robustness of the oil-hinders-democracy hypothesis is confirmed, and diamonds other non-fuel mineral resources are found to be compatible with it (ibid.). This is especially true in developing countries with weak political institutions, widespread corruption, and power struggles among the elite. It is now widely recognized that the sheer abundance of some natural resources is maybe even more hazardous than scarcity, which was once thought to be a significant cause of conflict (Baechler 1998; De Soysa 2000).

On the other hand, the effects of various natural resources vary. Civil war, particularly separatist warfare, seems to be more likely in countries with abundant oil and mineral resources (Ross 2004). In less developed nations, there are often plenty of "lootable commodities" like gemstones and drugs. While this does not always lead to civil wars, it often extends them since rebel forces may willingly exploit them. All oil-rich nations are either autocratic or semi-authoritarian, and many of them often face waves of social unrest and terrorism.

That the availability of natural resources causes it to overlook the development of human resources. This alters the individual's incentive for self-learning, reducing its usefulness. Instead, it joins political groups in which leads to conflict and corruption. On the other hand, companies and governments compete over oil and natural resources. At the same time, oil is a capital-intensive industry that ignores labor. This leads to extensive joblessness, prompting the unemployed to join illegal terrorist groups in search of earnings. However, the "resource curse" is not just limited to the Middle East. Lia and Kjk (2004) think that, oil-rich Nigeria has long been one of the countries that is most at risk from petroleum-related terrorism. Nigeria also experiences the majority of the problems associated with Third World petromodernization, including "ecological catastrophe, social deprivation, political marginalization, and a greedy company capitalism in which makes inexplicable foreign transnationals are granted a sort of immunity by the state." ¹⁶

2.8.2.4 Other Economic Determinants

There are other economic factors must be taken into consideration that affect terrorism, either transnational terrorism or domestic. For instance, Goldstein (2005) sees that unemployment is a crucial factor, also Adelaja and George (2020) found a direct relationship between youth unemployment, and domestic terrorism, but not with transnational terrorism. Bren, Zeman and, Urban (2019) perceive that GDP is another factor affecting terrorism. Abadie (2006) in his study found that each of human development index and GINI index have a negative relationship with terrorism index. Rizvi, and Véganzonès-Varoudakis (2019) declare that increasing incomes might reduce conflicts in fragile countries. Blomberg, Hess, and Weerapana (2002) concluded that terrorism and economic activity are interdependent; hence, during periods of recession, the

¹⁶ M. Watts, "Petro-Violence: Community, Extraction, and Political Ecology of a Mythic Commodity," In: M. Watts and N. Peluso, Eds., *Violent Environments*, Cornell University Press, Ithaca, 2001, pp. 189-212.

chance of future terrorist operations increases. On the other side, high rates of terrorism occur in democratic countries with high incomes, whereas low rates occur during economic downturns.

2.8.3 Political Factors

2.8.3.1 Democracy

The well-known theory, democracy-fosters-peace, is the foundation of the belief that democracy is scale down terrorist incidents. This theory is originally built on the thought of democracies don't engross in war against one another (Hegre 1997; Hegre et al. 2001). Therefore, origins of international terrorism elevated from existing wars and conflicts. Gurr (1990) asks whether the consequences of democratic peace might be that more democracies, or a more democratic world, would result in less terrorism. In this sense, the findings indicate an uncertain link.

Gurr (1990, 2003) highlights an observable distinction between ethnic and ideological terrorism. Where most terrorist efforts in democratic countries fail because violence offends the public, provokes a reaction among possible supportive populations, and increases widespread support for severe counter-measures by authorities. Only unique minorities, such as militant Catholics in Northern Ireland and Basque activists in Spain, will continue to support terrorist organizations throughout time. The persistence of both ethnic and socio-revolutionary terrorist organizations in Western societies, on the other hand, demonstrates that democracy is insufficient to get rid of terrorism (Skjolberg and Lia, 2005).

There are differentiated ways to link democracy and intra-state terrorism. Domestic terrorism is less expected in consolidated democracies and autocratic governments, comparing to medium semi-authoritarian or semi-democratic regimes. Countries in the process of democratic transition are more vulnerable to violent conflict and internal terrorism, and the implementation of democratic

government may have little influence on existing terrorist attacks. In terms of international terrorism, democracies and semi-democracies are often more vulnerable, although not always, than strong authoritarian governments.

2.8.3.2 State Legitimacy

The common perception on legitimacy is when governments get public support and whose authority is widely disseminated and recognized by peoples, are having state legitimacy. Legitimacy also refers to the system's ability to generate and sustain popular principles that the present political institutions are the best fit for society (Lipset 1963). Therefore, lack of such support might produce domestic violence and terrorism. The theory assumes the absence of such support may ultimately causes domestic conflict and civil violence. Legitimacy can be secured in various sources. Forsythe (1993) identifies some of these sources as; permissible traditions, recognized values and standards, history, ideology, leaders' personalities, and functional considerations such as effective governance and fulfilment of peoples demands.

Domestic terrorism is definitely a matter of governmental legitimacy. According to Lipset (1959), the legitimacy of democratic political systems is determined by how fundamental issues that have historically divided society are addressed. Terrorism increased in nations where the population is divided into multiple opposing groups, split on a scale ranging from approval to denial of the state. Engene (1998, 89) focuses on the following key difficulties to state legitimacy: unaddressed ethnic demands; relates to continuity in democratic development; and difficulty of integrating politically disadvantaged communities into the political system. Therefore, both political structure and economic conditions are responsible for terrorism (Nasir, Ali, and Rehman 2011).

2.8.4 Historical Traditions

There is certainly a link between a society's predominant social norms and historical traditions and its political culture, but the potential effect on the occurrence of terrorism has not been thoroughly addressed. Absence of continuity in democratic regimes, such as the consequences of recent dictatorship or semi-colonial rule, leaves countries more vulnerable to ideological terrorism (Engene 1998). Furthermore, a consistent conclusion in civil war studies is that 'violence tends to generate violence'; countries experiencing civil violence are more likely to encounter more of it, whereas nations without a history of civil wars are more likely to prevent future conflicts (Gleditsch 2002,17).

Mousseau (2002) states;

“There is something about ingrained habits and historical traditions that render terrorism a socially acceptable method for addressing grievances in some societies, but not others.”¹⁷

Crenshaw (1990a) suggests that the occurrence of terrorism in a given place may be related to customs of society and historical traditions that may justify the use of force against the government.

Other authors see that blood feuding traditions have had a significant influence on terrorist activities. Dennis Pluchinsky (1998) revealed that the southern parts of the Former Soviet Union, particularly the Caucasus, have a history of clan-based social structures in which the code of the blood feud is prominent, thus its expressed by "blood-feud terrorism". Students of radical Islamist groups have also observed that strong traditions of revenge and blood feuds in these

¹⁷ Mousseau, Michael. "Market Civilization and Its Clash with Terror." *International Security* 27, no. 3 (2002): 5–29. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3092112> .

communities may help to explain Islamist violence in countries like Algeria and Southern Egypt (Shahin 1997).

2.9 The Variables Employed for the Empirical Analysis

As mentioned previously this study is an insight of the impact of several economic and socioeconomic determinants on the consequences of terrorism risk, which is measured by the global terrorism index TI, for the most affected seven countries during the years 2000 to 2021. The estimated models in this study involve some economic determinants such as; GDP growth, Inflation, Unemployment, Gini coefficient, and Economic Globalization. While the socioeconomic determinants include; Political stability, External interventions, and Demographic pressures, therefore, the indicators (variables) employed in this study are defined as the following:

- i. Terrorism Index (TI) measures the magnitude of humanitarian and economic damages of terrorism in any specific country, and provides a thorough review of the important worldwide trends and patterns in terrorism (Global Terrorism Index 2019). The procedure of calculating this index is explained in Section 2.6.2 of the present chapter.
- ii. Gross Domestic Product Growth rate (GDPG), is the GDP's yearly percentage growth rate at market prices or constant local currency. GDP is calculated as the total of the gross value contributed by all resident producers in the economy, plus any taxes on products and minus subsidies that are not included in the product value. It is estimated without accounting for depreciation of manufactured assets or depletion and deterioration of natural resources ("Data Bank" 2022). The annual rate of GDP growth is calculated as:

$$GDP_{\text{growth}} \frac{GDP_{T1} - GDP_{T0}}{GDP_{T0}} = \frac{GDP_{T1}}{GDP_{T0}} - 1 \quad \dots\dots\dots 2.1$$

Where;

GDP_{growth} is the percentage change of the GDP from one time(year) compare with GDP of the previous time (year).

GDP_{T_0} is the GDP for the previous time (year).

GDP_{T_1} is the GDP for the current or later time (year).

Regarding this study, GDP aggregates are calculated using constant 2015 prices expressed in US dollars.

- iii. Inflation rate (INF) is the rate at which prices in a country rise overall, or the cost of living rises. Inflation, as measured by the consumer price index, is the annual percentage change in the cost to the typical consumer to purchase a basket of goods and services that may be constant or adjusted at periodic intervals, such as annually. A constant base Laspere’s index, that is weighted by quantities of the base time, is commonly used “Glossary | DataBank” as:

$$INF_L = \frac{\sum P_{it} Q_{i0}}{\sum P_{i0} Q_{i0}} \times 100 = \frac{CPI_t}{CPI_0} \times 100 \dots\dots\dots 2.2$$

Where;

P_{i0} is the price of commodity I at the base time.

Q_{i0} is the quantity of commodity I at the base time.

P_{it} is the price of commodity I at the current time or time t.

CPI_t is the cosumer price insex at the current time or time t.

CPI_0 is the consumer price index at the base time.

- iv. Unemployment rate (UEM) as defined by the International Labor Organization ILO is a person aged 15 or older who fits three requirements at the same time: being jobless for an entire week; being available to start work within two weeks; and actively seeking a job in the preceding four weeks or having discovered one beginning in a period of no more than three months. This indicator could be calculated utilizing the following formula:

$$\text{Unemployment Rate} = \frac{\text{No. unemployed}}{\text{No. labor force}} \times 100 \dots\dots\dots 2.3$$

- v. Economic Globalization (G) is the increasing interdependence and economic integration of national, regional, and local economies worldwide as a result of increased cross-border movement of commodities, services, technology, and capital (Hashemi-Pour and Lutkevich 2023). The Economic Globalization involves Cross-border economic activity which expands in five ways: (1) international trade, (2) foreign direct investment, (3) capital market flows, (4) emigration (labor mobility), and (5) diffusion of technology (Stiglitz 2003).
- vi. (PS) Political Stability and Absence of Violence/Terrorism, the index of Political Stability and Absence of Violence/Terrorism assesses the possibility of a government being destabilized or toppled by unconstitutional or violent means, such as politically motivated violence or terrorism. Estimate gives the country's score on the aggregate indicator, in units of a standard normal distribution, i.e. ranging from approximately -2.5 to 2.5”¹⁸
- vii. Demographic Pressures (DP) The Demographic Pressures Indicator evaluates pressures on the state resulting from the population or its surroundings. The indicator, for example, monitors population pressures linked to food availability, access to drinking water and other essential resources, or health, including illness prevalence and epidemics. The indicator takes into account demographic factors for example pressures of high population growth rates or biased population distributions, such as a "youth or age bulge," or sharply distinct rates of population growth among competing communal groups, acknowledging that these effects can have significant social, economic, and political consequences. In addition to population pressures, the indicator considers population pressures caused by severe weather conditions (hurricanes, earthquakes, floods, or drought), as

¹⁸ Kaufmann, Daniel. “The Worldwide Governance Indicators: Methodology and Analytical Issues,” September 1, 2010. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1682130.

well as population pressures caused by environmental threats (“S1: Demographic Pressures | Fragile States Index,” n.d.).

viii. External Interventions (EXI), evaluates the effect and impact of external players on a state's functioning, notably its security and economic functions. On the one hand, External Intervention focuses on the security aspects of covert and overt engagement by authorities, military forces, intelligence agencies, groups of people, or other organizations that may affect the division in power (or recovery of a conflict) within a state. External Intervention, on the other hand, emphasizes economic involvement by outside parties, including multilateral groups, via massive amounts of loans, projects for development, or foreign aid, such as continuing budget support, financial control, or direction of the state's economic policy, resulting in economic dependency (“X1: External Intervention | Fragile States Index,” n.d.).

ix. GINI coefficient, (also known as the Gini index or Gini ratio) is a statistical indicator of a population's economic inequality. The coefficient reflects the distribution of income or wealth among individuals of a population (The World Bank, 2019). The Gini coefficient measures how far the Lorenz curve deviates from the 'line of equality' when comparing regions, A and B, as determined in the following way:

Gini coefficient = $A / (A+B)$, see Figure 2.4.

As incomes are entirely evenly divided, the Lorenz curve is merely the 'line of equality'. Lorenz curve for a Gini coefficient of zero (red line) and a Gini coefficient between zero and one (blue line). The Gini Coefficient is also a measurement used in the redistribution of income and wealth among the population in terms of Pareto efficiency, which develops when resources may be reallocated to benefit one person without causing harm to others (“Gini Coefficient | INOMICS” 2020b).

Figure 2. 4 Lorenz Curve

Source: (“Gini Coefficient | INOMICS” 2020b)

2.10 Worldwide Terrorism

The following subsections makes the reader to understand about institutions involved in collecting terrorism data, facts concerning worldwide terrorist attacks, the economic impact of terrorism in the world, and worldwide top 10 perpetrators with the most fatalities.

2.10.1 Institutions Involved in Collecting Terrorism Data

Global terrorism data collected from four formal institutions around the world as are shown in the following Table 2.2.

Table 2.2 Global Terrorism Data Collection Stages by Assortment Institution

Start Date	End Date	Organization
1/1/1970	12/13/1997	Pinkerton Global Intelligence Service (PGIS)
1/1/1998	3/31/2008	Center for Terrorism and Intelligence Studies (CETIS)
4/1/2008	10/31/2011	Institute for the Study of Violent Groups (ISVG)
11/1/2011	12/31/2014 (ongoing)	National Consortium for the Study of Terrorism and Responses to Terrorism (START)

Source: Global Terrorism Database (GTD) Codebook: National Consortium for the Study of Terrorism and Responses to Terrorism (START), June 2015.

2.10.2 Global Terrorism Index (GTI)

The Institute for Economics and Peace (IEP) is producing annual reports, mostly relying on Global Terrorism Database (GTD), and extra sources, to calculate number of terrorism incidents, deaths, injuries, and damages. In the words of GTD, Global Terrorism Index GTI is:

“A comprehensive attempt to account for the direct and relative impact of terrorism in 158 countries in terms of its effects on lives lost, injuries, and property damage” (Global Terrorism Index 2012, 6).

GTD Data is organized by National Consortium for the Study of Terrorism and Responses to Terrorism (START). For instance, GTD reported that more than 170,000 terrorist incidents occurred during 1970-2019. There are four aspects, or components calculated in each country’s yearly GTI score in order to show the annual impact of terrorism. The raw score of this index is found by GTD through using a simple mathematical calculation by giving each type of a damage a specific weight and multiplying it by its counter number as is shown in the following hypothetical country example in Table 2.3.

Table 2.3 The Scoring Procedure of GTI

Dimension	Weights	No. of records for a given year	Score
Total number of incidents	1	20	20
Total number of fatalities	3	34	102
Total number of injuries	0.5	60	30
Sum of property damages measure	2	22	44
Total Score			196

Source: GTI report, 2018.

To account for the long-term impacts of terrorism, the previous four years are also scored, with a decreasing weight each year. So, A weighted average of five years is used to indicate the psychological impact of terrorist activities over time. Table 2.4 shows the weights for each year.

Table 2.4 Time Weighting of GTI Historical Scores

Year	Weight	% Of Score
Current year	16	52
Previous year	8	26
Two years ago	4	13
Three years ago	2	6
Four years ago	1	3

Source: GTI Report, 2022, p.88.

The generated raw scores are then quasi-logarithmically converted into a scale of 0-10 using 20 bands. A raw score of 0 (TI=0) indicates a GTI of 0. The following 20 levels on the GTI scale ($h = 0.5, 1, \dots, 10$) are specified as;

$$TIh = (TI_{\max} - TI_{\min})^{h/10}. \dots\dots\dots 2.4$$

Where;

TIh represent the raw score steps, TI_{\min} is the minimum recorded raw score, and TI_{\max} is the largest recorded raw score. The GTI is interpolated linearly between these phases (Hyslop and Morgan 2014, 107).

The GTI index is used to measure the magnitude of humanitarian and economic damages of terrorism in any specific country. It has been employed in many empirical studies such as in; Abadie (2006), Gries et al. (2011), Enders and Sandler (2012), and others. To account for the impacts of trauma caused by terrorist acts on a society, the GTI considers prior years' events as having an impact on a country's present score. For example, the magnitude of the 2011 terrorist attacks in Norway will have a long-term psychological impact on the people.

The GTD developed the levels and weights for property damages that are used in the Global Terrorism Index, as shown in Table 2.5.

Table 2.5 The GTD Property Damage Levels and Weights

Code/ Weight	Damage Level
0	Unknown
1	Minor (likely < \$1 million)
2	Major (likely between \$1 million and \$1 billion)
3	Catastrophic (likely > \$1 billion)

Source: GTI report, 2018.

The global impact of terrorism is not dispersed evenly. There are a few countries with extremely high levels of terrorism, compared to the vast majority of countries with low or no levels of terrorism. The GTI uses a base 10 logarithmic banding technique between 0 and 10 at 0.5 intervals to provide a more equally distributed index (GTI 2020, 97), as can be seen in Table 2.6.

Table 2.6 Global Terrorism Index (GTI) in 2020

RANK	COUNTRY	SCORE	RANK CHANGE
1	● Afghanistan	9.592	↔
2	● Iraq	8.682	↔
3	● Nigeria	8.314	↔
4	● Syria	7.778	↔
5	● Somalia	7.645	↑ 1
6	● Yemen	7.581	↑ 1
7	● Pakistan	7.541	↓ 2
8	● India	7.353	↔
9	● Democratic Republic of the Congo	7.178	↑ 1
10	● Philippines	7.099	↓ 1
11	● Mali	7.049	↑ 2
12	● Burkina Faso	6.755	↑ 15
13	● Cameroon	6.627	↑ 1

Source: Global Terrorism Index (GTI), 2020, P.8.

Taking some examples, in year 2020 Afghanistan, Iraq, and Nigeria experience the top heist ranking in their GTI scores 9.5, 8.7, and 8.3 respectively. the severity of their GTI scores didn't changed comparing the previous year. Then Syria, Somalia, and Yemen with 7.7, 7.6, and 7.5, respectively.

2.10.3 Facts Concerning Worldwide Terrorist Attacks

Worldwide terrorist attacks kept increasing in number during the years 2000 to 2020. Through Figure 2.5 we can see that Middle East, South Asia, Sub-Saharan Africa, and South East Asia are the most affected regions respectively. However, the number of deaths due to terrorism has been increasing continuously around the world during the last 50 years or so, but according GTD statistics it has increased significantly over the past decade.

Figure 2.5 Number of Terrorism Attacks in The World During 2000 to 2020

Source: Global Terrorism Database GTD.

The last two decades had an average of 26,000 worldwide fatalities each year. However, there might be substantial variation from year to year. Over the course of both decades, the worldwide mortality deaths fluctuated from 8,200

in 2011 to its highest of 44,600 in 2014, as shown in Figure 2.6. Since 2010, roughly 124,000 of the overall 167,000 worldwide terrorist deaths have occurred in Iraq, Afghanistan, Nigeria, Pakistan, and Syria. In other words, 74% of worldwide terrorism-related deaths happened in these countries (Bardwell and Iqbal 2021).

Figure 2.6 Number of Deaths Due to Terrorism in The World 1970 - 2020

Source: Global Terrorism Database GTD.

The National Consortium for the Study of Terrorism and Responses to Terrorism, declared that the Islamic State of Iraq and the Levant (ISIL), the Taliban in Afghanistan, al-Shabaab, Boko Haram, and Maoists in India were the perpetrator organizations responsible for the most terrorist incidents in 2014. These organizations were also responsible for the majority of assaults in 2013. In 2014, All of the five groups increased their attack frequency, albeit at different rates. ISIL was responsible for 17% of the incidents for which perpetrator information was available. Although ISIL mainly operated in Iraq and Syria, the organization expanded its geographical reach in 2014 by conducting assaults in Lebanon and Egypt for the first time. Several groups

established in other countries have also acknowledged commitment to ISIL and described as a "province," "chapter," or "supporter" of the Islamic State (START, June 2015).

2.10.4 The Economic Impact of Terrorism in the World

Terrorism cost the world's economy \$855 billion during 2000 and 2018. Global terrorism peaked in 2014, with 33,555 deaths and a \$US 111 billion economic damage. Terrorism-related deaths rose by 353% between 2011 and 2014, while terrorist incidents grew by 190% (Bardwell and Iqbal 2021).

The economic impact of Terrorism had about \$33.2 billion worldwide in 2018, which was recorded around 38% reduction from 2017. The overall number of terrorist-related deaths fell by 15.2% in 2018 in comparison with 2017. As a result, the economic effect of terrorist deaths has decreased, and the economic impact of terrorism has decreased as well, see and Figure 2.7.

Fig 2.7 Worldwide Economic Impact of Terrorism in Billions of Dollars

Source: Bardwell, & Iqbal. (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1515/peps-2020-0031>

Terrorism has had the greatest impact on the Middle East and North Africa. Since 2000, the economic effect of terrorism in the area has reached the amount of \$US 434 billion. Sub-Saharan Africa was the second most impacted area, accounting for \$US 133 billion. At \$US 125 billion, South Asia is the third most affected area. (Bardwell and Iqbal, 2021).

Terrorist funding, like money laundering, could be divided into into four stages. The four steps are collecting, storing, transporting, and using. Each of these actions, without a doubt, has a negative impact on society in a certain way.

2.10.5 Worldwide Top 10 Perpetrators with the Most Fatalities

The top ten terrorism Perpetrators accounted for 74% of the worldwide terrorist activities in 2020, with a 1% rise in terrorism incidences among the top ten perpetrators. They include: the Taliban, ISIS-DRC, ISIS-Core, al-Shabaab, the Communist Party of India-Maoist (CPI-Maoist), ISIS-Democratic Republic of the Congo (ISIS-DRC), Boko Haram, the Communist Party of the Philippines/New People's Army (CPP/NPA), the Haftar Militia, Hay'at Tahrir al-Sham, and the Cooperative for the Development of Congo (CODECO) (Annex of Statistical Information 2020, 10).

The top ten perpetrators in 2020 are shown in descending order of fatalities in Table 2.7. The Taliban, ISIS-DRC, ISIS-Core, al-Shabaab, Boko Haram, ISIS-West Africa, Cooperative for the Development of Congo (CODECO), Fulani Militants, ISIS-Mozambique, and Hay'at Tahrir al-Sham were among those involved. The top ten perpetrators were responsible for an 11% rise in deaths over the previous year, 2019, while the worldwide total number of fatalities attributed to terrorism climbed by 12% compared to year 2019. There were four exceptions to this overall trend: the Taliban, ISIS, Boko Haram, and al-Shabaab all experienced slight drops in the number of casualties they caused.

Table 2.7 Top 10 Terrorism Perpetrators with the Most Fatalities

Top Perpetrators		2018	2019	2020	2019-2020 change
1	Taliban	8554	7918	7417	-6%
2	ISIS-DRC	298	341	1435	321%
3	ISIS-Core	3654	1487	1434	-4%
4	al-Shabaab	2.090	1409	1393	-1%
5	Boko Haram	1311	1379	1286	-7%
6	ISIS-West Africa	114	929	982	6%
7	CODECO	-	23	658	2761%
8	Fulani Militants	1924	430	487	13%
9	ISIS-Mozambique	-	69	457	562%
10	Hay 'at Tahrir al-sham	304	930	433	-53%
Subtotal		17945	13985	15549	11%
Year-End Total (Worldwide)		32952	26273	29389	12%

Source: Global Terrorism Trends and Analysis Center GTTAC, Annex of Statistical Information, 2020, p.11

2.11 Synopsis Description about the Selected Countries

As mentioned previously in chapter one of this study, one of the main objectives is to reveal the most significant factors impact terrorism in the seven selected countries, therefore the researcher deems its essential to have a clue about each country, the following sections are a synopsis about each.

2.11.1 The Republic of Iraq

The republic of Iraq located in west of Asia, in the Middle east, its area is 438,317 km² with the estimated population 40.2 million (world bank, 2020). The most reliable source of Iraq's income revenues is from oil production. The government is federal parliamentary, Baghdad is the largest city and represents as the capital. There are diverse ethnic groups in Iraq such as; Arab, Kurd, Turkman, Assyrian, Keldon, and Arminian, with different religious doctrines such as; Shia, Sunni, Christians, Yazidi, Zoroastrianism, Kakai, and Sabia.

Iraq's terrorism index scored high from year 2004 to 2020. Which was the most affected, 14 times more, in comparison with the other countries, during 2000 - 2018 (Bardwell and Iqbal, 2021). This index reached to 10 during the period of 4 years, from 2014 to 2017 due to ISIS group extensive attacks. The direct costs were significantly high, such as the number of deaths due to terrorism attacks. The highest number of deaths was 14095 in year 2014, which is corresponding to the highest number of terrorist incidents 3934, in the same year, as shown in Figure 2.8. The ratio of Iraqi deaths to worldwide deaths due to terrorism was 0.23% in year 2000, then this ratio increased significantly to reach 31.57% in year 2014 (GTI, 2016).

Fig 2. 8 Terrorism Incidents and Deaths in Iraq During 2000-2020

Source: plotted by the researcher based on; GTD, START, and (“Our World in Data” 2022).

Sinjar massacre was Iraq's most serious humanitarian disaster. This was the world's second-costliest occurrence in terms of deaths and injuries from 2000 to 2018, with an economic loss of \$US 4.3 billion due to ISIL attacks, as they claimed the responsibility for an attack on Yazidi people in Sinjar,

Nineveh, Iraq. Consequently, at least 953 individuals were killed in this attack, and 5350 were kidnapped. However, the collective cost of 31 terrorist incidences in Iraq estimated to be \$US 31 billion in lost GDP due to fatalities and injuries (Bardwell and Iqbal, 2021).

2.11.2 The Islamic Emirate of Afghanistan

Afghanistan is located at the intersection of Central and South Asia, which is named as the Heart of Asia. The country's area is 652,864 km² (252,072 mi²), it is almost mountainous country, with prairies in the north and the southwest. According The World Bank (2022) Afghanistan population was 40.2 million in 2021, they are mostly consisting of Pashtuns ethnicity, Tajiks, Hazaras, and Uzbeks. The government is Islamic Emirate ruling by Taliban group in present, and Kabul is the largest city and serves as its capital. Afghanistan is rich in natural resources, which consist of Lithium, Iron, Zinc, and Copper, ...etc., also the major producer of Opium ("Claims Over Afghan Mineral Wealth," n.d.).

Terrorism index in Afghanistan was scoring quite high averages, between 9-10 in the last decade. Many terrorist organizations execute their activities in Afghanistan during 2000 to 2020, such as; Al Qaida (AQ), Daesh Khorasan Province (ISKP), and several others. However, these organizations have strong anti-Western beliefs. Their leader Osama bin Laden founded the core of Al Qaeda AQ in Afghanistan in 1988. In 1999, the US recognized AQ as one of Foreign Terrorist Organizations FTO. Following the group's involvement in the September 11, 2001 terrorist attacks on the United States, U.S.-led forces drove AQ out of Afghanistan. GTD reported the highest number of terrorist attacks by 2604 in year 2020, see Figure 2.9.

Figure 2.9 Terrorist Attacks and Deaths in Afghanistan during 2000-2020

Source: plotted by the researcher based on; GTD, START, and (“Our World in Data” 2022).

Afghanistan is the most wedged by terrorism, in spite of a decline in deaths from terrorism in years 2018 to 2019. Where, in 2019 the average of deaths declined to 22% comparing to year 2018. Yet, deaths ratio from terrorism in this country is quite high, which accounted for 41% of deaths from terrorism worldwide in 2018. Note that there have been 7522 terrorist incidences since 2018. On average terrorism costed Afghanistan 22% loss in its GDP in year 2018 (Bardwell and Iqbal, 2021). In 2019, GDP loss decreased to 16.7% (IEP, 2020).

2.11.3 Democratic Republic of the Congo

Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) located in central Africa, its area is 2,345,409 km² (905,567 mi²), 3.32 % of which is the watery area. Its population is 108,407,721, where, 95.8% follow Christianity religion, 1.8% Traditional faiths, 1.5% Islam, and 0.9% Others (world bank, 2022). The capital, Kinshasa, is the largest city in central Africa, it is the official administrative, economic, and cultural center. DRC is rich in natural resources

containing vast deposits of industrial Diamonds, Cobalt, and Copper. The country has the largest forest reserves in Africa, and huge hydroelectric potentials of the continent. More than 200 African ethnic groups live in DRC, such as Bantu, which constitute a large majority of the country's population. More than 200 languages are spoken in Congo. Four "national" languages have been used such as: Swahili, Tshiluba (Kiluba), Lingala, and Kongo. These four national languages are widely used in regional transactions, while, French is the official language and the language of instruction, business, administration, and international communications.

Minerals smuggling caused wars and conflicts particularly in eastern Congo, example of such minerals are; Coltan and Cassiterite, Ores of Tantalum and Tin. However, the country has been subjected to terrorist attacks more frequently in recent years. The effective terrorist groups in the Democratic Republic of the Congo include; Mayi Mayi, Nyatura Militia, Kamwina Nsapu Militia, Mai Mai Simba Militia, and others. In general, they were responsible of 489 terrorist incidents recorded during the last five 5 years, in which 1727 people have been murdered, and 742 injured, out of 207 incidents 1775 people have been taken as hostage or kidnapped, in which only 23 of them released through ransoms. ("Democratic Republic of the Congo" 2022).

Figure 2.10 shows that the number of terrorist incidents and deaths in DRC increase during the period 2000 to 2020. In addition, the chart illustrates that the year 2020 had the largest number of events and deaths, with 310 and 1356, respectively.

Figure 2.10 Terrorism Incidents and Deaths in Democratic Republic of the Congo During 2000-2020

Source: plotted by the researcher based on; GTD, START, and (“Our World in Data” 2022).

2.11.4 Federal Republic of Nigeria

Nigeria is located in West Africa, between the Sahel to the north and the Gulf of Guinea to the south in the Atlantic Ocean, its area is 923,769 km² (356,669 sq mi²), where 1.4% of its area is water. Nigeria population was 218,541,212 in 2020, which is considered the most populous country in Africa, and the world’s sixth-most populous country. There are 36 states in Nigeria, with the capital, Abuja. Nigeria has more than 250 ethnic groups, with many languages and customs, and ethnicities. Hausa, Yoruba and Igbo are the three largest ethnic groups in Nigeria, the three groups together are forming more than 60% of the country’s population. Religions in Nigeria are almost equally divided into Islam and Christianity, with a tiny minority of believers of traditional African religions and other religions.

The first most reliable source of Nigeria income comes from petroleum, the second source is from payments sent by Nigerians from abroad. Nigeria also has other unexploited mineral resources which comprise of; gold, coal, tin,

bauxite, ore, tantalite, iron, limestone, lead, niobium, and zinc. Agriculture contributes around 26.5% of Nigeria’s GDP, and other natural resources such as; rain forests, savannah, and waterfalls especially for Tourism purposes, which is another source of income in Nigeria.

Terrorism activities had adverse impact on the Nigerian communities, several groups like Boko Haram or JASDJ and, Islamic State in West Africa ISWA were operating in Nigeria and its neighboring countries such as Cameroon, Chad and Niger. Their main goal was to destabilize the Nigerian government and eradicate western effect in the country (“Nigeria – Boko Haram and the Fight against Terrorism” 2015). Statistic reports show that economic impact of terrorism in African countries during 2007 - 2019 was 141889.4 million dollars with the average annual cost of terrorism on Nigeria’s GDP, is 0.82% (“Statista - the Statistics Portal” 2022.).

Number of terrorist incidents in Nigeria’s was at its peak 713, with 7775 deaths in year 2014, see Figure 2.11.

Figure 2.11 Terrorism Incidents and Deaths in Nigeria During 2000-2020

Source: plotted by the researcher based on; GTD, START, and (“Our World in Data” 2022).

Nigeria had the second-highest number of terrorist events after Iraq, with 14 among the 100 riskiest during years 2000 to 2018 (Bardwell and Iqbal, 2021).

2.11.5 The Islamic Republic of Pakistan

Pakistan is located in South Asia, according to the World Bank (2022) estimation its population 242,923,845, which has the world's second-largest Muslim population. Pakistan is the 33rd-largest country by area, 881,913 km² (340,509 mil²), and Islamabad is the capital. Pakistan is practicing a democratic parliamentary federal republic, with Islam as the state religion and its official languages are Urdu and English. Different ethnicities are existing in the country but the major ethnic groups are; Punjabis which consists 44.7% of the country's population, Pashtuns or Pathans 15.4%, Sindhis 14.1%, Saraikis 8.4%, Muhajirs who are more than 7.6% of the population, and the Baloch with 3.6%. The majority of Pakistanis are Muslims which consist 96.47% of the country's population, followed by Hindus 2.14%, and Christians 1.27% (Bezhan 2017). Also, there are other religions followers, such as Sikhism, Buddhism, Jainism and the minority who follow Zoroastrianism.

Different sorts of natural commodities are produced in Pakistan, also it has the tenth largest labor market in the world. The economic system has changed from agricultural to service base system in recent years, where the service sector makes up 58.8% of its GDP. Agriculture accounted for 20.9% of the country's GDP in 2015, on which the majority of the population relies, directly or indirectly. The agriculture sector in Pakistan accounts for 43.5% of employed labor force, and is the main source of foreign exchange incomes. The second main production sector is Industry, which accounts for 19.74% of its GDP, which engage 24 % of Pakistani total employment (Alam 2023).

Terrorism risk was high in Pakistan since 2003, but peaked in 2009. Tehrik-i-Taliban Pakistan (TTP) group was the most fatal terrorist group in 2019. This group was in charge of 73 terrorist deaths in 2019, followed by Lashkar-e-Jhangvi LeJ caused 21 deaths, and Hizb-ul-Ahrar (HuA) caused 20 deaths. Jointly, the three groups accounted for 38% of terrorist deaths in 2019.

Many terrorist groups are supported by Al Qaeda organization in Pakistan such as; Al Qaeda in the Indian Subcontinent (AQIS), Islamic State-Khorasan Province (ISKP) or (IS-K), Tehrik-i-Taliban Pakistan TTP, Haqqani (HQN) group, Balochistan Liberation Army (BLA), Jundallah (aka Jaysh al-Adl), Sectarian Anti-Shia Militants Sipah-e-Sahaba Pakistan SSP which is known as Ahle Sunnat Wal Jamaat (“Terrorist and Other Militant Groups in Pakistan / K. Alan Kronstadt - Penn State University Libraries Catalog,” n.d.).

Haider et. al., (2015) found that the most leading causes of terrorism in Pakistan are; lack of law enforcement, poverty, Pakistan’s participation in war on terror, foreign involvement, and unemployment. Terrorism related incidents kept increasing starting from year 2000 till reached to its highest number 2215 in 2013, then began to decrease in 2014 until now, with a total of 30354 terrorist occurrences from 2000 to 2023, see Figure 2.12.

Figure 2.12 Terrorism Incidents and Deaths in Pakistan During 2000-2020

Source: plotted by the researcher based on; GTD, START, and (“Our World in Data” 2022).

2.11.6 The Syrian Arab Republic

Syria is located in west of Asia, in Eastern Mediterranean and the Levant, it has 14 governorates. People of several nationalities and cultures live in this country, including Arabs, Kurds, Turkmens, Assyrians, Armenians, Circassians, Albanians, and Greeks. The religions practiced are: Islamic, Christianity, Alawi's, Druze, and Yazidis. Syria's area is 185,180 km² (71,500 Mi²), with 1.1 % of water, and the estimated population in 2022 was 22,142,061.

Syria was classified by the World Bank as having the lowest average income as a result of civil wars and conflicts in the past decade. Oil exports make up nearly 40% of Syria's GDP, then the agriculture sector contributes nearly 20%, and official employment by the government make up about 20%. The economy of Syria shrank about 35%, and the Syrian currency "Lera" has dropped to one-sixth of its prewar value during the civil war period. This war caused poverty which 11.4% of population live below the survival level (UNDP 2005).

During the recent decade, the Islamic State of Iraq and Levant (or Sham), also known as ISIL or ISIS, committed several lethal terrorist acts in 11 of Syria's 14 governorates. The highest terrorism risks such as; murder, kidnaping, damage and torture of civilians, mostly involved, ethnic and religious minorities such as the; Christian and Kurdish population. Number of Terrorism Incidents in the Syrian Arab Republic was on peak 491 in year 2015 then declined gradually till now see Figure 2.13. The Independent International Commission of Inquiry on the Syrian Arab Republic "UN Com. I Syria" classified ISIS attacks on civilians in Syria since 2014 as extensive and systematic, implementing an organized policy, and these actions were considered crimes against humanity ("Increase in Actions against Impunity for War Crimes by Syrian Regime" 2022).

Figure 2.13 Terrorism Incidents and Deaths in Syrian During 2000-2020

Source: plotted by the researcher based on; GTD, START, and (“Our World in Data” 2022).

2.11.7 The Republic of Yemen

Yemen locates to the West of Asia, on the southern part of the Arabian Peninsula. Yemen is the second-largest Arab independent country in the peninsula, with 555000 km² area (214,000 mil²). With a seashore extends nearly 2000 km (1,200 miles), and Sanaa is the capital. The country’s estimated population in year 2021 was 30,491,000. The majority of Yemenis are Arabs, followed by other ethnicities such as, Afro-Arabs, South Asians and Europeans. Various tribal societies exist in Yemen, where 400 Zaidi tribes are inhabited in the northern mountainous, Al-Akhdam tribes are mostly live in urban areas, and Yemenis of Persian origin. The official language in Yemen is Modern Standard Arabic, while they use their Arabic Yemeni slang. According to the UNHCR (2018) Report there are two basic Islamic religious groups in Yemen: About 35% of population is Shia, and 65% is Sunni. Approximately 5% of the Yemenis are non-Muslim, following Christianity, Judaism, or Hinduism or having no religious affiliation.

The largest economic sector in Yemen is Services which constitutes about 61.4% of GDP, followed by the industrial sector 30.9%, and agriculture 7.7%, where the petroleum production embodies about 25% of the country's GDP and 63% of the government's revenue. The main agricultural commodities produced in Yemen include; grain, vegetables, fruits, pulses, qat, coffee, cotton, dairy products, fish, livestock (sheep, goats, cattle, camels), and poultry. While the country's industries entail crude oil production, and petroleum filtering, food processing, handicrafts, small-scale production of cotton textiles and leather goods, aluminum products, commercial ship repair, cement, and natural gas production ("Yemen - the World Factbook," n.d.).

Number of terrorist incidents kept increasing starting from 2008 until 2016, where it reached to its highest 917 incidents, afterwards the incidents declined until the time being, observe Figure 2.14. Deaths from terrorism in Yemen raised up significantly to reach 2506 in year 2015. The majority of the killings were committed by the Ansar Allah organization, which was the most lethal terrorist group in recent years, causing 75% of all deaths in Yemen. However, Al-Qa'ida in the Arabian Peninsula (AQAP) is likewise conducted active conflicts in Yemen. Afterwards the terrorist group of ISIS groups started doing suicide operations against Shia targets in Sadah and Sana'a, in March 2015. Also, terrorist activities occurred in other cities such as; Aden, Sana'a, Ibb, Hodeida and al-Bayda. ISIS used vehicle bombs and suicide bombers as terrorist tactics in Yemen, where the focus has been on the Houthis, security people, and government institutions. AQAP targeted the Western and Houthi interests in Yemen since October 2014.

Figure 2.14 Terrorism Incidents and Deaths in Yemen During 2000-2020

Source: plotted by the researcher based on; GTD, START, and (“Our World in Data” 2022).

In summary, terrorism has had the biggest impact on the Middle East and North Africa. Starting from year 2000 till 2020, the economic impact of terrorism in the region has been \$US 434 billion. Sub-Saharan Africa was the second most severely damaged region, with \$US 133 billion in losses. South Asia was the third most hit region, accounting for \$US 125 billion GDP losses (Bardwell and Iqbal, 2021).

2.12 Trends of Terrorism Index for The Selected Countries

The Worldwide Trends of Terrorism Index is an in-depth review that aims to give insights into the worldwide landscape of terrorism by emphasizing trends, patterns, and dynamics found in various areas and countries. Terrorism Index of a country, or the repercussions of terrorist activities, is calculated using four categories of outcomes: total number of fatalities, total number of incidents, total number of injuries, and sum of property damage expenses.

After assigning a weight to each item and performing a few math calculations, terrorism index will be obtained (GTI 2019). Since year 2001, the magnitude of this indicator has been growing in the countries that are studied. Figure 2.15 shows that all seven countries have high TI scores ranging from 6 to 10, from 2012 to 2020. However, Iraq and Afghanistan had the highest frequency of high TI scores, ranking first and second, respectively, due to high and persistent TI scores in the period of the study.

Figure 2.15 Terrorism Index Trends for the Selected Countries

Source: (Plotted by the researcher based on GTD 2022)

Iraq and Afghanistan are the most two vulnerable countries to terrorism threatens starting from year 2003 until the time being. Since the US-led entry to Iraq in 2003, terrorism has been a persistent threat, with various insurgent groups and terrorist organizations, such as Al-Qaeda in Iraq (AQI) and the Islamic State (IS), exploiting the country's political instability and sectarian divisions to carry out attacks on security forces, civilians, and infrastructure. The data may indicate changes in the frequency, lethality, and methods of terrorist attacks over time, as well as adjustments in conflict dynamics and counterterrorism operations.

Afghanistan has faced terrorism and insurgency since the fall of the Taliban administration in 2001. The Taliban, along with other terrorist organizations including Haqqani Network and ISIS-Khorasan Province, have maintained a long-running war against the Afghan government and foreign forces. The Taliban, among other terrorist organizations such as the Haqqani Network and ISIS-Khorasan Province, have maintained a long-running insurgency against the Afghan government and foreign troops, resulting in massive carnage, displacement, and humanitarian misery. Historical statistics may reveal patterns in terrorist attacks, territorial control, and casualties, as well as the effect of external interventions, political transitions, and peace attempts on Afghanistan's security situation.

CHAPTER THREE: ESTIMATING THE IMPACT OF ECONOMIC AND OTHER ADDED VARIABLES ON TERRORISM IN THE SEVEN SELECTED COUNTRIES

3.1 Preface

In this chapter panel data models will be constructed for the variables under study via two main models for seven selected countries. The first model involves economic indicators only, while the second model embrace assorted macro-indicators, such as; economic, political, and demographic. The first model consists of Terrorism Index (TI) as a dependent variable with independent variables of; GDP growth (GDPG), Inflation rate (INF), Unemployment rate (UEM), and Economic Globalization Index (G). While the second model consists of the independent variables of; GDP growth (GDPG), Inflation rate (INF), Economic Globalization Index (G), political stability index (PS), Demographic pressure index (DP), and external intervention Index, related to the dependent variable of (TI).

First, descriptive statistics will be performed for each variable of the study. Second, since panel data modeling embrace several methods, and in order to apply the most suitable one, several kinds of econometric modeling have been followed. However, in this chapter two groups of linear models will be constructed; static, and dynamic, for each of economic and socioeconomic variables, each group embrace three approaches, pooled OLS, random effect, fixed effect models for the static category. While pooled mean group, mean group, and dynamic fixed effect models will be developed for the dynamic category. To develop the most appropriate static or dynamic model, specific preference tests will be performed. And third, Granger causality test also will be implemented to reveal which independent variable Granger causes terrorism index for future forecasting's. Table 3.1 demonstrates the acronym, description, measurement, and the expected sign for the variables under investigation.

Table 3.1 Variables, Measurements, and Description.

Acronym	Description	Measurement	Expected sign
TI (dependent variable)	Terrorism Index	0 to10	+ for TI lags
INF	Inflation rate	% Rate	+
GDPG	Annual GDP growth	% Rate	-
G	Economic Globalization Index	0 to100	+ or -
UEM	Unemployment	% Rate	+
PS	Political Stability Index	-2.5 to 2.5	-
DP	Demographic Pressures Index	0 to 10	+
EXI	External Interventions Index	0 to 10	+ or -

Source: Prepared by the researcher, 2023.

3.2 Panel Data

A panel data consists of data for N different entities or countries observed at T different time periods (Baltagi 2021). Panel data analysis is desirable because it produces more efficient estimates, offers a higher degree of freedom, and reduces collinearity issues within variables (Hsiao 2005). Panel data techniques excel in situations where variables exhibit dynamic changes over time when dealing with a cluster of countries with inter or intra cross-sectional characteristics, resulting in more robust findings (Baltagi, 2008). Panel data techniques are chosen over country-specific time-series econometrics, because they produce more reliable results (Maddala and Wu 1999; Im et al. 2003).

The notation used in the simple linear panel data model with one explanatory variable is (Y_{it}, X_{it}) , where $i = 1, \dots, N$ and $t = 1, \dots, T$. The model is represented as:

$$Y_{it} = \alpha + \beta X_{it} + U_{it} \dots\dots\dots 3.1$$

Where:

Y_{it} represents the dependent variable,

X_{it} represents the independent variables,

U_{it} represents the error term.

As we have seven countries in this study, so $N=7$ and twenty-two years, $T =22$, thus the total number of observations is 154. This panel data set considered a long panel data, where T is greater than n (Gujarati 2015). Besides, the dataset covers all of its observations for each panel with no missing values in any year, implying that we have a balanced panel data set (Asteriou and Hall 2006; Stock and Watson 2015), see Figure 3.1.

```

Panel variable: CID (strongly balanced)
Time variable: Years, 2000 to 2021
Delta: 1 year

```

Figure 3.1 Description of this Study’s Panel Dataset

Source: screenshot by the researcher using Stata17, 2023.

3.3 Types of Panel Data Models

3.3.1 The Static Models

3.3.1.1 Pooled Ordinary Least Squares POLS model

POLS delivers efficient and reliable parameter estimations if the individual effect u_i (cross-sectional or time specific impact) does not exist ($u_i=0$). So, the general formula of a POLS model would be:

$$Y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{it} + E_{it} \dots\dots\dots 3.2 \quad , \text{ for } (u_i=0).$$

Where;

Y_{it} dependent variable (for country i at time t).

β_0 is the unknown intercept for all countries.

X_{it} is a vector of predictors (for entity i at time t).

E_{it} overall error term.

u_i within-country error term

POLS entails five essential assumptions (Greene,2008; Kennedy,2008)

- Linearity – the model is linear function.
- Exogeneity – expected value of disturbance is zero or disturbance are not correlated with any regressor.
- Homoscedasticity & no autocorrelation.
- Not stochastic for the independent variable but fixed in repeated samples.
- Full rank – there is no exact linear relationship among independent variables.

The following is the specification of both the economic and the assorted variables, POLS models:

$$TI_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 GDPG_{it} + \beta_2 INF_{it} + \beta_3 UEM_{it} + \beta_4 G_{it} + E_{it} \quad \dots\dots\dots 3.3$$

$$TI_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 GDPG_{it} + \beta_2 INF_{it} + \beta_3 G_{it} + \beta_4 PS_{it} + \beta_5 EXI_{it} + \beta_6 DP_{it} + E_{it} \quad \dots\dots\dots 3.4$$

3.3.1.2 Fixed Effect Model FEM

The country simple fixed effects model is;

$$Y_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta X_{it} + u_i + E_{it} \quad \dots\dots\dots 3.5 \quad i = 1 \dots n ; t = 1 \dots T$$

Where:

Y_{it} dependent variable (for country i at time t).

α_i is the unknown intercept for each country (n country-specific intercepts).

X_{it} is a vector of predictors (for entity i at time t).

u_i within-country error term

E_{it} overall error term.

And the country and time fixed effects regression model is;

$$Y_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta X_{it} + \delta t + u_i + E_{it} \dots\dots\dots 3.6, \quad i = 1 \dots n; t = 1 \dots T$$

Where; δt is the unknown coefficient for the time regressors (t).

The assumptions of Fixed Effects Model are:

- i. The error term u_{it} has conditional mean zero, that is;

$$E(u_{it} | X_{i1}, X_{i2}, \dots, X_{iT}) = 0$$

- ii. $(X_{i1}, X_{i2}, \dots, X_{iT}, u_{i1}, \dots, u_{iT})$, $i=1, \dots, n$ are i.i.d. draws from their joint distribution.
- iii. Large outliers are unlikely, i.e., (X_{it}, u_{it}) have nonzero finite fourth moments.
- iv. There is no perfect multicollinearity.

When there are multiple regressors, X_{it} is replaced by $X_{1,it}, X_{2,it}, \dots, X_{k,it}$.

The following models are specification for both the economic and the assorted variables, by using the fixed effect FE approach:

$$TI_{it} = \beta_i + \beta_1 GDPG_{it} + \beta_2 INF_{it} + \beta_3 UEM_{it} + \beta_4 G_{it} + E_{it} \dots\dots\dots 3.7$$

$$TI_{it} = \beta_i + \beta_1 GDPG_{it} + \beta_2 INF_{it} + \beta_3 G_{it} + \beta_4 PS_{it} + \beta_5 EXI_{it} + \beta_6 DP_{it} + E_{it} \dots\dots\dots 3.8$$

3.3.1.3 Random Effect Model REM

Up to now the previous panel data regressions we've examined have assumed that the coefficients on regressors are similar across all countries or groups. This assumption is relaxed by the random coefficients model, which provides individual-specific effects via the coefficient, such that

The random effects should be employed if differences across countries have an effect on the dependent variable, but they are uncorrelated to the predictors. The main benefit of random effects is that time invariant variables (such as gender) can be included. These variables are taken into account by the intercept in the fixed effects model.

The Random Effect model will take the following general form:

$$Y_{it} = \alpha + \beta x_{it} + U_i + E_{it} \quad \dots\dots\dots 3.9$$

Where;

Y_{it} = t th response from i th subject: $i = 1, \dots, n$ x_{it} = corresponding value of explanatory variable

- i. U_i = random effect for subject i
- ii. E_{it} = overall residuals
- iii. all U_i and all E_{it} mutually independent
- iv. different responses on same subject positively correlated

$$\rho = \text{Var}(U) / \text{Var}(U) + \text{Var}(Z) \quad \dots\dots\dots 3.10$$

Considering the Random Effect model, the economic and mixed variables model specifications will be as follows:

$$TI_{it} = \beta + \beta_1 GDPG_{it} + \beta_2 INF_{it} + \beta_3 UEM_{it} + \beta_4 G_{it} + U_i + E_{it} \quad \dots\dots\dots 3.11$$

$$TI_{it} = \beta + \beta_1 GDPG_{it} + \beta_2 INF_{it} + \beta_3 G_{it} + \beta_4 PS_{it} + \beta_5 EXI_{it} + \beta_6 DP_{it} + U_i + E_{it} \quad \dots\dots\dots 3.12$$

Two main assumptions can be made considering the individual specific effect:

- i. The assumption of random effects is that individual unobserved heterogeneity is uncorrelated with the independent variables.
- ii. According to the fixed effect assumption, the individual specific impact is connected to the independent factors.

3.3.1.4 Selecting POLS, FEM, or REM

i. The F- test or Likelihood Ratio test (Chow test) used to select between the Fixed Effect Model (FEM), and Pooled OLS (Wooldridge, 2011, & Gujarati, 2015). Accordingly, the hypotheses will be as the following:

H0: All the constants are the same (homogenous), so, Pooled OLS (POLS) is the appropriate method.

H1: All the constants are not the same (heterogenous), so, Fixed Effect Model FEM is appropriate.

$$F = \frac{(RSS_p - (RSS1+RSS2))/k}{\frac{(RSS1+RSS2)}{(N1+N2-2k)}} \dots\dots\dots 3.13$$

where:

RSSp = pooled (combined) regression line.

RSS1 = regression line before break.

RSS2 = regression line after break.

k = number of variables.

N1 = Sample 1.

N2 = Sample 2.

Find the F-critical value from the F-table. Reject the null hypothesis if your calculated F-value falls into the rejection region (i.e. if the calculated F-value is greater than the F-critical value).

ii. Next Breusch–Pagan BP Lagrange Multiplier (LM) statistic will be calculated to choose between POLS and Random Effect Model, so:

H_0 : No REM or POLS effects.

H_1 : REM is the appropriate method.

$$LM = \frac{IT}{2(T-1)} \cdot \left[\frac{\sum_{i=1}^I (\sum_{t=1}^T \hat{\mu}_{it})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{t=1}^T \hat{\mu}_{it}^2} - 1 \right]$$

where,
T is number of time periods and *I* is number of cross sectional units 3.14

The LM statistic has *k* degrees of freedom and follows the Chi square distribution.

iii. Lastly, in order to choose between the Fixed Effect Model (FEM) and the Random Effect Model (REM), we implemented the Hausman test statistic, which is;

$$m = q'(\text{var}\hat{\beta}^{\text{FE}} - \text{var}\hat{\beta}^{\text{RE}})^{-1}q \quad \dots\dots\dots 3.15$$

$$\text{with } q = \hat{\beta}^{\text{FE}} - \hat{\beta}^{\text{RE}} \quad \dots\dots\dots 3.16$$

Under RE, the matrix difference in brackets is positive, as the RE estimator is efficient and any other estimator has a large variance. The *m* statistic is distributed χ^2 under the null of RE. According to Gujarati and Porter (2011) the following hypotheses are tested:

H_0 : REM is the appropriate method.

H_1 : FEM is the appropriate method.

3.3.2 The Dynamic Models:

In case if the static model post estimation tests like Multicollinearity, Heteroskedasticity, and Autocorrelation, reject their corresponding H_0 , we infer that the selected static model is inefficient and unreliable. As an alternative we try to estimate a dynamic model.

Firstly, we need to investigate whether the estimated model would take a dynamic pattern or not. We do this investigation by entering one lag of the dependent variable as an added regressor into the selected random effect model.

Secondly, observing the t-statistic for the added lag dependent variable, if it is significant, we conclude that construction of a dynamic model would be more reliable. Besides reviewing the studies of Chuku, Abang, and Isip (2017); McGovern (2012, p.51); Kis-Katos, Liebert, and Schulze (2011); and Richardson (2011), all agree on dynamic interactions between terrorism and macroeconomic determinants, and these effects are relatively significant in countries exposed to terrorist attacks in past.

In such conditions incorporation of the lag dependent variable as a regressor would be desirable, which is compatible with the work carried out by reputable authors such as; Andersen and Hsiao (1980), Arellano and Bond (1991), Arellano and Bover (1995), and Blundell and Bond (1998). In other words, utilizing a lag dependent variable as a regressor in an econometric model allows for dynamic adjustment. However, the lagged dependent variable is linked with the cross section-specific impact, introducing the issue of endogeneity. Because of this endogeneity, least squares estimators may be inconsistent. Therefore, use of instrumental variable (IV) or generalized method of moments (GMM) approaches are preferred (Das 2019, 541). Or we can estimate the error correction related models such as Mean Group, Pool Mean Group, and Dynamic Fixed Effect (Pesaran Shin and Smith, 1999).

As mentioned previously in this study sample, the number of time span $T=22$, which is relatively greater than the number of cross section countries $N=7$, therefore the panel dataset of this study considered as long panel dataset. According to Das (2019, p.458); Cameron and Trivedi (2009, p. 230), long panels are convenient for performing dynamic analysis.

3.3.2.1 Which Dynamic Modeling Approach to Develop, GMM or ARDL?

Following Roodman (2006), a fundamental property of dynamic panel data models, such as the GMM approaches which involve: the Difference- GMM of Arellano and Bond (1991), and the System-GMM by Arellano and Bover (1995), and Blundell and Bond (1998), is N should be greater than T , or $N \rightarrow \infty$ and T is finite. Therefore, adopting the GMM approach yields superior results, because the results of the estimated coefficients would be inconsistent, and over identified for two main reasons;

- i. small N causes unreliable serial correlation test.
- ii. As the time span (T) gets larger, we might get larger number of instruments as well, which will affect the validation and accuracy of Sargan's overidentification restrictions test (Arellano and Bond, 1991; Blundell and Bond, 1998). Therefore, the null hypothesis of instruments exogeneity would be rejected.
- iii. In addition, GMM approaches detects the short-run dynamic effects only, and the stationarity of the regressors will be ignored because it works only on short time series, while the existence of long run equilibrium relationship would be unclear or spurious (Christopoulos and Tsionas, 2004).
- iv. Serious biases might occur due to the imposition of slope coefficients homogeneity assumptions for the lag dependent variable. Thus, we might get inconsistent and misleading long run coefficients, unless the coefficients of the slopes are certainly identical (Pesaran and Smith, 1995; Pesaran, 1997; Pesaran and Shin, 1999).

Due to the aforementioned reasons, we cannot depend on the inconsistent and erroneous results provided by the GMM techniques for the panel dataset under investigation, See Table 3.2 below.

Table 3. 2 Validity of GMM Estimations, Considering Number of T and N

Number of groups, countries, or entities (N)			
		High	Low
Period of Time (T)	High	Low probability of overidentification	High probability of overidentification
	Low	Normal condition of panel	The number of observations can be insufficient to perform the model

Source: (Labra and Torrecillas 2018, 40)

As an alternative, we can estimate the ARDL models, such as; mean group (MG), pool mean group (PMG), and dynamic fixed effect (DFE) models for our panel dataset, as they do not account for endogeneity produced by heterogeneity.

3.3.2.2 The ARDL Models

The error correction based on autoregressive distributed lag ARDL (p,q) model used to determine the influence of the variables of interest. The ARDL regressors can be stationary at I (0), or I (1), and mix of I (0) and I (1). No, I (2) or higher.

Following Pesaran et al. (1999), using the autoregressive distributed lag ARDL (p, q) method, we can enter the dynamic heterogeneous regression into the error correction model. The general form of panel ARDL model for t= 1, 2, ..., T periods, and i= 1, 2, N groups is as follows:

$$ARDL (p, q) TI_{it} = \sum_{k=1}^p \lambda_{ik} TI_{i,t-k} + \sum_{k=0}^q \delta_{ik} X_{i,t-k} + \omega_i + \epsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots 3.17$$

Where;

TI= Terrorism Index.

Xit = (k×1) vector of explanatory variables for group I, can be I(0), I(1), or mix.

λ_{ik} = Coefficients of lagged dependent variable (scaler).

δ_{ik} = (k×1) coefficients vectors.

ω_i = group-specific fixed effect error term.

ϵ_{it} = iid error term.

By reparametrizing ARDL to get the vector error correction model VECM we get:

$$\Delta TI_{it} = \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \lambda_{ik} \Delta TI_{i,t-k} + \sum_{k=0}^{q-1} \delta_{ik} \Delta XI_{i,t-k} + \Phi_i(TI_{i,t-1} + \beta_i XI_{it}) + \omega_i + \epsilon_{it} \quad \dots\dots\dots 3.18$$

Where;

- i. λ_{ik} , δ_{ik} = the short run coefficients.
- ii. Φ_i = group-specific error correction coefficients (carries a minus sign).
- iii. β_i = vector of long-run coefficients.

The estimated parameters of interest would be:

- The long- run coefficients.
- The short- run coefficients.
- The speed of adjustment or the error correction term.

3.3.2.3 Types of Panels Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) Models

i. The Mean Group (MG)

MG is least restrictive approach comparing with OLS approaches. MG is allowing for parameter heterogeneity (no cross-country restrictions). It involves estimating different model for each country and generating averages of the country-specific coefficients to get consistent estimates of the long-run

coefficients. The assumptions are strong: the group-specific parameters must be distributed independently of the regressors, and the regressors must be strictly exogenous. Furthermore, it does not account for the fact that certain parameters may be shared between groups.

ii. Dynamic Fixed Effect (DFE)

DFE is an approach that its Individual-specific effects (such as country, state, and company) are controllable. The model slope coefficients must be homogeneous, and allowing only for the intercepts to differ among countries.

iii. Pool Mean Group (PMG)

PMG is a hybrid model (between DFE and MG) which allows intercepts, short-run coefficients, and error variances to vary freely among groups while requiring long-run coefficients to be the same, with an emphasis on the unique characteristic of the PMG model above the other error-correction based estimations such as MG and DFE (Samargandi, Fidrmuc and Ghosh 2014, pp.9-10).

In short, from equation (3.17) the properties of DFE, MG, and PMG estimators are:

- i. DFE estimator assumes λ_{ik} , δ_{ik} , and β_i are the same across countries.
- ii. MG estimator assumes λ_{ik} , δ_{ik} , and β_i vary across countries.
- iii. PMG estimator assumes only β_i are same across countries.

3.3.2.4 Selecting PMG, MG, or DFE Model

The Hausman test is commonly used to choose the more efficient model between each pair of the dynamic models. Such as selection between PMG and MG, selection between PMG and DFE, and selection between MG and DFE models. According to Piroette (1999), the MG model enables parameters to be independent across countries or entities and does not take into consideration

group heterogeneity. However, Pesaran and Shin (1999) indicated that the PMG model is superior since it provides short-run variance coefficients for every country. Long term coefficients, on the other hand, are expected to be homogenous (similar) across all countries. In contrast, the MG model only accepts heterogeneous (different) lengths of time between countries for short and long-term coefficients.

Selecting PMG or MG model is determined by the null hypothesis test of the Hausman's χ^2 statistic. If the null hypothesis is accepted, the PMG model is used since it is more efficient than the MG model. If the null hypothesis is rejected, the MG model is used instead of the PMG model. When choosing between the PMG and DFE models, if the null hypothesis is accepted, then PMG model is superior to the DFE model (Shaari Abidin and Karim 2020, 620).

3.4 The Descriptive Statistics for the Variables Under Study

Table 3.3 demonstrates the descriptive statistics for the studied variables in the seven selected countries during the period from 2000 to 2021, with each variable having 154 observations. The researcher found that the overall average terrorism index for the seven countries is 6.47, ranging from 0.00 to 10.00, with a standard deviation of 2.59 from the mean. Examining the overall averages of the economic determinants, we find that the growth rate of GDP increases by 3.27%, annually. Inflation and unemployment rates are 10% and 7.77%, respectively. And, the overall average of economic globalization is 38.963.

Table 3. 3 Descriptive Statistics of the Studied Variables.

Variable	Mean	Std. dev.	Min	Max	Observations
overall	6.477	2.592	0.000	10.000	N = 154
TI between		1.642	4.413	8.397	n = 7
within		2.096	1.780	10.000	T = 22

Variable	Mean	Std. dev.	Min	Max	Observations	
GDPG	overall	3.273	-		N = 154	
	between	8.501	36.660	53.390	n = 7	
	within	2.526	-1.098	5.221	T = 22	
INF	overall	10.043	-		N = 154	
	between	11.204	10.100	63.100	n = 7	
	within	4.875	2.428	15.977	T = 22	
UEM	overall	7.771	4.083	0.400	16.200	N = 154
	between	4.113	1.866	12.784	n = 7	
	within	1.441	5.659	13.899	T = 22	
G	overall	38.963	7.135	26.646	55.796	N = 154
	between	6.731	31.782	49.159	n = 7	
	within	3.439	26.700	46.276	T = 22	
PS	overall	-2.058	0.669	-3.180	0.280	N = 154
	between	0.349	-2.459	-1.380	n = 7	
	within	0.585	-3.648	-0.398	T = 22	
EXI	overall	8.680	1.370	5.400	10.000	N = 154
	between	1.216	6.125	9.608	n = 7	
	within	0.776	5.943	10.443	T = 22	
DP	overall	8.617	0.917	5.500	10.000	N = 154
	between	0.846	6.937	9.624	n = 7	
	within	0.473	7.180	10.080	T = 22	

Source: Researcher analysis using Stata17.

The seven countries overall mean of the terrorism index TI is 6.47, for the period years 2000-2021, which is considered a high rate, as Figure 3.2 shows.

Figure 3.2 Global Terrorism Impact Ratings

Source: (GTI 2022, p.8)

3.5 Correlation Between the Variables

Correlational analysis entails investigating the link between the variables in question. For example, one may investigate if there is a negative relationship between the number of terrorist occurrences and the amount of political stability in a certain period of time. Alternatively, one may look at if there is a negative relationship between the presence of effective counterterrorism measures and the number of casualties.

Correlation coefficients vary from -1 to 1. A correlation value near to 1 suggests a significant positive association, which means that when one variable grows, so does the other. A correlation value around -1 implies a significant negative link, implying that when one variable grows, the other tends to decrease. A correlation value close to zero suggests weak or no

The following correlation coefficients matrix Table 3.3 depicts the correlations between the investigated variables.

Table 3.4 Correlations Coefficients Between Pairwise Variables

	TI	UEM	INF	GDPG	G	PS	EXI	DP
TI	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
UEM	0.1139	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
INF	0.1060	0.1625	1	0	0	0	0	0
GDPG	-0.0759	-0.1776	-0.3308	1	0	0	0	0
G	0.0391	0.2021	0.2444	0.0916	1	0	0	0
PS	-0.6782	-0.0475	-0.1482	0.1301	-0.0723	1	0	0
EXI	0.2229	0.1051	-0.0478	-0.0209	-0.2592	-0.3946	1	0
DP	0.1952	-0.0627	-0.1999	0.1737	0.1602	-0.3938	0.3719	1

Source: Researchers' analysis using Stata17.

Considering the correlation between each pair of the studied variables, generally no strong correlation exists as the correlation coefficients of the majority are less than 0.7, thus we can decide that there will not be a high level of multicollinearity problem for the estimated linear models.

3.6 Panel Data Modeling

3.6.1 Specifying the Models

The model specification for the economic variables will be as follows:

$$TI = f(GDPG, INF, UEM, G)$$

While the model specification for the combination of economic, political, and demographic variables will be as follows:

$$TI = f(GDPG, INF, G, PS, DP, EXI).$$

Where; TI is the terrorism index, GDPG annual GDP growth rate, INF inflation rate, UEM the unemployment rate, G economic globalization index, PS political stability index, DP demographic pressures index, and EXI external intervention index.

3.6.2 Mechanism for Panel Data Modeling in this Study

Figure 3.3 shows a flow chart depicting the mechanism of panel data modeling. Appendices 1.1 to 1.8 illustrate the computational results for the panel data analysis of the present chapter. Taking into consideration both of long-run and short-run effects, this analysis applied on the panel data of the selected countries, for $T > N$, where $T=22$ years, and $N=7$ countries. Therefore, relying on the literatures cited in this chapter, the mechanism of panel data modeling in this study is summed up as follows:

- 1- Strat inputting the data.
- 2- Conducting the descriptive statistics for all variables.
- 3- Testing for variables cross section dependency (CSD), see Table 3.5.
- 4- Performing the first-generation unit root test for variables with no CSD, see Table 3.6.
- 5- Performing the second-generation unit root test for variables with CSD, see Table 3.7.
- 6- Also, checking for variable stationarity by using structural break unit root test in order to account for the existence of structural breaks in the series, see Table 3.8.
- 7- After approving the stationarity of the data, estimate REM, FEM, and POLS models.
- 8- Performing Brousch-Pegan LM test to select either the POLS or RE model.
- 9- Performing Likelihood Ratio F-test to select either the FEM or POLS model.
- 10- Performing Hausman χ^2 -test to select either the REM or the FEM.
- 11- Conducting the post estimation tests for the validation of the selected model. If it's not valid, then trying to diagnose for the dynamism or significance of the dynamic part of the selected model, which is lag of the dependent variable added to the chosen model in the previous step, see figure 3.3.

- 12- Testing for panel data cointegration of the specified model using; Pedroni, Kaw, Westerlund, ...etc. However, in this study the researcher preferred to depend on the second generation cointegration test of Westerlund, because it accounts for the presence of CSD among the panels. If the variables were cointegrated then we would be going for the dynamic modeling techniques such as GMM, or ARDL. Considering the dataset of this study as $T > N$ we use the ARDL approaches, such as PMG, MG, and DFE.
- 13- Performing Hausman χ^2 -test between each pair of the PMG, MG, and DFE models to select the most appropriate one.
- 14- Conducting Panel Granger causality test between the dependent variable and each independent variable at a time, in order to reveal whether the independent variable could be used for future forecasting's or not.

Figure 3.3 Flow Chart of Panel Data Modeling Mechanism

Designed by the researcher, 2022.

3.7 Pre-Tests for Model Estimation

3.7.1 Cross Section Dependency (CSD)

Panel data Cross-sectional dependency (CSD) in macro panels has garnered significant attention in recent years, especially since the 2010s. This dependency represents a form of correlation stemming from common shocks, that have diverse effects across countries. For instance, events like the 2007 worldwide financial crisis, oil price shocks in the 1970s, and rapid increases in terrorist incidents in the Middle East, North Africa, and South Asia, which have notably elevated terrorism index records in the last decade. Additionally, CSD can also refer to domestic consequences' spillover effects between countries or regions. Other factors contributing to CSD may include omitted common effects, spatial effects, and interactions of socioeconomic factors (Atasoy, 2017).

As per Atasoy (2017); Apergis, Christou, and Gupta (2017), CSD in panel data sets is a common issue. In this study, we employ the CD test introduced by Pesaran (2004), and the Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test introduced by Breusch and Pagan (BP) in 1980 to examine the presence of CSD in our panel dataset. For each test, the null and alternative hypotheses are as follows:

H0: $\text{Cov}(u_{it}, u_{jt}) = 0$, for all $t, i \neq j$, or the panels are cross sectionally independent

H1: $\text{Cov}(u_{it}, u_{jt}) \neq 0$, for all $t, i \neq j$, or the panels are cross sectionally dependent

Group wise cross-sectional dependence (CSD) test for this study's raw data, using Pesaran (2004) CD test, and Breusch-Pagan LM (1980) test, and the average of correlation coefficients are illustrated in Table 3.5 below:

Table 3.5 CD and LM Tests for Panels Cross Section Dependence (CSD)

Variable	CD-test		LM-test		Abs. (corr.)
	Stat.	p-value	Stat.	p-value	
TI	16.320	0.000	281.197	0.000	0.759
INF	1.160	0.245	23.573	0.314	0.196
GDPG	1.050	0.291	16.252	0.755	0.154
G	2.310	0.021	88.869	0.000	0.359
UEM	10.280	0.000	173.867	0.000	0.547
PS	6.620	0.000	107.018	0.000	0.367
EXI	2.780	0.005	98.178	0.000	0.395
DP	0.100	0.923	77.950	0.000	0.345

Source: Researcher analysis using Eviews13.

A cross section dependence (CSD) test of Pesaran's (2004) developed to test for the degree of dependency among the data of balanced panel data with $N < T$ (De Hoyos and Sarafidis 2006, 490). Reading the CSD test of Pesaran's CD statistic in Table 3.5, we see that the statistic's p-values of TI, G, UEM, PS, and EXI are less than the 5% significance level, thus we reject H_0 . So, we conclude that CSD exists. While INF, GDPG, and DP have p-values more than 5%. Therefore, we can say they are cross-sectionally independent.

Nowadays, testing for cross-sectional dependency is essential when fitting panel-data models. Since $T > N$ of our panel dataset, then we can also apply the Breusch and Pagan (1980) BP LM test for CSD test (Bhujabal Sethi and Padhan 2021; Baum 2001, 2003, 2004). By doing so, we reached to the same conclusions by using the Pesaran CD test, except for the variable DP, so we reject H_0 since the variable's p-value is less than 5% and conclude that DP is not cross-sectionally independent. Appendix 1 shows the strength of pairwise countries correlation for each of the studied variables.

3.7.2 The Stationarity Test (Unit Root Test)

In general, there are two generations for testing the stationarity of panel datasets. The first-generation tests, which assume that the countries or the entities are cross-sectionally independent, but the second generation tolerates for cross-sectional dependency (Pesaran 2007). In this regard, Table 3.6 summarizes the commonly used methods of first-generation, and second-generation panel unit root tests.

Table 3.6 First-Generation, and Second-Generation Unit Root Tests

First Generation		Second Generation	
H0: No Stationarity	H0: Stationarity	H0: No Stationarity	H0: Stationarity
Levin and Lin (1992, 1993)	Hadri (2000)	Bai and Ng (2001, 2004)	Bai and Ng (2005) Harris et al. (2005)
Levin, Lin, and Chu (2002)		Moon and Perron (2004a)	
Harris and Tzavalis (1999)		Philips and Sul (2003a)	
Im, Pesaran, and Shin (1997, 2002, 2003)		Pesaran (2003)	
Maddala and Wu (1999)		Choi (2002)	
Choi (1999, 2001)		Pesaran (2007)	

Source: prepared by the researcher depending on related literature.

In this study the researcher applied the first-generation unit root tests for the variables that don't have CSD issue. The preferred tests are Levin Lin and Chu (2002), which usually adopted for balanced panel data sets and assumes $N/T \rightarrow 0$, and the ADF test. Observing Table 3.7 we see that INF, GDPG, and DP are stationary at both level and the first difference.

Table 3.7 First Generation Unit Root Tests of Levin, Lin and Chu, and ADF

Variable	LLC Level		LLC First Difference		ADF Level		ADF First Difference	
	Constant	Constant and Trend	Constant	Constant and Trend	Constant	Constant and Trend	Constant	Constant and Trend
INF	-4.159 ***	-3.598 ***	-7.082 ***	-4.353 ***	47.924 ***	38.428 ***	94.645 ***	73.224 ***
GDPG	-5.840 ***	-4.750 ***	-8.272 ***	-4.914 ***	53.882 ***	43.608 ***	102.568 ***	71.548 ***
DP	-0.852	-0.592	-9.977 ***	-6.744 ***	23.964 **	16.741	93.0006 ***	65.816 ***

Significant at: *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0 , Source: Researchers' analysis using Eviews13.

Due to the presence of cross-sectional dependencies, traditional first-generation unit root tests can yield inaccurate and biased results in panel data analysis. To address this issue, second-generation unit root tests are commonly employed (Pesaran 2007; Das 2019; Baltagi 2021). In this study, we focus on variables that exhibit cross-sectional dependence, namely TI, UEM, G, PS, EXI, and DP as in Table 3.4, and subject them to second-generation unit root tests.

So, two specific second-generation unit root tests are utilized: the Cross Section Augmented Dickey Fuller (CADF), developed by Pesaran (2007), and the Im, Pesaran. And Shin (CIPS) test, proposed by Im et al. (2003). Both tests share the same null hypothesis of;

H0: the variable is non-stationarity, and the alternative hypothesis of;

H1: the variable is stationary.

The results are presented in Table 3.8, showing that few variables are stationarity at the level, while all of them are stationarity at the first difference.

Table 3.8 Second Generation Unit Root Tests of CADF and CIPS.

Variable	CADF Level		CADF First Difference		CIPS Level		CIPS First Difference	
	Constant	Constant and Trend	Constant	Constant and Trend	Constant	Constant and Trend	Constant	Constant and Trend
TI	-2.281*	-2.057	-2.941 ***	-3.550 ***	-2.210*	-2.032	-3.984 ***	-4.137 ***
UEM	-1.272	-1.974	-3.008 ***	-2.805 *	-1.526	-2.501	-4.332 ***	-4.194 ***
G	-1.821	-2.583	-3.474 ***	-3.599 ***	-2.050	-2.538	-4.548 ***	-4.560 ***
PS	-2.521 **	-2.675	-3.407 ***	-3.340 ***	-2.213*	-2.737*	-4.170 ***	-3.963 ***
EXI	-1.742	-1.543	-2.295*	-2.803*	-1.064	-1.016	-3.833 ***	-4.330 ***
DP	-2.196	-2.194	-2.736 ***	-2.770*	-2.319*	-2.327	-4.431 ***	-4.391 ***

CADF t- bar statistic, CIPS statistic. Significant at: *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.

Source: Researcher analysis using Stata17.

In the real world, changes in policy regimes or significant global events are often considered as factors that lead to structural breaks. Examples of such events include the Great Depression, oil price shocks, World War II, terrorist attacks, and the Covid-19 pandemic, ... etc. To address the impact of structural breaks in panel data sets, Karavias and Tzavalis (2014) developed a unit root test.

The first Stata command, "xtbunitroot" is utilized to conduct panel unit root tests that account for breaks in the intercepts of individual series, or both intercepts and linear trends. This test allows for the consideration of one or two breaks at known or unknown dates, considers cross-section heteroskedasticity and dependence, and accommodates non-normal errors. The test exhibits

significant power against both homogeneous and heterogeneous alternatives and is applicable to panels with small or large time-series dimensions (Chen Karavias and Tzavalis 2022).

Conventional unit root tests may be misled by structural breaks, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis when the unit root is stationary, or vice versa. The ignorance of structural fractures can bias the test power and result in erroneous inferences (Chen, Karavias, and Tzavalis, 2022). Table 3.9 presents the results of the KT (Karavias and Tzavalis) unit root test, which accounts for structural breaks in our panel data. The hypotheses tested are as follows:

H0: All panel time series are unit root processes.

H1: Some or all of the panel time series are stationary processes.

Table 3.9 Karavias and Tzavalis KT (2014) Panel Unit Root Test

Variable	Level		First Difference		No. of Structural Breaks	Accept
	constant	Constant & trend	constant	Constant & trend		
TI	-7.7875*** (-0.1110)	-2.4455** (-2.7162)	-13.5868*** (-3.3680)	-7.2104*** (-3.0783)	1	H1
UEM	-4.3464*** (-0.2600)	-2.5923** (-2.5585)	-14.5475*** (-4.4779)	-8.8961*** (-2.5719)	1	H1
INF	-7.5420** (-7.7264)	-5.2191 (-6.1026)	-19.1472*** (-4.9632)	-10.3016 *** (-3.1908)	1	H1
GDPG	-14.7027*** (-5.0390)	-8.6454*** (-3.1356)	-23.3463*** (-1.4356)	-13.6411*** (-1.8089)	1	H1
G	-4.7457*** (-1.9301)	-1.8500 (-3.1033)	-14.8115*** (-3.2224)	-7.8696*** (-2.4239)	1	H1
PS	-1.2878 ** (-0.9441)	-0.7150 (-1.2346)	-6.0677* (-7.6880)	-4.0076* (-5.3155)	1	H1

Variable		Level		First Difference		No. of Structural Breaks	Accept
		constant	Constant & trend	constant	Constant & trend		
DP	CD No CSD	-0.6732 (-1.6009)	-0.2753 (-1.2254)	-8.9849 (-3.0940)	-5.4631*** (-2.2411)	1	H1
	LM CSD	-1.1792** (-1.0296)	-0.3799 (-0.8938)	-8.4633*** (-3.6181)	-4.9394*** (-2.7952)		
EXI		-0.9264*** (-0.0988)	-0.7769** (-0.6960)	-9.0528*** (-3.5603)	-5.6279*** (-2.5913)	1	H1

The numbers in parentheses reflect Bootstrap crucial values. The minimum Z-statistic corresponds to the following significance levels: Significant at: *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Source: Researcher analysis using Stata17.

Karavias and Tzavalis (KT) test results indicate that all four economic variables experience stationarity at both the original level and the first difference, taking into consideration the results of Cross-Sectional Dependence (CSD) test which presented in Table 3.5. So, we reject the null hypothesis (H0) and accept the alternative hypothesis (H1) that some or all of the panel time series are stationary processes. Similarly, the other three variables, social and political variables, show stationarity at both the level and the first difference.

In summary, Karavias and Tzavalis (2014) unit root test reveals that all the variables, in the presence of one structural break and CSD in our panel dataset, are stationary either at the level or at the first difference. As per Engle and Granger (1987); a group of variables that are stationary at the first difference $I(1)$, indicates the presence of cointegration among them. Therefore, these $I(1)$ series are in long-run equilibrium, meaning they move together, although some random variation may occur. Since all the variables under study are stationary at the first difference $I(1)$, we can conclude that they are

cointegrated in the long run. To further support this conclusion, cointegration tests will be conducted in the following section.

3.7.3 Cointegration Tests

To examine the long-run cointegration between panels, we adopt first-generation cointegration tests that assume cross-sectional independence among panels. Therefore, we utilize the tests proposed by Pedroni (2004) and Kao (1999). According to Baltagi (2005, 256), the Pedroni test exhibits higher accuracy than the Kao test when the time span (T) is significantly larger than the groups' dimension (N). Both tests outperform the LR-bar test developed by Larsson et al. (2001). However, after considering Cross-Sectional Dependence (CSD) identification, these tests no longer produce reliable findings. In light of this, Westerlund (2007) introduced an error correction-based cointegration test that accounts for CSD between the panels. This test is commonly referred to as the second-generation cointegration test. The core concept of this test is to examine the nonexistence of cointegration by assessing whether error correction occurs among individual panel members or among the entire panels. The results of both first and second-generation cointegration tests for both models, one focusing on economic variables and the other including a mix of Economic, Political, and Demographic variables, are presented in Table 3.10.

Table 3.10 The Cointegration Tests

Cointegration test	M1 (Economic variables)	M2 (Economic, Political, and Demographic variables)																								
Westerlund	Variance ratio sta. = 2.4074 P-value= 0.0080	Variance ratio sta.= 5.139 P-value=0.0000																								
Pedroni	<table style="width: 100%; border: none;"> <tr> <td></td> <td style="text-align: center;"><u>Stat.</u></td> <td style="text-align: center;"><u>p-value</u></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Modified Phillips Perron t</td> <td style="text-align: center;">3.4334</td> <td style="text-align: center;">0.0003</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Phillips Perron t</td> <td style="text-align: center;">2.5176</td> <td style="text-align: center;">0.0059</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Augmented Dickey Fuller t</td> <td style="text-align: center;">3.1002</td> <td style="text-align: center;">0.001</td> </tr> </table>		<u>Stat.</u>	<u>p-value</u>	Modified Phillips Perron t	3.4334	0.0003	Phillips Perron t	2.5176	0.0059	Augmented Dickey Fuller t	3.1002	0.001	<table style="width: 100%; border: none;"> <tr> <td></td> <td style="text-align: center;"><u>Stat.</u></td> <td style="text-align: center;"><u>p-value</u></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Modified Phillips Perron t</td> <td style="text-align: center;">2.7578</td> <td style="text-align: center;">0.0029</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Phillips Perron t</td> <td style="text-align: center;">-1.2838</td> <td style="text-align: center;">0.0996</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Augmented Dickey Fuller t</td> <td style="text-align: center;">-0.9300</td> <td style="text-align: center;">0.1762</td> </tr> </table>		<u>Stat.</u>	<u>p-value</u>	Modified Phillips Perron t	2.7578	0.0029	Phillips Perron t	-1.2838	0.0996	Augmented Dickey Fuller t	-0.9300	0.1762
	<u>Stat.</u>	<u>p-value</u>																								
Modified Phillips Perron t	3.4334	0.0003																								
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Augmented Dickey Fuller t	-0.9300	0.1762																								

Cointegration test	M1 (Economic variables)			M2 (Economic, Political, and Demographic variables)		
	<u>test</u>	<u>Stat.</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>test</u>	<u>Stat.</u>	<u>p-value</u>
Kao	Modified Dickey Fuller t	-0.4614	0.3223	Modified Dickey Fuller t	2.0449	0.0204
	Dickey Fuller t	-1.0575	0.1451	Dickey Fuller t	-1.8038	0.0356
	Augmented Dickey Fuller t	1.2442	0.1067	Augmented Dickey Fuller t	-0.9198	0.1788
	Unadjusted modified Dickey Fuller t	-0.7651	0.2221	Unadjusted modified Dickey Fuller t	-2.5519	0.0054
	Unadjusted Dickey Fuller t	-1.2371	0.1080	Unadjusted Dickey Fuller t	-2.0083	0.0223

Source: Researcher analysis using Stata17.

From Table 3.10 the p-values of the corresponding statistics of Westerlund and Pedroni tests are less than 0.01, so, all panels of the economic model are cointegrated, therefore, we reject H0 which says there is no cointegration between all panels. While the Kao test shows revers results. But since the dependent and most of the independent variables are crosse sectional dependent, we rely on the second generation cointegration test of Westerlund (2007), therefore we conclude that all panels of our economic model are cointegrated. Regarding panels cointegration of the Economic, Political, and Demographic variables model, we also reject the H0 and accept H1 of all panels are cointegrated, because the p-values of Westerlund and Kao statistics are less than 0.05.

3.7.4 Models Break dates

- i. The results of Ditzen, Karavias & Westerlund DKW (2021) test for multiple breaks dates of the economic model is shown in table 3.11.

H0: no break(s) vs. H1: 1 break(s)

Table 3.11 DKW Test of Break Dates for Economic Variables Model

Bai & Perron Critical Values				
	Test statistic	1% Critical value	5% Critical value	10% Critical value
supW(tau)	22.31	5.06	4.05	3.56
Estimated break dates	2009 , Trimming: 0.15			

Source: Researcher analysis using Stata17.

The statistic of supW(tau) is significant at 1% level, with reference to Bai & Perron Critical Values. Thus, we reject H₀, and decide that the economic model has a break date in year 2009.

- ii. The results of Ditzen, Karavias & Westerlund (2021) test for multiple breaks dates of the Mix model of Economic, Political, and Demographic variables, shown in table 3.12.

H₀: no break(s) vs. H₁: 1 break(s).

Table 3.12 DKW Test of Break Dates for the Assorted Variables Model

Bai & Perron Critical Values				
	Test statistic	1% Critical value	5% Critical value	10% Critical value
supW(tau)	13.20	4.08	3.35	2.99
Estimated break date	2009 , Trimming: 0.15			

Source: Researcher analysis using Stata17.

Upon observing Bai and Perron Critical Values, we find that the statistic of supW(tau) is significant at the 1% level. Consequently, we reject the null hypothesis (H₀) and accept the result that the model with a mix of economic, political, and demographic indicators has a break date, which occurred in year 2009. This might be explained by the macro-indicators were encountering greater shocks in their trajectories in year 2009 as a result of the selected

countries socioeconomic fragility. As absenteeism and not appreciating the role of the law, as well as the prevalence of militias and authoritarian governments.

3.8 The Estimated Models for the Economic Indicators

3.8.1 The Static Models

The static models in Table 3.13 displays the relationship and the magnitude of the coefficients for the economic determinants; INF, GDPG, UEM, and G with the dependent variable TI, and their related tests for each. Also, selection of one model from each pair of models is examined, in order to reach the best static model via model preference test in the table.

Table 3.13 The Estimated Static Models by Using the Economic Predictors.

Variables	POLS			FEM			REM			Accept
	Coef.	Std. Err.	t. stat.	Coef.	Std. Err.	t. stat.	Coef.	Std. Err.	t. stat.	
INF	0.018	0.021	0.88	0.043	0.017	2.58**	0.04	0.017	2.37**	
UEM	0.06	0.054	1.12	0.385	0.12	3.2***	0.28	0.099	2.84***	
G	0.001	0.032	0.04	-0.067	0.051	-1.31	-0.071	0.046	-1.55	
GDPG	-0.01	0.027	-0.38	-0.024	0.021	-1.14	-0.025	0.021	-1.19	
Constant	5.806	1.184	4.90***	5.739	2.433	2.36**	6.733	2.144	3.14***	
Model statistic	F (4, 149) = 0.830			F (4,143) = 7.06 ***			Chi ² = 23.445 ***			
Mean dependent variable	6.477			6.477			6.477			
Overall R ²	0.022			0.0172			0.017			
R ² within	-			0.1648			0.163			
R ² between	-			0.0034			0.010			

Variables	POLS	FEM	REM	Accept
CD- test ¹	5.77***	10.99 ***	9.710 ***	H1
Sigma - u	-	2.377	1.751	
Sigma - e	-	1.980	1.980	
rho	-	0.590	0.4387	
² Slope heterogeneity	6.472 ***	-	-	H1
Model Preference test	B.P. LM.: Chi-bar ² (01) = 192.44 ***	LR: F (6, 143) = 18.87 ***	Hausman: Chi ² =7.2512 d.f =4, P-value =0.1232	RE
Heteroskedasticity	³ B.P. Chi ² (1) = 2.33	Wald Chi ² (7) =435.46 ***	Wald Chi ² (7) =2393.62 ***	H1
Autocorrelation	⁴ F (1,6) = 107.297 ***	⁵ Q(p)-stat= 17.68 ***	⁵ Q(p)-stat= 14.41***	H1
⁶ Group wise Correlation of residuals	-	B-P LM test: Chi ² (21) = 175.463, P-V = 0.000	-	H1
Number of obs.	154	154	154	

¹ (Pesaran, 2004, H0: cross-section independence $CD \sim N(0,1)$). ² (Pesaran, Yamagata. 2008 H0: slope coefficients are homogenous). ³ (Breusch–Pagan/Cook–Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity, H0: constant variance). ⁴ (Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data, H0: no first-order autocorrelation). ⁵ Bias-corrected Born and Breitung (2016) Q(p)-test on variables H0: “No serial correlation up to order 2”. Ha: “Some serial correlation up to order 2.” ⁶ (Breusch-Pagan LM test H0: Group Residuals independence). Significant at: *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0 .

Source: Researcher analysis using Stata17.

The P-Value of F-statistic, Likelihood Ratio (Chaw) test, has been found to be statistically significant at the 5% level. This guide us to reject H0 and accept H1. Indicating that the Fixed Effect Model (FEM) is appropriate for the analysis. Similarly, the P-Value of Breusch and Pagan Lagrange Multiplier (BP LM) Chi²-bar found to be significant at the 5% level, leading to the rejection of H0, which suggests that there are random effects. Consequently, the Random Effect Model (REM) is deemed appropriate. The results of Hausman test show that the P-Value of Chi² statistic is insignificant at both the 5% and 10% levels.

Therefore, we accept H_0 , implying that the coefficients are equal, and we conclude REM is appropriate for the economic regressors.

3.8.1.1 Interpretation of the selected REM

The estimated REM in Table 3.13 demonstrates a significant positive relationship between INF and TI, UEM and TI, at 5% and 1% significant level, respectively. Therefore, as inflation rate increases by 1% terrorism increases by 0.04 of a point, while as unemployment rate rises by 1% terrorism rises by 0.28 of a point, *ceteris paribus*. As stated by Richardson (2011), unemployment raises the number of terrorist incidents. Caruso and Schneider 2011; Goldstein 2005; and Cruz D'Alessio, and Stolzenberg 2020, All agreed on the same sort of relationship we discovered between unemployment and terrorism threats.

3.8.1.2 REM Post Estimation Tests

According to Pesaran (2004) CD test of dependency, the error terms of the estimated model are cross sectionally dependent, by accepting H_1 of dependency, due to the significance of CD statistic at 1% level. This means any innovation in variables rather than the four economic variables significantly affect terrorism in the seven countries. Also, the model suffers from heteroskedasticity issue, because Wald χ^2 statistic p-value is significant at 1% level. Testing for the issue of autocorrelation, the p-value of the F statistic is significant at 10% level. Therefore, we found autocorrelation for the estimated random effect model. These results are exhibited in Appendix 3.C as well.

Therefore, as per Balestra and Varadharajan-Krishnakumar (1987), we examine our new estimated model if it may have the dynamic pattern in Table 3.14.

Table 3.14 G2SLS Random-Effects IV Regression

TI	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Lag TI	0.913	0.027	34.37	0.000	0.861	0.965	***
GDPG	-0.013	0.009	-1.51	0.131	-0.031	0.004	
INF	0.007	0.007	1.09	0.276	-0.006	0.021	
G	0.009	0.011	0.89	0.372	-0.011	0.03	
UEM	-0.012	0.018	-0.65	0.518	-0.047	0.023	
Constant	0.453	0.431	1.05	0.293	-0.391	1.297	
Mean dependent var		6.618	SD dependent var			2.541	
Overall r-squared		0.895	Number of obs			147	
Chi-square		1206.799	Prob > chi2			0.000	
R-squared within		0.843	R-squared between			0.993	

Significant at: *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0

Source: Researcher analysis using Stata17.

Observing Table 3.14 we realized that lag TI is significant at 1% level, so, the model should take a dynamic structure. Now we can estimate mean group, pool mean group, and dynamic fixed effect models.

3.8.2 The ARDL Models

The ARDL models' outcomes in Table 3.15 illustrates the error correction models of; pool mean group, mean group, and dynamic fixed effect, concentrating on the economic determinants that may influence terrorism in the selected countries from 2000 to 2021. The results from all three approaches indicate long-run cointegration between the variables, as evidenced by their error correction terms showing negative signs and significance at the 1% level. The confirmation of long-run cointegration is consistent with the Granger approximation theorem proposed by Engle and Granger (1987). According to this theorem, if the model's cointegration test is significant, as shown in Table 3.10, then the error correction term will also be significant.

Table 3.15 Mean Group, Pool Mean Group, and Dynamic Fixed Effect Models of the Economic Determinants.

Variables	PMG			MG			DFE			Accept
	Coef.	Std. Err.	z. stat.	Coef.	Std. Err.	z. stat.	Coef.	Std. Err.	z. stat.	
Long run										
GDPG	-0.339	0.118	-2.880 ***	-0.385	0.146	-2.650 ***	-0.294	0.118	-2.480 **	
INF	0.131	0.069	1.880 *	-0.011	0.172	-0.060	0.052	0.063	0.820	
G	0.320	0.206	1.550	0.256	0.192	1.330	0.419	0.221	1.890 *	
UEM	-0.750	0.537	-1.400	-0.027	0.826	-0.030	-0.187	0.442	-0.420	
Short run										
¹ ECT (speed of adjustment)	-0.109 (9.17)	0.018	-6.230 ***	-0.206 (4.854)	0.079	-2.610 ***	-0.137 (7.299)	0.036	-3.78 ***	
D1. GDPG	0.039	0.026	1.490	0.048	0.020	2.430 **	0.022	0.009	2.370 **	
D1. INF	-0.046	0.030	-1.500	0.004	0.019	0.230	-0.004	0.008	-0.460	
D1. G	-0.101	0.038	-2.660 ***	-0.117	0.062	-1.870 *	-0.067	0.034	-1.990 **	
D1. UEM	0.264	0.226	1.170	0.155	0.478	0.330	0.072	0.124	0.580	
Constant	0.095	0.146	0.650	-0.941	2.093	-0.450	-0.907	1.120	-0.810	
² CD- test	CD=-0.17, p-value=0.861, corr.= -0.008			CD=-0.45, p-value=0.650, corr.= -0.021			CD=-0.31, p-value=0.758, corr.= -0.014			H0
³ Autocorrelation	F(1, 6) = 0.221 Prob. F = 0.655			F(1, 6) = 0.061 Prob. F = 0.8133			F(1, 6) = 0.047 Prob. F = 0.8361			H0
Hausman test	MG & PMG: Chi ² = 1.87, (P-value= 0.759) DFE & PMG : Chi ² = 0.684, (P-value = 0.953)									PMG
Obs per group	22			22			22			
Number of groups	7			7			7			
Number of obs.	154			154			154			

¹ECT speed of adjustment in years between the parentheses. ² (Pesaran, 2004, H0: cross-section independence CD ~ N (0,1)).

³(Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data, H0: no first-order autocorrelation).

Significant at: *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, *p<0.1. Source: Source: Researcher analysis using Stata17.

The test of Hausman Chi² or Hausman *h*-test was employed to select the most appropriate model among PMG, MG, or DFE, to assess efficiency and

consistency among them. The Hausman test between MG and PMG selected the PMG model, as the p-value of the Chi^2 statistic is insignificant, see Table 3.15, indicating that the PMG model is efficient under H_0 . Also, the Hausman test for choosing between DFE and PMG supported the PMG model, as the p-value is insignificant at the 5% level, further confirming H_0 of coefficients homogeneity.

In summary, the results of both Hausman tests suggest selecting the model that allows for heterogeneous short-run dynamics while maintaining common long-run coefficients. Consequently, the most suitable model is the PMG model.

3.8.2.1 Interpretation of the selected PMG model in Table 3.15

Pooled mean group (PMG) in Table 3.15 characterized by having similar long-run coefficients, while allowing the short-run coefficients and error variances to vary among groups. The long-run component of the PMG model reveals a significant inverse relationship between GDP growth rate (GDPG) and terrorism. Specifically, for every 1% increase in GDP growth rate, the terrorism index decreases by 0.339 points at a 1% level of significance, all else being equal. Similarly, there is a positive relationship between INF and TI. Caruso and Schneider (2011) also support this finding. According to our PMG model, a 1% rise in inflation rate leads to an increase of 0.131 points in terrorism at the 10% level of significance, all else being equal.

The short-run aspect of the estimated PMG model indicates a significant inverse relationship between (G) and terrorism. As the economic globalization index (G) increases by one point, the terrorism index (TI) decreases by 0.101 points at a 1% level of significance, all else being equal. Rajput, Khoso, Sial, Dakhan, and Syed (2021) also provide support for the existence of a negative relationship between economic globalization and terrorism.

In conclusion, the values and signs of the coefficient of inflation rate in the REM align with the results in the PMG model, as both show a positive and significant relationship. Therefore, we may infer that among the four economic regressors studied, GDP growth rate and inflation are causal factors for terrorism in the long run. Appendix 4.B displays the short-run estimates for each country as well as the long-run estimates for all seven countries pooled.

3.8.2.2 The Error Correction Terms in Table 3.15

The adjustment or error correction coefficient (ECT) results indicate that the PMG, MG, and DFE models all exhibit both short and long-run equilibrium. The long-run equilibrium is captured by the coefficient of the one-period lag residual, which displays a negative and significant relationship at 1% level. ECT value is -0.109, implying that the system corrects its previous period's disequilibrium at a rate of 10.9% per year to attain a state of equilibrium. In other words, the impact of INF, UEM, GDPG, and G results in terrorism consequences persisting for approximately $(1/0.109 = 9.17)$ years until equilibrium is achieved.

Structural break findings in Table 3.10 support the results of speed of adjustment through a structural break test, which occurred in year 2009 for the economic model. This is due to the vulnerability of the economic indicators to shocks, leading to substantial and abrupt changes in data trends. These countries are considered fragile and are greatly affected by imposed external and internal economic strategies and policies, which lead to significant shocks to the data. Consequently, these significant and dramatic variations take a considerable amount of time (9 years in this study) to return to their regular course.

3.8.2.3 Post Estimation tests for the PMG model in Table 3.15

Panel data estimation suggests that disturbances are cross-sectionally independent; however, given the cross-country impacts in the population, a

cross-sectional relationship may emerge. Such dependency may be caused by an identical geographic area, political or economic inducements (Gaibulloev et al. 2014), hence it is required to assess the presence of cross-sectional dependence.

Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data indicates that the null hypothesis (H0) of no autocorrelation in the idiosyncratic error terms is accepted. This is supported by the insignificant p-value of the F statistic. Additionally, the p-value of the CD statistic for the PMG error terms is also insignificant, which further confirms the acceptance of H0, indicating cross-section independence in the idiosyncratic error terms.

3.9 The Estimated Models with Assorted Variables

3.9.1 The Static Models

Table 3.16 presents the estimated POLS, Fixed Effect (FEM), and Random Effect (REM) models for the assorted regressors. The LR F test statistic with degrees of freedom (6, 141) is 15.00 and found to be significant at the 1% level. Consequently, we reject the null hypothesis (H0) that the individual specific effects (Ui's) are all zero or that all the constants are the same. This leads us to conclude that the POLS model is not suitable, and instead, we accept the alternative hypothesis (H1) that all the constants are not the same, making the Fixed Effect model appropriate.

Next, the Hausman test is utilized to choose between the FEM and REM models. The Chi² test statistic is calculated as 55.159 with a p-value of 0.000. As a result, we reject the H0, which suggests that the ideal model is random effects, and instead, we accept H1, which supports the fixed effects model as the preferred choice.

Table 3.16 The Estimated Static Models by Using Assorted Predictors

Variables	POLS			FEM			REM			Accept
	Coef.	Std. Err.	t. stat.	Coef.	Std. Err.	t. stat.	Coef.	Std. Err.	t. stat.	
GDPG	0.009	0.019	0.49	-0.008	.017	-0.49	0.01	0.02	0.48	
INF	-0.001	0.031	-0.06	0.001	0.014	0.11	-0.002	0.016	-0.12	
PS	-2.837	0.408	-6.95 ***	-2.288	0.243	-9.41 ***	-2.837	0.277	-10.24 ***	
EXI	-0.070	0.226	-0.31	-0.05	0.223	-0.22	-0.07	0.138	-0.51	
DP	-0.239	0.652	-0.37	0.657	0.343	1.91 *	-0.239	0.211	-1.14	
G	-0.003	0.063	-0.06	-0.088	0.039	-2.28 **	-0.004	0.025	-0.16	
Constant	3.452	4.154	0.83	-0.002	2.991	-0.00	3.452	1.829	1.89 *	
Model statistic	F (6, 147) = 21.57			F (6,141) = 23.830 ***			Chi ² = 129.434***			
Mean dependent variable	6.477			6.477			6.477			
Overall R ²	0.4682			0.364			0.468			
R ² within	-			0.503			0.432			
R ² between	-			0.168			0.652			
¹ CD- test	6.95 ***			5.27 ***			6.95 ***			H1
Sigma - u	-			1.589			0.000			
Sigma - e	-			1.538			1.538			
rho	-			0.516			0.000			
² Slope heterogeneity test	4.557 ***			-			-			H1
Model Preference test	B.P. LM.: Chi-bar ² (01) = 0.000 Prob Chi-bar ² = 1.000			LR: F (6, 141) = 15.00 *** Prob. F = 0.000			Hausman: Chi ² d.f(6)= 90.0120 *** P-value = 0.000			FE
Heteroskedasticity	³ B.P. Chi ² (1) = 0.09			Wald Chi ² (7)= 380.83***			WaldChi ² (7)=6615.48* **			H1
Autocorrelation	⁴ F (1,6) = 36.921 *** Prob F = 0.0009			⁵ Q(p)-stat= 14.12 ***			⁵ Q(p)-stat= 13.72 ***			H1
⁶ Group Correlation of residuals	-			B-P LM test: Chi ² (21) = 87.762 ***, Pr. = 0.000			-			
Number of obs.	154			154			154			

Variables	POLS	FEM	REM	Accept
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¹ (Pesaran, 2004, H0: cross-section independence $CD \sim N(0,1)$). ² (Pesaran, Yamagata, 2008. H0: slope coefficients are homogenous). ³ (Breusch–Pagan/Cook–Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity, H0: constant variance). ⁴ (Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data, H0: no first-order autocorrelation). ⁵ Bias-corrected Born and Breitung (2016) Q(p)-test on variables H0: No serial correlation up to order 2. Ha: Some serial correlation up to order 2. ⁶ (Breusch-Pagan LM test H0: Group Residuals independence). Significant at: *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Source: Researcher analysis using Stata17.

3.9.1.1 Interpretation of the selected FEM

The selected fixed effect model FEM in Table 3.16 shows that PS has an inverse relationship with TI, at 1% significance level. Such that, when political stability index rises by one point, terrorism index falls by 2.288 points, *ceteris paribus*. This inverse relation is supported by Tahir (2020) through a fixed effect model to support the fact that political instability is a key factor of terrorism.

Economic globalization G has an inverse relationship with TI at 5% level, therefore as G increases by one point, terrorism decrease by 0.088 points, *ceteris paribus*. DP have a positive relationship with TI at 10% significance level. So, when the index of demographic pressures increases by one point, terrorism index increases by 0.657 of a point, *ceteris paribus*.

Thus, we can infer that, comparing to other variables, political stability has a substantial impact on the occurrence of terrorist acts in all seven countries studied.

3.9.1.2 FEM Post Estimation Tests

The F statistic of the chosen FEM is significant at the 1% level, indicating that all of the independent variables adequately explain the variances in terrorism in the selected countries. Rho statistic represents the intra-countries correlation, where 51.6% of the variances is due to differences across panels. And the mean of dependent variable $TI = 6.47$ throughout the period of 22 years in the selected countries.

The CD test of the residuals, in Table 3.16, allows us to reject H0 of cross-section independence, and accept H1, which supports the CSD of the model's residuals. This means any innovation in variables rather than these six social and economic variables affect terrorism in the selected countries. Also, the model has the problem of heteroskedasticity, as the p-value of Wald Chi2 statistic is significant at 1% level. Examining for autocorrelation in the error terms, the p-value of the F statistic is significant at 10% level, therefore, we found autocorrelation problem for the selected fixed effect model. Finally, testing for group correlation of residuals shows that B-P LM Chi2 is significant at 1% level, which makes us to reject H0 of no group correlation of residuals, and accept H1. Since the statistical tests of CSD, Heteroskedasticity, and Autocorrelation are accepted there corresponding H1, see also Appendix 5.B, we can't decide that the selected FEM is efficient, therefore, we try to investigate whether the estimated model would take a dynamic pattern or not, by entering the lag of the dependent variable to our FEM as shown in the following Table 3.17.

Table 3.17 Fixed-Effects (Within) IV Regression

TI	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Lag TI	0.808	0.044	18.43	0.000	0.722	0.894	***
GDPG	-0.014	0.009	-1.53	0.126	-0.031	0.004	
INF	0.002	0.007	0.26	0.794	-0.012	0.016	
G	0.029	0.022	1.34	0.18	-0.014	0.072	
PS	-0.469	0.162	-2.88	0.004	-0.787	-0.15	***
EXI	0.09	0.117	0.77	0.441	-0.139	0.32	
DP	-0.189	0.184	-1.03	0.303	-0.55	0.171	
Constant	0.189	1.581	0.12	0.905	-2.91	3.289	
Mean dependent var		6.618		SD dependent var		2.541	
Overall r-squared		0.900		Number of obs		147	
Chi-square		10907.131		Prob > chi2		0.000	
R-squared within		0.858		R-squared between		0.977	
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1							
Source: Researcher analysis using Stata17.							

The t-statistic value for the added lag dependent variable in Table 3.17, is significant at 1% level, so we reach to a point that the new estimated model will have a dynamic pattern (Andersen and Hsiao 1980). We may now estimate mean group, pool mean group, and dynamic fixed effect models for our mix Economic, Political, and Demographic Regressors model.

3.9.2 The ARDL Models for the Assorted Indicators

Table 3.18 demonstrates mean group, pool mean group, and dynamic fixed effect models for a mix of economic, political, and demographic variables that might affect terrorism in the selected countries during 2000 – 2021. The three approaches approve long run cointegration between the variables through their error correction terms as having negative signs and significant at 1% level.

Table 3.18 Mean Group, Pool Mean Group, and Dynamic Fixed Effect Models for the Economic, Political, and Demographic Indicators

Variables	PMG			MG			DFE			Accept
	Coef.	Std. Err.	z. stat.	Coef.	Std. Err.	z. stat.	Coef.	Std. Err.	z. stat.	
Long run										
GDPG	-0.081	0.040	-2.040 **	-0.087	0.088	-0.990	-0.161	0.084	-1.930 *	
INF	0.052	0.025	2.040 **	-0.140	0.179	-0.790	-0.001	0.052	-0.030	
PS	-2.036	0.247	-8.26 ***	-1.707	3.780	-0.450	-1.923	0.846	-2.27 **	
EXI	-0.651	0.307	-2.120 **	1.727	1.797	0.960	0.350	0.772	0.450	
DP	0.755	0.464	1.630 *	1.057	1.813	0.580	-0.838	1.248	-0.670	
G	0.005	0.047	0.100	0.240	0.257	0.940	0.254	0.157	1.620 *	
Short run										
¹ ECT (Speed of adj years)	-0.256 (3.906)	0.087	-2.960 ***	-0.417 (2.398)	0.114	-3.67 ***	-0.186 (5.376)	0.048	-3.9 ***	
D1. GDPG	0.038	0.027	1.420	0.059	0.052	1.140	0.016	0.009	1.740*	
D1. INF	-0.042	0.035	-1.210	0.008	0.022	0.380	0.001	0.008	0.100	

Variables	PMG			MG			DFE			Accept
D1. PS	-0.196	0.420	-0.470	-0.684	0.80	-0.850	0.049	0.23	0.210	
D1. EXI	0.121	0.193	0.620	-0.639	0.332	-1.930 *	0.106	0.192	0.550	
D1. DP	0.181	0.376	0.480	0.016	0.338	0.050	0.009	0.232	0.040	
D1. G	-0.095	0.042	-2.250 **	-0.107	0.070	-1.530	-0.054	0.034	-1.570	
Constant	0.377	0.174	2.160 **	-1.598	5.676	-0.280	-0.313	1.750	-0.180	
² CD- test	CD=1.510, p-value=0.132, corr.=0.070			CD= 2.87, p-value= 0.004, corr.= 0.134			CD=2.33, p-value=0.020, corr.=0.108			H0
³ Autocorrelation	F (1, 6) = 1.712 Prob. F = 0.238			F (1, 6) = 5.095 Prob F = 0.0648			F (1,6) = 0.216 Prob. F = 0.6583			H0
Hausman test	MG & PMG: Chi ² = 5.36, (P-value= 0.498) DFE & PMG: Chi ² = 4.51, (P-value = 0.608)									PMG
Obs. per group	22			22			22			
No. groups	7			7			7			
No. of obs.	154			154			154			

¹ECT Speed of Adjustment in years between the parentheses. ²(Pesaran, 2004, H0: cross-section independence CD ~ N(0,1)). ³(Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data, H0: no first-order autocorrelation).

Source: Researcher analysis using Stata17.

Hausman Chi² test was employed between each two estimated ARDL models to select the most appropriate model, either PMG, MG, or DFE. Therefore, the findings showed that Hausman Chi² statistic to choose between MG and PMG models, selected the PMG model, due to the insignificance p-value of Chi² statistic, therefore, PMG model is efficient under H0. Also, the Hausman test for choosing between DFE and PMG supported the PMG model because the test's p-value is insignificant. Therefore, we cannot reject H0 of homogeneity.

The final result of both Hausman tests informs us to select the model that allows for heterogeneous short-run dynamics in the model with common long-run coefficients. Thus, the PMG model would be the chosen model, which is the most appropriate.

3.9.2.1 Interpretation of the Selected PMG model in Table 3.18

The long run part of the PMG model shows an inverse relationship between GDPG rate and TI. So, as GDPG rate increases by 1%, terrorism index decreases by 0.081 of a point at 5% significance level, *ceteris paribus*. While INF has a positive relationship with TI, therefore, if inflation rate rises by 1%, terrorism index increases by 0.052 of a point at 5% significance level, *ceteris paribus*.

Political stability index (PS) has a negative significant relationship with TI at 1% significance level in the long run. Therefore, with the increase of PS by one point, terrorism decreases by 2.036, *ceteris paribus*. Also, Meierrieks, and Gries (2013) support a significant relationship between terrorism and political instability. External interventions are concerned with external economic and political support, such as the deployment of an international peacekeeping team. The long run impact of EXI has an inverse significant relationship with TI, at 5% level. However, when External Interventions (EXI) rises by one point, TI falls by 0.651 points, *ceteris paribus*.

The index of demographic pressures DP evaluates pressures on the state resulting from the population or its surroundings. The indicator, for example, monitors population pressures linked to food availability, access to drinking water, and other life-sustaining resources, or health, such as illness prevalence and epidemics. The PMG model shows DP index has a positive relationship with TI. Accordingly, when demographic pressures increase by one point terrorism index increases by 0.755 of a point at 10% significant level, *ceteris paribus*.

Going through the short-term estimations of the assorted PMG model, we discover that economic globalization (G) has a significant negative impact on TI at the 5% level. As a result, for every one-point rise in (G) index, TI lowers by 0.095 points, *ceteris paribus*.

In summary, the PMG model supports the static FE model of assorted macro determinants, through the signs of PS, DP, GDPG, INF, and EXI coefficients, which is the most important factors that impacts terrorism in the selected countries of the study during 2000-2021 in the long run. Appendix 5.B shows the short-run estimates for each country, in addition to the long-run estimates for all seven countries pooled.

3.9.2.2 The Error Correction Terms in Table 3.18

The results of the error correction coefficient ECT reveal that all three AR models exhibit both short- and long-term equilibrium, which are negative and significant at the 1% level. The PMG ECT= -0.256 denotes that the system corrects its previous period disequilibrium at a rate of 25.6% each year in order to achieve equilibrium. Meaning that the impact of INF, G, DP, GDPG PS, and EXI make terrorism consequences to persist for $(1/0.256) = 3.9$ years.

The model has an error correction coefficient of 0.256, which is more than the economic model's error correction coefficient of 0.109. This shows that equilibrium might be reached in a shorter amount of time, approximately four years, in comparison to the economic model, which requires more than nine years.

3.9.2.3 Post Estimation tests for the selected PMG model in Table 3.18

Wooldridge test for autocorrelation accepts the H₀ of no autocorrelation in the idiosyncratic error terms, where the p-value of F statistic is insignificant. The CD test for cross-section independence in the model's error term found the p-value to be insignificant at 5% level, which accepts H₀ of cross-section independence in the idiosyncratic error terms.

3.10 Granger causality Test

Granger causality test is a statistical test used to determine if one time series may be used to predict another (Granger, 1969). Dumitrescu and Hurlin (2012) proposed statistical statistic to test for Granger causality in heterogeneous panels, which is useful with panels of large T and small N, and is also known by DH test. We applied this test by the Stata command “xtgcause” which introduced by Lopez and Weber (2017) as shown in table 3.19. The test was extended using Akaike information criterion (AIC) for optimal lag selection. lastly, to account for the empirical issue of cross-sectional dependency, p-values and critical values are computed using a bootstrap approach (Lopez and Weber 2017). Therefore, we assume:

H0: Xi does not Granger-cause TI,

H1: Xi does Granger-cause TI for at least one panel.

Table 3.19 The DH Test of The Determinants That Ganger Cause Terrorism

Variable Granger cause TI	W-bar	Z-bar	Z-bar Tilde	Optimal No. of lags (AIC)	Accept
INF	1.3446	0.6446	0.3314	1	H0
UEM	20.1015	12.6348**	3.3134**	5	H0
GDPG	9.4185	3.6968 ***	0.5044	5	H0
G	14.9423	8.3183***	1.9568**	5	H0
PS	3.6228	4.9068**	3.7694**	1	H1
EXI	10.3652	4.4888	0.7534	5	H0
DP	8.4594	2.8943***	0.2523	5	H0

P-values computed using 1000 bootstrap replications, significant at: *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, *p < 0.10,

Source: Researcher analysis using Stata17.

Z-Bar Tilde statistic in Lopez and Weber (2017) is utilized to assess Ganger causality by comparing the p-value with the critical value in a small

panel data set with cross-sectionally dependent series. Accordingly, the DH test in Table 3.19 reveals that UEM Granger causes terrorism, with $Z\text{-bar}$ and $Z\text{-bar Tilde}$ statistic being significant at 5% level. Therefore, H_0 is rejected, and conclude that unemployment Granger cause terrorism as (Malik and Zaman 2013; and A. Yaseen 2019) are agreeing upon. Economic Globalization Granger causes terrorism using $Z\text{-bar}$, and $Z\text{-bar Tilde}$ statistic being significant at the 1%, and 5% significance level, as Rajput, et.al. (2021) approved. Also, the factor of political stability Granger cause terrorism in the selected countries under study, with both of $Z\text{-bar}$, and $Z\text{-bar Tilde}$ statistic being significant at 5% level, as Tahir (2020) suggested. Knowing that each of GDPG and DP aren't cross sectional dependent, see Table 3.5, we can depend on the $Z\text{-bar}$ statistic, which is significant at 1% level. Therefore, we reject the H_0 of Granger causality test regarding each of; UEM, G, PS, GDPG, and DP which states that these variables do not predict terrorism, individually. Thus, we accept H_1 which states; the factors of unemployment, economic globalization, political stability, GDP growth, and demographic pressures, Granger cause terrorism in the selected countries of the study. Considering the remaining variables under study, we accept H_0 , which means they have no effect on terrorism index TI's predictions.

3.11 Summary of the Selected Econometrics Model - Chapter Three:

As is commonly known, panel data models are classified into two types; static and dynamic. After doing the appropriate measurement tests, which are computed and evaluated in depth in this chapter, it was determined that the dynamic model better captures the study data. The PMG model has been determined to be the most efficient of the dynamic models, as demonstrated by the summary results in Table 3.20.

Table 3.20 Summary of the Econometrics Results – Chapter Four

Economic Variables PMG Model (Dependent Variable TI)					
Effect on TI	Variable	Sign & Coefficient	Relationship	Size of Effect	Z-statistic
Long-run	GDPG	-0.339	Inverse	Small	-2.880 ***
	INF	+0.131	Positive	Small	1.880 *
	G	+0.320	Positive	Small	1.550
	UEM	-0.750	Inverse	Moderate	-1.400
Short-run	D(GDPG)	+0.039	Positive	Small	1.490
	D(INF)	-0.046	Inverse	Small	-1.500
	D(G)	-0.101	Inverse	Small	-2.660 ***
	D(UEM)	+0.264	Positive	Small	1.170
ECT	TI _{t-1}	-0.109	Inverse	Small	-6.230 ***
Assorted Variables PMG Model (Dependent Variable TI)					
Effect on TI	Variable	Sign & Coefficient	Relationship	Size of Effect	Z-statistic
Long-run	GDPG	-0.081	Inverse	Small	-2.040**
	INF	+0.052	Positive	Small	2.040
	PS	-2.036	Inverse	Big	-8.26***
	EXI	-0.651	Inverse	Moderate	-2.120**

	DP	+0.755	Positive	Moderate	1.630 *
	G	+0.005	Positive	Small	0.10
Short-run	D(GDPG)	+0.038	Positive	Small	1.420
	D(INF)	-0.042	Inverse	Small	-1.210
	D(PS)	-0.196	Inverse	Small	-0.470
	D(EXI)	+0.121	Positive	Small	0.620
	D(DP)	+0.181	Positive	Small	0.480
	D(G)	-0.095	Inverse	Small	-2.250
ECT	TI _{t-1}	-0.256	Inverse	Moderate	-2.920 ***

The Variables that Granger Cause Terrorism in the Selected Countries

Variable	CSD	Z-bar	Z-bar Tilde	H ₀ : X _i does not Granger-cause TI
UEM	Yes	12.6348**	3.3134**	Reject H ₀
GDPG	No	3.6968 ***	0.5044	Reject H ₀
G	Yes	8.3183***	1.9568**	Reject H ₀
PS	Yes	4.9068**	3.7694**	Reject H ₀
DP	No	2.8943***	0.2523	Reject H ₀

Significant at: *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, *p < 0.10.

Source: Researcher analysis using Stata17.

CHAPTER FOUR: ESTIMATING THE IMPACT OF ECONOMIC AND POLITICAL VARIABLES ON TERRORISM IN IRAQ

4.1 Preface

Terrorism in Iraq has been a serious and ongoing issue, with the country facing different types of terrorist attacks for decades. Iraq has faced complex and multidimensional threats from both internal and international terrorist groups, ranging from ethnic bloodshed after the US-led invasion in 2003 to the formation of the Islamic State (IS) in the mid-2010s. This chapter gives an overview of the impact of main economic, political, variables that contribute to terrorism in Iraq.

Terrorism in Iraq has direct and indirect effects, which are embodied in an index, called Terrorism Index (TI), as is mentioned in chapter two section (2.10.2). Iraq's terrorism index recorded extremely high scores starting from year 2004 to 2020. This index reached to 10 during years 2014 to 2017, which was the highest boundary point of (GTI). An ARDL model will be constructed to track the variables with the greatest significance impacting (TI) in Iraq during the years 2000 to 2020. In an effort to understand how shocks in the independent variables impact Iraq's TI, variance decomposition analysis and impulse response analysis will be performed in VAR system. Finally, to get insight into the trend and values of Iraq's TI in the medium and long term, a forecasting ARMA model will be developed.

4.2 Data Description

Table 4.1 displays the examined factors that could be contributing to terrorism in Iraq, with their acronyms, descriptions, measurements, and expected signs for the estimated parameters.

Table 4.1 Variables Acronym, Description, Measurements, and the Expected Sign

Acronym	Description	Measurement	The expected sign
TI (dependent variable)	Terrorism Index	Ranges from 0 to 10	+ for TI lags
INF	Inflation rate	% Rate	+
GDPG	Annual GDP growth	% Rate	-
GINI	Income inequality index	Ranges from 0 to 1	- or +
UEM	Unemployment	% Rate	- or +
PS	Political Stability index	Ranges from -2.5 (weak); to 2.5 (strong)	-

Source: Prepared by the researcher, 2022.

The direct costs were significantly high, represented as the number of deaths due to terrorism attacks. The highest number reported is 13965 deaths in year 2014, which is corresponding to the highest figure of terrorist incidents 3933, for the same year, as shown in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2 Number of Terrorist Attacks and Deaths in Iraq.

Years	No. of Attacks	No. of Deaths	TI
2000	10	10	3.7
2001	3	9	4
2002	6	10	4.09
2003	102	391	6.56
2004	323	2171	8.03
2005	617	3384	8.65
2006	838	4612	9.1
2007	1047	6665	9.45
2008	1106	2864	9.33
2009	1137	2585	9.33
2010	1179	2074	9.22
2011	1308	1870	9.11

Years	No. of Attacks	No. of Deaths	TI
2012	1437	2679	9.56
2013	2852	7042	9.01
2014	3933	14095	10
2015	2751	8885	10
2016	3360	12276	9.96
2017	2466	6619	10
2018	1956	1432	9.75
2019	1131	799	9.241
2020	495	525	8.682
Total	28057	80997	-

Source: GTD annual reports.

Table 4.2 shows terrorist attacks in Iraq increased significantly during 2004 to 2018, while the numbers decreased in both years 2019 and 2020 of the sample under study to reach to 1131, and 495 respectively. Correspondingly, number of deaths from terrorism decreased to 799, and 525 for the same last two years 2019, and 2020, as also illustrated in Figure 4.1.

Figure 4. 1 Terrorist Attacks and Deaths in Iraq during 2000-2020

Source: plotted by the researcher depending on Table 4.2

Terrorism costs in Iraq such as fatalities, injuries, and property damages that are measured by terrorism index is illustrated in Figure 4.2. The dotted line

shows the increasing trend of Iraq’s GTI during the years of 2000 to 2020. This index was 10, i.e., at its highest score during the years 2014 to 2017, indicating that Iraq suffered from severe terrorism consequences during these four years. Specifically, during the period of ISIS extensive threats on the country.

Figure 4. 2 Trend of Terrorism Index in Iraq During the Years 2000-2020

Source: plotted by the researcher depending on Table 4.2

Iraq terrorism index recorded more than 8 during the period years 2004 till 2020, particularly during the years 2014 to 2018, where it was at peak, rather close to 10. Therefore, the trend of TI is raising upward to the right.

4.2.1 Annual and Average Growth Rate of The Economic Indicators Related to Terrorism

Annual growth rates of the variables are calculated depending on the raw data from Appendix 2.1. The following formula calculates the percentage change from one period to the next:

$$PR = \frac{(V_{pr} - V_{pa})}{V_{pa}} \times 100 \quad \dots \dots \dots 4.1, \quad \text{Where};$$

PR = Percent Rate, V Pr = Present or Future Value , V Pa = Past or Present Value.

In Figure 4.2, we can observe a structural break (date) in the terrorism index curve in 2003. This also found throughout the structural break stationarity (Unit Root) test for TI in Table 4.7. Accordingly, we divide the status of average growth rate for each indicator of this study into two time periods; period (1); 2000-2002 and period (2); 2003-2020 as exhibited in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3 Annual and General Growth Rate for Terrorism Index and Some Economic Indicators in Iraq During 2000-2020.

Year	TI%	INF%	GINI%	UEM%	GDP%	PS%
2000	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
2001	8.11	228.00	1.75	0.92	1.76	-3.45
2002	2.25	17.68	1.72	0.51	-8.20	-4.17
2003	60.39	74.09	-40.68	-0.37	-36.66	48.45
2004	22.41	-19.64	17.14	-2.39	53.38	33.05
2005	7.72	37.04	2.44	1.14	1.67	-15.41
2006	5.20	43.78	-9.52	-0.62	5.65	5.20
2007	3.85	-118.98	-18.42	-0.02	1.89	-2.12
2008	-1.27	-225.74	0.00	-1.92	8.23	-10.83
2009	0.00	-45.67	3.23	-1.07	3.38	-11.74
2010	-1.18	-57.97	0.00	-1.69	6.40	2.75
2011	-1.19	100.00	-3.13	-1.56	7.55	-17.41
2012	4.94	5.17	-6.45	-1.99	13.94	4.32
2013	-5.75	-68.85	-6.90	16.38	7.63	4.15
2014	10.99	15.79	-7.41	14.31	0.20	23.38
2015	0.00	-36.36	-8.00	1.27	4.72	-8.87
2016	-0.40	-57.14	4.35	0.89	13.79	2.21
2017	0.40	-66.67	12.50	20.33	-1.82	0.00

Year	TI%	INF%	GINI%	UEM%	GDP%	PS%
2018	-2.50	100.00	7.41	-0.41	2.63	9.52
2019	-10.97	-150.00	6.90	-0.79	5.96	2.77
2020	0.02	-400.00	-3.23	9.52	-15.67	-2.69
Series' Average of Growth %						
Period (1) 2000-2002	5.14	96.47	1.74	0.71	-3.35	-3.81
Period (2) 2003-2020	1.57	-20.04	-0.85	2.64	5.96	0.32
Entire Time 2000-2020	4.36	-10.06	-3.16	2.42	2.62	1.89

Source: Calculated by the researchers using EViews13.

Annual growth rates are fluctuating for each indicator comparing to its previous year figure. Considering TI in year 2003 terrorism increased by 60.39%. Iraq's GDP dropped to 36.66% in the same year. In 2014 the year of ISIS attacks, TI raised by 11% comparing with year 2013, and unemployment increased by 14.31%, and inflation raised by 15.79%. And Political stability experienced anticable decrease 8.87% in 2015 comparing to year 2014.

Average rate of growth for each series is calculated using exponential growth rate model 4.2, for the two above-mentioned periods separately, and also for the entire time frame of the collected dataset, as the following:

$$Y = e^{a+bT} \quad , \quad \text{or} \quad \text{Log}Y = a+bT \quad \dots\dots\dots 4.2 \quad (\text{Panik, 2014, p.33}).$$

Where; Y represents the series of concern, a is the constant, b the rate of growth in unit time, T Refers to time variable i.e., years under study that starts from 2000 until and 2020.

Terrorism average rate of growth was increasing in period (1) and period (2), by 5.14% and 1.57%, respectively, and for the entire time frame by 4.36%. comparing the rise in TI in the two periods, we see that in period (1) was more. This caused a significant decrease in Iraq's GDP by 3.35%, and raised the

average rate of each of; inflation by 96.47%, unemployment rate by 0.71%, income inequality by 1.74%. While the average growth rate of political stability index was dropping by about 3.81% in period (1).

As for period (2) during 2003-2020, terrorism was growing with annual average rate of 1.57%, this increase was associated with annual growth in GDP by 5.96%, decrease in inflation by 20.04%, rise in unemployment by 2.64%, a minor reduction in income inequality by 0.85%, and a slight growth in political stability 0.32%.

The consequences of terrorism growth in Iraq for the entire period of the study 2000-2020 was 4.36%, associated with 2.62% increase in GDP growth, 10.06% decrease in inflation, 2.42% increase in unemployment, 3.16% reduction in the rate of income inequality, and 1.89% increase in the growth of political stability, which is a slight increase comparing to period (1), the era of Bath party authority in Iraq.

4.2.2 The Descriptive Statistics

Measurements of descriptive statistics are calculated for the data under study such as the mean, maximum and minimum values, standard deviation, and Jarque - Bera statistic for data normality test and its probability in Table 4.4. The average of terrorist attacks in Iraq is 1336, where the maximum number of the attacks reached 3933 in year 2014, and the minimum was 3 attacks in 2001. The mean of the deaths from terrorism was nearly 3857 people, with the maximum number of deaths is 14095 in year 2014, and minimum is 9 people in year 2001.

In view of the variables entered in the econometric models of this study; the mean score of terrorism index TI was 8.4, the maximum score was 10 reported during the years 2014 to 2017, and the minimum score was 3.7 in year 2000. The mean of unemployment rate is 9.77%, with maximum rate of 14% and minimum rate of 7.96%. We can observe that the data of unemployment is

distributed normally because p-value of Jarque-Bera test is 0.112 which is higher than 0.05 significance level. The mean score of Income inequality index (GINI) is 34.85. Meanwhile the average of GDP growth in Iraq is 4.44%. The price levels of goods and services are high in the period under study in Iraq, where the mean inflation rate is 10.61%. And the mean of political stability indicator is around -2.31, which refers that Iraq is quite unstable politically.

Table 4.4 The Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.	Jarque-Bera	Probability
No. of Attacks	1336.048	3933.00	3.00	1148.514	2.184353	0.335486
No. of Deaths	3857	14095	9.00	4025.813	5.5392	0.062686
TI	8.391048	10	3.7	2.023857	8.973795	0.011256
GDPG	4.444286	53.39	-36.66	15.98226	15.64722	0.0004
INF	10.61429	53.2	-10.1	15.42606	7.258686	0.026534
UEM	9.779381	14.088	7.96	1.904312	4.361406	0.112962
GINI	34.8571	59	23	10.8503	6.093245	0.047519
PS	-2.31381	-1.61	-3.18	0.406626	0.219087	0.896243

Source: calculated by the researcher using EViews13.

4.3 Model Specification

There are several determinants that might affect terrorism in Iraq. To show the impact of these determinants this study adopts the ARDL approach for time series data. The dependent variable represents terrorism index of Iraq (TI), while the independent variables are; unemployment rate (UEM), income inequality (GINI), inflation rate (INF), gross domestic product growth (GDPG), and political stability index (PS), see Table 4.1. Thus, we can write the Iraq's terrorism index relation as a function of some economic variables as key variables and one controlling variable which is represented by PS as;

$$TI = f(UEM, GDPG, GINI, INF, PS)$$

4.4 The ARDL Model Specification of Terrorism in Iraq

The ARDL model contains the endogenous variable which involves TI lags, and Xi exogenous variables in current and lagged values, including; INF, UEM, GDPG, GINI, and PS. The general model specification of ARDL (p, q) is as the following:

$$TI_t = \gamma_{0i} + \sum_{i=1}^p \delta_i TI_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^q B_i X_{t-i} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad \dots\dots\dots 4.3$$

Where; TI_t is the dependent variable, which represents a vector of the terrorism index, and X_t is a vector of economic variables (independent variables), that could be purely in order I (0), I (1), or a mix of both. δ and B are coefficients, γ is the constant, $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, k$, p is the optimal lag order for TI, and q is the optimal lag for X, and ε_{it} is the vector of the error term. Appendices 2.1 to 2.5 offer computational analyses of the time series findings related to the current chapter. The following steps deliver the construction procedures for ARDL model estimation:

4.4.1 Selecting an Appropriate Lag Length

Selecting the appropriate lag length is the first crucial step to perform the ARDL model building. The system of VAR in appendix 2.5 provides five criteria's that are used for lag length selection in, such as; Schwarz information criterion SIC, Akaike information criterion AIC, Hannan-Quinn information criterion HQC, Final prediction error FPE, and LR sequential modified LR. Implementing this test on the entered data series variables, one year lag length has been selected, see the asterisks in Table 4.5.

Table 4.5 Selecting the Lag Lengths

Endogenous variables: TI

Exogenous variables: C GDPG GINI UEM INF PS

Lag	Log L	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-15.25506	NA	0.560932	2.237374	2.535618	2.287849
1	-2.289830	16.37713*	0.161435*	0.977877*	1.325828*	1.036764*
2	-2.284693	0.005947	0.182786	1.082599	1.480258	1.149899

* Indicates lag order selected by the criterion.

Source: calculated by the researcher using EViews13.

4.4.2 Data Stationarity Test (Unit Root Test)

Unit root test shows the stationarity status for each data series. Therefore, before running an ARDL model for time series data, each variable data has to be stationary at its original level of integration I (0), or at its first difference of integration I (1), or mix of both of I (0) and I (1).

Augmented Dicky Fuller ADF, and Philips- Peron approaches are adopted to show the results of unit root test. Where the hypotheses of these tests are:

H₀: the series has a unit root (not stationary)

H₁: the series hasn't a unit root (stationary)

Table 4.6 shows the results of unit root test at the original level of the data i.e., I (0) level of integration, and at their first differences i.e., I (1) of integration. Some of the series are stationary at level, with intercept, and intercept and trend such as TI, GDPG, and GINI, at 10%, 1% alpha significance level. While, all of the economic determinant are stationary at their corresponding first difference i.e., I (1) level of integration, with intercept, or intercept and trend. Because the corresponding t-statistic's p-value of each series are significant at % 1, %5, and % 10 significance level. Therefore, we can reject the null hypothesis H₀, which says the series has a unit root, and accept

the alternative hypothesis H_1 , which states that the series hasn't a unit root i.e., stationary.

Summing up, the ARDL method could be applied to the data of this study because all data series are stationary at either I (0), or I (1), and mix of I (0) and I (1) of integration.

Table 4.6 ADF and PP Unit Root Test.

Variables		Level		First Difference	
		Intercept	Intercept and trend	Intercept	Intercept and trend
TI	ADF	-2.9516 0.0571*	-1.1867 0.8857	-2.9422 0.0591 *	-4.1410 0.0211 **
	PP	-2.8719 0.0665 *	-1.0809 0.9072	-2.9202 0.0616 *	-4.1393 0.0211 **
GDPG	ADF	-5.9626 0.0001 ***	-5.7920 0.0008 ***	-7.9476 0.0000 ***	-7.7077 0.0000 ***
	PP	-7.2954 0.0000 ***	-7.0290 0.0001 ***	-17.2085 0.0000 ***	-18.5216 0.0001 ***
INF	ADF	-2.6447 0.1010	-4.0708 0.0230 **	-4.4769 0.0028 ***	-4.3315 0.0156 **
	PP	-2.5717 0.1150	-4.0729 0.0229 **	-8.5218 0.0000 ***	-8.1631 0.0000 ***
UEM	ADF	0.9978 0.9947	-0.7389 0.9551	-1.2226 0.6390	-2.6493 0.2669
	PP	1.1472 0.9964	0.5206 0.9985	-3.6238 0.0153 **	-7.4587 0.0000 ***
GINI	ADF	-5.5623 0.0003 ***	-1.9516 0.5890	-2.6729 0.1014	-3.9741 0.0352 **
	PP	-3.2826 0.0298 **	-1.5298 0.7839	-5.3665 0.0004 ***	-14.1354 0.0001 ***
PS	ADF	-2.2094 0.2091	-2.9783 0.1672	-4.0514 0.0063 ***	-3.9970 0.0276 **
	PP	-2.2620 0.1927	-2.1570 0.4858	-4.0425 0.0064 ***	-3.9856 0.0282 **

* Significant at %10 level. ** significant at %5 level. *** significant at %1 level.

Source: prepared by the researcher using EViews13.

The ADF and PP unit root tests have a well-known defect in that they might misinterpret breaks in the series as evidence of non-stationarity. In other words, if the series has a structural break as shown through the panels of Figure 4.3, where the series are having structural break points in different years and

they might fail to reject the unit root hypothesis (Perron 1989; Perron 1997, 358). Therefore, unit root structural break needed to be tested, see Table 4.7.

Figure 4.3 Trends of The Studied variables During 2000 -2020

Source: plotted by the researcher using EViews13.

Table 4.7 shows unit root structural break test for the studied variables. In which, we can note that all variables are stationary at $I(0)$, and/or $I(1)$.

Table 4.7 Unit Root Structural Break Test

Variables	Level		First difference	
	Intercept	Intercept and trend	Intercept	Intercept and trend
TI	-4.6828 ** (2003)	-3.0390 (2003)	-4.5222 ** (2006)	-5.1920 ** (2013)
GDPG	-8.9711 *** (2003)	-10.9937 *** (2003)	-16.0787 *** (2004)	-15.7963 *** (2008)
INF	-16.9607 *** (2006)	-16.4766 *** (2006)	-14.8690 *** (2007)	-32.2897 *** (2007)
UEM	-5.0374 *** (2019)	-4.1176 (2019)	-8.5860 *** (2013)	-9.7576 *** (2013)
GINI	-5.2752 *** (2019)	-5.6674 *** (2016)	-5.9468 *** (2005)	-6.2728 *** (2005)
PS	-4.5536 ** (2019)	-3.5841 (2018)	-5.9942 *** (2004)	-6.4812 *** (2004)

Source: calculated by the researcher using EViews13.

Table 4.7 shows that all variables are stationary at I(0) with intercept while only three of them are stationary with intercept and trend. Considering stationarity at I(1) the results show that all variables are stationary with intercept and intercept and trend.

4.5 The ARDL Model of Terrorism in Iraq

After checking for data stationarity at I (0) or I (1), and existence of long run cointegration equation among the data series, now the ARDL model estimation could be performed, the empirical results are demonstrated in the following Table 4.8.

Table 4.8 The Estimated ARDL Model of Terrorism in Iraq

Dependent Variable: TI				
Selected Model: ARDL (1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0)				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
TI (-1)	0.180697	0.129800	1.392110	0.1914
GDPG	-0.024724	0.011143	-2.218717	0.0485
INF	0.014657	0.006473	2.264286	0.0448
INF (-1)	0.015327	0.007610	2.014131	0.0691
UEM	-0.183912	0.067927	-2.707496	0.0204
GINI	-0.043148	2.143589	-2.012920	0.0693
GINI (-1)	-0.122057	4.382969	-2.784809	0.0178
PS	-0.587544	0.322169	-1.823715	0.0955
C	13.04882	2.529024	5.159627	0.0003

R-Squared	0.986293	Mean Dependent Var	8.625600
Adjusted R-Squared	0.976324	S.D. Dependent Var	1.759392
S.E. of Regression	0.270718	Akaike Info Criterion	0.526687
Sum Squared Res.	0.806172	Schwarz Criterion	0.974766
Log Likelihood	3.733132	Hannan-Quinn Crite.	0.614157
F-Statistic	98.93715	Durbin-Watson Stat	2.528723
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

Source: Calculated by the researcher using EViews13.

Hence, we can introduce the general ARDL equation as the following:

$$TI = 13.0488 + 0.180 TI_{t-1} - 0.0247GDPG + 0.0146INF + 0.0153 INF_{t-1} - 0.1839UEM - 0.0431GINI - 0.1220GINI_{t-1} - 0.5875PS \dots\dots\dots 4.4$$

The best ARDL(p, q₁, q₂, q₃, q₄, q₅) model is ARDL(1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0), which demonstrated in Figure 4.4.

Figure 4.4 The Best Estimated ARDL Model for Terrorism in Iraq

Source: plotted by the researcher using EViews13.

4.6 Long Run and Short Run Impacts

4.6.1 Long Run Cointegration (F-Bounds) Test

The F- Bound's test of Pesaran et. al. (2001) is adopted to examine the presence of long-run relationship among the data series of the estimated ARDL model (4.4), see Table 4.9.

we can specify the hypotheses as follows:

H_0 : There is no long run cointegration among the data series.

H_1 : There is long run cointegration among the data series.

Table 4.9 F- Bound's Test

F-Bounds Test		Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship		
Test Statistic	Value	Sig.	I (0)	I (1)
F-statistic	12.12529	10%	2.080	3
k	5	5%	2.390	3.380
Actual Sample Size	20	1%	3.060	4.150

Source: calculated by the researcher using EViews13.

Since the F-Bounds statistic is 12.12529, which is more than the upper bounds I (1), are; 4.150, 3.380, and 3 at each of 1%, 5%, and 10% significance levels, respectively. Thus, we can reject the null hypothesis H_0 , which says there is no cointegration among the data series in the long run. Rather we accept the alternative hypothesis H_1 which suggests the existence of long run relationship among the series. Accordingly, we can estimate the long run model estimates, as is illustrated in Table 4.10.

Table 4.10 The Estimated Long Run Model of Terrorism in Iraq.

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
GDPG	-0.030177	0.011115	-2.714981	0.0201
INF	0.036596	0.013014	2.812083	0.0169
UEM	-0.224474	0.073655	-3.047662	0.0111
GINI	-0.201642	0.014207	-14.19273	0.0000
PS	-0.717126	0.402838	-1.780184	0.1026

Source: calculated by the researcher using EViews13.

From Table 4.10, notice that the estimated coefficients GDPG, INF, and UEM, all are significant at 5% level, while GINI is significant at 1% level. As for PS is significant at 11% level. Inflation rate is taking a positive sign, meaning that it has a significant direct impact on terrorism in Iraq in the long run. This positive relationship agrees with that of; Piazza (2006), (Shahbaz 2013), (Malik and Zaman 2013), (Gulzar and Zhaohua 2016), (Tahir 2018), and (Ajide and Alimi 2021). Thus, as INF increase by one percent, TI increases by 0.036 points, *ceteris paribus*.

GDP growth showed an inverse relationship with terrorism (Blomberg Hess and Weerapana 2002; Crain and Crain 2006; Gaibulloev and Sandler 2011; Shahbaz 2013; Chinar 2017; and Zakaria Jun and Ahmed 2019). So, as GDPG increases by 1% terrorism reduces by 0.03 points, *ceteris paribus*.

The GINI coefficient also showed a negative relationship with terrorism in Iraq. The indirect association between income inequality and terrorism does not appear to be consistent with economic theory, however certain studies, such as Goldstein (2005), Abadi (2006), and Azam and Thelen (2008), support the inverse relationship. The empirical results showed as GINI rises by 1% in Iraq, terrorism falls by 0.21 points, all other factors remain constant. Furthermore, Piazza (2013) discovered a negative association between the Gini coefficient and terrorism in semi-autocratic countries with low levels of human development. The plausible explanation for this form of relationship is due to limited resources and scarcity, as well as the type of controlling power in the country as militias and mercenary forces are having a substantial role. As income inequality gap is wide in autocratic countries, and the authority system prohibits political freedom practices and bans a number of civilian activities, therefore, the consequences of terrorism may jeopardize their ability to maintain power and rule.

Unemployment impacts terrorism adversely, due to the potential direct relationship between income inequality, explained in the previous paragraph, and unemployment. Therefore, as 1% increase in UEM terrorism decreases by 0.22 points, *ceteris paribus*. One justification for this inverse relationship is as during terrorism actions, common people are feeling insecure, they prefer to stay at home rather than being targeted, and they decide to consume less (Yaseen 2019).

Also, the factor of political stability PS has a negative sign, meaning that it affects TI in an adverse manner. Therefore, in the long run as PS increases by one unit, terrorism reduces by 0.71 points, *ceteris paribus*. Thus, it is worth noting that PS coefficient has a relatively high impact on TI in Iraq.

4.6.2 The Short Run Impact

The impacts of the economic regressors in short run are illustrated in the ARDL Error Correction Regression table 4.11 below.

Table 4.11 The Short Run Impact Model

ECM Regression				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	13.04882	2.529024	5.159627	0.0003
D(INF)	0.014657	0.003215	4.558866	0.0006
D(GINI)	-0.043148	0.008775	-4.735624	0.0005
Coint, Eq (-1)*	-0.819303	0.076346	-10.73139	0.0000
R-Squared	0.923677	Mean Dependent Var		0.249100
Adjusted R-Squared	0.914697	S.D. Dependent Var		0.745604
S.E. of Regression	0.217766	Akaike Info Criterion		-0.073313
Sum Squared Res.	0.806172	Schwarz Criterion		0.076047
Log Likelihood	3.733132	Hannan-Quinn Criteria		-0.044157
F-Statistic	102.8683	Durbin-Watson Stat		2.528723
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: calculated by the researcher using EViews13.

Through the estimated ARDL Error Correction Model in Table 4.11, we can observe the direct relationship between Inflation rate, and terrorism, in the short run, and the indirect relationship between D(GINI) coefficient and TI. We

can notice that Inflation rate affects terrorism in Iraq in the short run at 1% significant level, because the corresponding t statistic is $4.5 > 2$. Therefore, if $D(INF)$ increases by one percent, $D(TI)$ will rise by 0.014 points, ceteris paribus. While if $D(GINI)$ increases by one unit, TI will decrease by 0.043 points, ceteris paribus.

In view of the error correction coefficient or the speed of adjustment - 0.819, the empirical results show that it is negative in the sign, and significant at %1 level. This indicates that 81.9% of any activities into disequilibrium are corrected for, within one period, which is one year in this study. In another word, the rate of speed of adjustment from previous year's disequilibrium in TI is added to current year's equilibrium by 81.9%. The optimum time (speed) for this adjustment takes about $(1/0.819) = 1.22$ years, i.e., one year and two months.

4.7 Diagnostic Tests for Goodness of Model Specification

4.7.1 The Reliability Tests

The reliability assessments of autocorrelation, heteroskedasticity, Ramsey RESET, residual normality for the estimated ARDL model of terrorism in Iraq, are illustrated in the following Table 4.12, which support our estimations and goodness of model specification.

Table 4.12 Reliability Check for the Estimated ARDL Model

Inspections	Test *	The Hypotheses	F Statistic	P Value	Accept
Autocorrelation	Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM test	H ₀ : there is no autocorrelation between the residuals H ₁ : there is autocorrelation between the residuals.	2.356982	0.1503 F (2,9)	H ₀
Heteroscedasticity	Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test	H ₀ : residuals are not heteroscedastic. H ₁ : residuals are heteroscedastic.	0.887372	0.5562 F (8,11)	H ₀
	ARCH	H ₀ : residuals are not heteroscedastic. H ₁ : residuals are heteroscedastic.	3.081206	0.0972 F(1,17)	H ₀
Correct specification of the model	Ramsey Reset test	H ₀ : the model is specified correctly H ₁ : the model is mis-specified.	0.000598	0.9810 d.f(1,10)	H ₀
Residuals Normality Distribution	Jarque-Bera	H ₀ : the residuals are distributed normally. H ₁ : the residuals are not distributed normally.	Jarque-Bera Statistic= 0.119984	0.9417	H ₀

Calculated by the researcher using EViews13. *(Gujarati & Porter, 2009; Gujarati, 2011)

The results in Table 4.12 permits the researcher to accept H₀ for each test. Therefore, the model doesn't suffer from autocorrelation, and heteroskedasticity issues. We can say its correctly specified as RAMSEY F-statistic p-value = 0.9810 which is more than 0.05. And the residuals are normally distributed for Jarque-Bera Statistic p-value = 0.9417 is more than 0.05. Thus, we can approve that the estimated ARDL model 4.4 is well specified, and reliable for doing future forecasts.

4.7.2 CUSUM and CUSUM Square Tests

CUSUM cumulative sum of recursive residuals, and CUSUM of Squares, are two graphical tests used to reveal the stability of coefficients β s of any estimated time series multiple linear regression model; $y = \beta X_i + \varepsilon$, via detecting the structural breaks in the estimated regression by computing iterative sequence of sums of recursive residuals (Wu 2005).

We apply this test to detect a nonzero mean of the recursive residuals due to changes in the model coefficients. But, if there is more than a coefficient change, the CUSUM test may lose its power. Therefore, the CUSUM Squares plot is adopted. Reminding, that various changes may compensate their influences by the means of the recursive residuals. If the curve crosses the dotted lines, which represents 5% significance error, a structural instability is identified. The value of intercept C depends on the preferred significance level, the sample size T, and the number of independent variables (Lutkepohl and Kartzig 2004). As for the terrorism model of Iraq equation 4.4, the CUSUM and CUSUM of Squares test plotted in Figures 4.5 and 4.6 respectively.

Figure 4. 5 CUSUM Test of the Estimated Model of Terrorism in Iraq.

Source: Plotted by the researcher using EViews13.

Figure 4.4 exhibits the CUSUM test, where the curved line of the estimated model lies between the bounds of the two dotted lines at %5 significant level. This indicates that the coefficients of the estimated model are stable.

Concerning the CUSUM Squares test, which is illustrated in figure 4.6 shows that the estimated model lies between the bounds of the two dotted lines at %5 significant level. Thus, we can conclude that the model is fitted well, and the estimated coefficients are having the stability characteristic.

Figure 4. 6 CUSUM Test of the Estimated Model of Terrorism in Iraq.

Source: Plotted by the researcher using EViews13.

4.8 Variance Decomposition (VD) Analysis in VAR System

In the auto regression the amount of information each variable contributes to the other variables is examined by variance decomposition (VD) which will be estimated in the VAR system equations see appendix 2.5. Variance decomposition approach shows how much of the forecast error variance of each variable could be explained, by exogenous shocks, to the other variables (Lutkepohl 2005). (VD) determines the extent of the variability in the

dependent variable that explained by the independent variables, that is the strength of independent variables to explain the volatility in the dependent variable over time. In order to know the rate of the variances that each independent variable such as INF, GINI, UEM, GDPG, and PS makes to the dependent variable TI, we applied VAR analysis, then the variance decomposition developed by adopting the Cholesky method as is shown in Table 4.13.

Table 4.13 Variance Decomposition of TI

Cholesky Ordering: TI INF GINI UEM GDPG PS

Period	S.E.	TI	INF	GINI	UEM	GDPG	PS
1	0.63	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
		0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
2	0.98	96.54	1.25	2.09	0.06	0.06	0.00
		6.62	5.69	4.58	0.83	0.97	0.52
3	1.11	96.61	1.33	1.65	0.19	0.21	0.00
		10.03	8.45	5.64	2.17	1.37	1.39
4	1.17	95.81	1.69	1.58	0.68	0.21	0.02
		12.15	9.40	6.04	4.70	1.35	2.25
5	1.22	94.88	1.93	1.51	1.34	0.20	0.15
		15.00	10.85	6.87	7.37	1.35	2.98
6	1.25	93.69	2.18	1.60	2.00	0.19	0.34
		17.35	12.01	7.90	9.69	1.34	3.54
7	1.27	92.14	2.50	1.88	2.69	0.19	0.61
		18.93	12.92	8.46	11.39	1.48	4.00
8	1.29	90.50	2.83	2.18	3.33	0.19	0.97
		20.09	13.48	8.98	12.63	1.63	4.47
9	1.30	88.90	3.16	2.50	3.86	0.19	1.39
		20.78	13.85	9.39	13.53	1.61	4.96
10	1.31	87.41	3.48	2.83	4.24	0.20	1.83
		21.44	14.32	9.66	14.20	1.65	5.43

Cholesky One S.D. (d.f. adjusted) Innovations.
Cholesky ordering: TI INF GINI UEMP GDPG PS.
Standard errors: Monte Carlo (100 repetitions) standard deviations are shaded in blue.
Calculated by the researcher using EViews13.

In table 4.13 we observe that TI explains 100%, 96.54%, and 96.61% of the variances in TI after the first, second, and the third period (year) respectively. Then the variances in TI are declining gradually during the 10-year periods until it reaches to 88.90% and 87.41 % in year 9th, and 10th, respectively. Each of the exogenous variables; INF, GINI, UEM, GDPG, and PS are not having any contemporaneous effect on TI, i.e., in the first period. This validates the accuracy of estimating a dynamic model such as ARDL, as previously done. While GINI coefficient explains 2.09% of the variances in TI in the second year, then it starts rising to 2.83 % in year 10th. While UEM has a small influence 0.06% in the second period, i.e., the short run, but the variations get larger in the long run, 4.24% in period 10. Therefore, we can say that Unemployment rate is having the heaviest weight for explaining the variances in TI comparing to the remaining independent variables, in the long run. Next comes inflation rate, which explains 1.25 % in the second year and keep increasing till reaches 3.48% in the last year. Thus, all independent variables have trivial long run impact on TI, where UEM explains most of the variances in TI, comparing to the remaining exogenous variables, next comes inflation rate.

4.9 The Impulse Response Analysis IRA in VAR system

Impulse responses are Tabulated and graphical system that traces the impact of structural shocks or innovations on the endogenous variable (Lutkepohl 2005; Stock and Watson 2001). Table 4.14 shows the reaction of (TI), when each variable gets one standard deviation shock or innovation during the period of 10 years, as also illustrated in the panels of Figure 4.7.

Table 4.14 Cholesky Impulse Response of TI

Period	TI	INF	GINI	UEM	GDPG	PS
1	0.63	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
2	0.73	0.11	-0.14	-0.02	-0.02	0.00
	0.18	0.17	0.12	0.07	0.06	0.07
3	0.51	0.07	-0.02	-0.04	-0.04	0.00
	0.20	0.18	0.17	0.14	0.06	0.11
4	0.36	0.08	0.04	-0.08	-0.02	-0.02
	0.19	0.15	0.12	0.18	0.04	0.11
5	0.30	0.07	0.03	-0.10	-0.01	-0.04
	0.17	0.14	0.12	0.22	0.04	0.11
6	0.23	0.07	0.05	-0.11	-0.01	-0.06
	0.15	0.13	0.14	0.25	0.04	0.11
7	0.16	0.08	0.07	-0.11	0.00	-0.07
	0.14	0.13	0.16	0.27	0.04	0.11
8	0.11	0.08	0.08	-0.11	0.01	-0.08
	0.13	0.12	0.17	0.28	0.04	0.12
9	0.07	0.08	0.08	-0.10	0.01	-0.09
	0.12	0.12	0.18	0.29	0.04	0.13
10	0.03	0.08	0.08	-0.09	0.02	-0.09
	0.12	0.12	0.19	0.28	0.04	0.15
Cholesky One S.D. (d.f. adjusted) Innovations. Cholesky ordering: TI INF GINI UEM GDPG PS Standard errors: Analytic standard deviations are shaded in blue. Calculated by the researcher using EViews13.						

Interpreting the impulse response functions offers important information about the dynamic interactions between the system's variables and how shocks spread across them over time. This information may be used for forecasting, policy analysis, and understanding the underlying mechanisms that influence the behavior of the variables in the VAR model As demonstrated in Panels A to F in Figure 4.7.

**Response to Cholesky One S.D. (d.f. adjusted) Innovations
95% CI using analytic asymptotic S.E.s**

Figure 4.7 Impulse Responses of Iraq's TI to Innovations in the Exogenous Variables

Source: Plotted by the researcher using EViews13.

Observing the panels (A) to (F) in Figure 4.7, the X-axis represents the periods (10 years), and the Y-axis is the percentage variations. We can see that one standard deviation innovation of each of exogenous variables are affecting the endogenous variable TI significantly at 5% significant level. Since the blue curves are located between the orange dashed boundaries area of standard error

confidence bands, therefore, if one standard deviation shock or innovation is given to:

- i. TI, it will increase by 0.63 points in the first period then TI keep rising to reach 0.73% in period 2, then it starts to decline to 0.53 in period 3. And the rate of the variations would be almost zero or steady starting from periods 9 and 10, i.e., in the long run, to 0.07, and 0.03, respectively, as shown in Panel (A) Figure 4.7.
- ii. Inflation rate, it will make TI incline slowly and positively 0.11 points in period 2 and onwards. After that it starts to decline till periods 7 and onwards, where TI will be almost steady, i.e., in the long run, see panel (B).
- iii. GINI coefficient, forces TI to decline starting from period 1 till period 2 with a negative sign. Afterwards it will climb to become positive and almost steady from period 8.
- iv. Unemployment rate, which makes TI to decline by 0.04 points in period 3, then it starts to incline in period 5 and onwards with small fluctuations and will be almost steady starting from period 7, i.e., in the long run.
- v. GDP growth, that doesn't cause variations in TI in period 1, then it starts to decline by 0.02 points in period 2. The variations in shocks in GDPG keep fluctuate till period 7 where they start incline, but in rather small rates, and be in a steady state till period 10, in the long run.
- vi. Political stability, forces TI to decline in period 2 by 0.02 points. Afterward it fluctuates slowly with minus sign till period 5, where it'll almost be steady till the last period, as illustrated in panel (F) Figure 4.7. Generally, shocks in PS have negative impacts on TI almost all in all 10 periods ahead.

4.10 Forecasting Terrorism in Iraq

Forecasting is the process of estimating an outcome with a high degree of accuracy, typically using historical data and statistical modeling. In this context, the ARDL model used to perform in-sample forecasting, while the ARMA model used to make out-of-sample forecasting for terrorism index TI in Iraq.

4.10.1 In-Sample Forecasting Using ARDL Model

The estimated ARDL model 4.4, for Iraq time series data 2000-2020 is adopted to make in-sample forecasting for terrorism index TI is shown in Figure 4.8.

Figure 4.8 Forecasted and Actual TI in Iraq Using ARDL Model

Source: Plotted by the researcher using EViews13.

The blue curve in Figure 4.8 represents the forecasted TI in Iraq during 2000 to 2020, which is close to the actual values of TI and locates within the 2 upper and lower standard error boundaries green dotted lines. The reliability tests of Root Mean Squared error and Mean Absolute Error are relatively low, 0.19 and 0.14 respectively. Theil Inequality Coefficient is also quite low 0.01, means that the forecasting results by adopting ARDL is quite accurate. Also, since the value of Theil U2 is $0.13 < 1$, we can say that

the forecasting with ARDL has more accuracy than the naive forecasting method, which sets all future projections on historical data, with no changes made to adjust for periodic or seasonal fluctuations (Indeed Editorial Team 2023). This strategy allows one to exclude elements that have an effect on real future data, commonly known as causative factors.

4.10.2 The ARMA Model

The ARMA model, also known as an autoregressive moving average model, is a forecasting model that forecasts future values based on previous values. The simplicity of ARMA models is a significant advantage. They just require a minimal dataset to generate a prediction, and they are very accurate for short predictions, and operate with data that does not have a known trend.

The ARMA model was initially presented in Peter Whittle's 1951 thesis, which merged mathematical analysis of Laurent series and Fourier analysis, as well as statistical inference. A 1970 book by George E. P. Box and Jenkins popularized ARMA models by explaining an iterative Box-Jenkins approach for selecting and estimating them. This technique worked well for polynomials of degree no more than three (Hannan and Deistler 1988, p. 227).

The ARMA model is just a white noise infinite impulse response filter with some additional interpretation attached to it. The notation ARMA (p,d,q) refers to a model containing p autoregressive terms, d the dependent variable's integration level, and q moving-average terms (Shumway and Stoffer 2000). Because d is integrated at level I(0), d=0 and our ARMA model is expressed as ARMA(p,q).

In this study the autoregressive model for Iraq terrorism index of order p would be as:

$$TI_t = \sum_{i=1}^p \phi_i TI_{t-i} + \epsilon_t \quad \dots\dots\dots 4.5$$

Where;

TI_t represents terrorism index in year t, TI_{t-i} is ith year lag of terrorism index, and ε_t is the error term.

The moving average MA(q) model, which is a linear combination of error terms occurring contemporaneously and at various times in the past, is:

$$TI_t = \mu + \epsilon_t + \sum_{i=1}^q \theta_i \epsilon_{t-i} \dots\dots\dots 4.6$$

Where;

θ₁, ..., θ_q are the parameters of the model, μ is the expectation of TI (often assumed to equal 0), and the ε_t, ..., ε_{t-i}, are i.i.d white noise error terms that are commonly normal random variables.

Thus, the ARMA model for terrorism in Iraq would be developed through combining both models 4.3 and 4.4, which yields:

$$TI_t = C + \sum_{i=1}^p \varphi_i TI_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \theta_i \epsilon_{t-i} \dots\dots\dots 4.7$$

, it is quite likely that TI has characteristics of both AR and MA and is therefore ARMA(p,q). Thus, TI_t follows an ARMA(1, 1) process if it can be written as:

$$TI_t = C + \varphi_1 TI_{t-1} + \theta_0 \epsilon_t + \theta_1 \epsilon_{t-1} \dots\dots\dots 4.8$$

So, there is one autoregressive term, and one moving average term (Gujarati 2004, 839). Where, C represents a constant term.

In general, in an ARMA(p, q) modeling, there will be p autoregressive and q moving average terms (Hallin, and Puri, 1988).

4.10.2.1 Selecting the Appropriate ARMA (p, q) Model:

Here we deal with two essential concepts autocorrelation and partial autocorrelation, they are measurements of relationship between current and previous series values that reveal which previous series values are most beneficial in forecasting future values. This information is used to identify the order of processes in an ARMA model. To be more specific, ACF stands for autocorrelation function. This is the correlation between series values that are k gaps apart at lag k. while PAF stands for partial autocorrelation function. This

is the correlation between series values that are k intervals apart at lag k , taking into consideration the values of the intervals between (IBM Documentation, n.d.).

Through plotting TI partial autocorrelation for an estimate of p , and also using the autocorrelation functions for an estimate of q , we can decide that ARMA(1,1) is a suitable model for the forecasting process, as shown in the following correlogram Table 4.15. Here we can observe that partial correlation $p = 1$, and Autocorrelation $q = 1$ because p and q values are spiked out of the dashed range of significance. Therefore, ARMA(1,1) is the appropriate rank for TI forecasting process. We also could, and in fact applied ARMA(1,2), but the results and post estimation tests were unreliable, therefore we settled on ARMA(1,1) model. Eventually this technique is somewhat dependent on the analyst's subjective assessment (Gooijer, Abraham, Gould, and Robinson, 1985, p. 301).

Table 4.15 TI Series Correlogram

Sample (adjusted): 2000 2020
 Included observations: 21 after adjustments

	Autocorrelation	Partial Correlation	AC	PAC	Q-Stat	Prob
1			0.79...	0.79...	15.19...	9.71...
2			0.54...	-0.2...	22.80...	1.11...
3			0.25...	-0.2...	24.59...	1.87...
4			0.08...	0.13...	24.79...	5.53...
5			-0.0...	0.03...	24.79...	0.00...
6			-0.0...	-0.1...	24.90...	0.00...
7			-0.0...	-0.0...	25.12...	0.00...
8			-0.0...	0.06...	25.33...	0.00...
9			-0.0...	-0.0...	25.63...	0.00...
10			-0.1...	-0.0...	26.14...	0.00...
11			-0.1...	-0.0...	27.03...	0.00...
12			-0.2...	-0.1...	29.26...	0.00...

Source: found by the researcher using EViews13.

Finding appropriate values of p and q in the ARMA(p,q) model can be simplified by:

1. Finding the model that residuals are white noise, through (Ljung-Box Q statistic) H_0 : residuals are white noise. Which means the variables

are independently and identically distributed (i.i.d) with a mean of zero. This implies that all variables have the similar variance (σ^2) and each has a zero correlation with all other values in the series.

2. The ARMA model is covariance stationary (AR roots should lie inside the unit circle).
3. MA roots should lie inside unit circle.

If these three conditions are satisfied then forecasting process could be achieved appropriately.

4.10.2.2 The Estimated ARMA Model

Table 4.16 includes the estimated ARMA(1,1) model for terrorism index in Iraq during the period 2000-2020 with related statistics.

Table 4.16 Iraq TI ARMA Model

Dependent Variable: TI				
Method: ARMA Maximum Likelihood (OPG - BHHH)				
Included observations: 21				
Convergence achieved after 35 iterations				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	7.1287	1.91633	3.7199	0.0017
AR(1)	0.9313	0.1109	8.3908	0.0000
MA(1)	0.2948	0.2452	1.2022	0.2457
SIGMASQ	0.5102	0.1319	3.8673	0.0012
R-squared	0.8691	Mean dependent var	8.3910	
Adjusted R-squared	0.84611	S.D. dependent var	2.0238	
S.E. of regression	0.7939	Akaike info criterion	2.6696	
Sum squared resid.	10.7153	Schwarz criterion	2.8685	
Log likelihood	-24.0310	Hannan-Quinn criter.	2.7128	
F-statistic	37.6554	Durbin-Watson stat	1.8306	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000			

Source: developed by the researcher using EViews13.

In Table 4.16 the coefficient of one year TI lag AR(1) is significant at 1% significance level. Implying that, one year lag of TI has a significant positive effect on the present year TI. As one year lag of TI increases by one

point, TI increases by 0.93 points, *ceteris paribus*. While the coefficient of one year lag of the moving average hasn't any effect on TI, *ceteris paribus*. Though it has, jointly with rest variables, as the F statistic is significant at 1% level. The R squared and adjusted R squared are relatively close to each other, 87%, and 85%, respectively. indicating that 85% of the variations that might TI experience are due to the independent variables. Akaike and Schwarz criterions are 2.6, and 2.8 respectively. Durbin- Watson statistic is 1.83, which is close to 2, might be a sign of no serial correlation.

4.10.2.3 The Diagnostic Tests of the Estimated ARMA Model

The estimated model would be reliable, through the diagnostic tests, which are shown in Figure 4.9, and Tables 4.17, and 4.18.

Figure 4.9 AR and MA Roots of Terrorism ARMA Model

Source: Plotted by the researcher using EViews13.

From Figure 4.9 we can decide that the ARMA model is covariance stationary because autoregressive roots AR roots are locating inside the unit circle. Also, the moving average MA roots are inside the unit circle. And conclude the residuals are white noise, through (Ljung-Box Q statistics) and we accept H_0 , which says residuals are white noise.

Table 4.17 Ljung-Box Q Statistics of Iraq Terrorism ARMA Model

Sample (adjusted): 2000 2020

Q-statistic probabilities adjusted for 2 ARMA terms

Autocorrelation	Partial Correlation	AC	PAC	Q-Stat	Prob
		1	-0.0...	-0.0...	0.122...
		2	0.15...	0.15...	0.743...
		3	-0.2...	-0.2...	2.158... 0.14...
		4	-0.0...	-0.1...	2.335... 0.31...
		5	-0.1...	-0.1...	3.274... 0.35...
		6	0.01...	-0.0...	3.282... 0.51...
		7	-0.0...	-0.1...	3.601... 0.60...
		8	0.05...	-0.0...	3.709... 0.71...
		9	0.09...	0.09...	4.045... 0.77...
		10	-0.0...	-0.1...	4.410... 0.81...
		11	0.27...	0.25...	8.174... 0.51...
		12	-0.1...	-0.1...	10.14... 0.42...

Source: calculated by the researcher using EViews13.

Since residuals values of partial correlation, and autocorrelation coefficients are not spiking out of their significance boundaries in Table 4.17, and their probabilities are greater than 5%, so H0 will be accepted. Therefore, we can confirm that the residuals of the estimated ARMA (1,0,1) are white noise.

In order to be sure about well specification of the estimated ARMA model in Tab 4.16, Ramsey RESET test is applied, and the results are shown in Table 4.18.

Table 4.18 Ramsey RESET Test for the Estimated ARMA Model

Specification: TI C AR(1) MA(1)			
	Value	df	Probability
t-statistic	1.1478	16	0.2679
F-statistic	1.3175	(1, 16)	0.2679
Likelihood ratio	2.87519	1	0.0899

Source: calculated by the researcher using EViews13.

Looking at Table 4.18, the p-value of F-statistic is 0.26, which is greater than 0.05 we agree on the fact that the estimated ARMA model isn't mis-specified and could be relied on for the purpose of forecasting terrorism in Iraq.

4.10.2.4 Forecasting Iraq Terrorism Indices TI

Now we are reassured to forecast TI values for the years 2021 to 2028 as shown in Table 4.19.

Table 4.19 The Forecasted Values of Iraq TI from Year 2021 to 2028

Year	Forecasted TI	Upper Bound	Lower Bound
2021	8.24	9.56	6.91
2022	8.16	9.82	6.50
2023	8.09	10.01	6.17
2024	8.03	10.16	5.89
2025	7.96	10.28	5.65
2026	7.91	10.38	5.44
2027	7.85	10.45	5.25
2028	7.80	10.52	5.09

Source: calculated by the researcher using EViews13.

The following Figure 4.10 shows the forecasted values of TI during the period 2020-2028. Where we can observe a very slow declining in TI. And Their inequality coefficient of 0.02 is quite low, expresses a perfect fit of forecasted model.

Figure 4.10 Trend of the Forecasted Terrorism Indices From 2020 to 2028 in Iraq.

Source: Plotted by the researcher using EViews13.

As the time frame of Iraq’s annual Terrorism Index is from year 2000 to 2020, the ARMA model employed to forecast this index for extra eight extended years, i.e., until year 2028. According to the forecasted values in Table 4.19 terrorism index of Iraq is decreasing in a slow manner. In year 2021 TI expected to be 8.24, which located between the upper and lower boundaries of 9.56, and 6.91, respectively. Now, while the researcher writes this dissertation, we are in year 2023, GTI (2022) has reported Iraq’s actual TI for year 2021 to be 8.51, which is quite close to this study’s empirical forecasting’s. Considering the year 2028 TI might decline to 7.8, within the upper and lower boundaries of 10.52 and 5.09, respectively. Figure 4.11 shows the actual, and the forecasted values of TI along with its upper and lower boundaries.

Figure 4.11 Actual and Forecasted Iraq TI from 2000 to 2028
 Source: Plotted by the researcher using EViews13.

In Figure 4.11, the red line, represents the actual TI, and the purple line is the forecasted TI from year 2021 to 2028. We can see that the actual TI started to increase in year 2003 and was at pick of 10, during the years 2014 to 2018.

Then it started to decline from year 2019, but in a very slow pace. Now the results of ARMA forecasting's show a slow continuous declining in TI, where it may decline to 8 in year 2024, and keeps declining to reach 7.8 in year 2028, with ± 1 standard error for upper and lower boundaries, the dotted green and yellow frontiers, respectively.

4.10.2.5 Impulse Response of Iraq TI

The impulse response function (IRF) of a time series model, or dynamic response of the system, assesses the changes in the future responses of all variables in the system when one variable is shocked by an impulse (Lütkepohl, 2007). In this study starting at period 0 to period 24, the impulse depicts the dynamic responses, during which impulse runs one shock to the innovation or change.

Figure 4.12 Two Panels Representing the Impulse Response to One SD Innovation of Iraq TI Within 24 Years.

Source: Plotted by the researcher using EViews13.

Figure 4.12 contains two panels represent the impulse responses, and the accumulates responses of one standard deviation innovation might occur to Iraq terrorism index. In these panels we note that both blue curves incur few fluctuations at the first five periods, as being relatively far from zero, i.e., not stationarity. But they get closer and closer to zero as time passes and be stationary starting from period 5 and onwards. Bothe curves are representing reliable images as they remain within the boundaries of ± 2 standard errors.

4.11 Summary of the Econometrics Results - Chapter Four:

Table 4.20 shows the summary results of the econometric methods used in this chapter.

Table 4.20 Summary of the Econometrics Results – Chapter Four

ARDL Model (Dependent Variable TI)							
Effect on TI	Variable	Sign & Coefficient	Relationship	Magnitude	P-Value of t-statistic		
Long-run	INF	+0.036	Positive	Small	0.016		
	GDPG	-0.030	Inverse	Small	0.020		
	UEM	-0.224	Inverse	Small	0.011		
	GINI	-0.201	Inverse	Small	0.000		
	PS	-0.717	Inverse	Moderate	0.10		
Short-run	D(INF)	0.014	Positive	Small	0.000		
	D(GINI)	-0.0431	Inverse	Small	0.000		
ECT	TI _{t-1}	-0.819	Inverse	High	0.000		
Variance Decomposition in VAR							
Period	TI%	INF%	GINI%	UEM%	GDPG%	PS%	Effect
1	100	0	0	0	0	0	Short-run
2	96.54	1.25	2.09	0.06	0.06	0	
9	88.90	3.16	2.50	3.86	0.19	1.39	Long-run
10	87.41	3.48	2.83	4.24	0.20	1.83	
Impulse Responses of TI as a Result of Shocks to the Studied Variables in VAR							
Period	TI	INF	GINI	UEM	GDPG	PS	Effect
1	0.63	0	0	0	0	0	Short-run
2	0.73	0.11	-0.14	-0.02	-0.02	0	
9	0.07	0.08	0.08	-0.10	0.01	-0.09	Long-run

10	0.03	0.08	0.08	-0.09	0.02	-0.09	
Forecasting Terrorism Index by ARMA Model							
Year	TI	Upper bound	Lower Bound	Time Frame			
2025	8.24	9.56	6.91	Short-run			
2028	7.80	10	5.09	Long-run			

CHAPTER FIVE: CONCLUSIONS, RECOMMENDATIONS, LIMITATIONS, AND FUTURE STUDIES.

5.1 Conclusions

5.1.1 The Selected Countries Panel Data Analysis

This study examined the impact of certain economic and other different determinants on terrorism, in Iraq, Afghanistan, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Nigeria, Pakistan, Syria, and Yamen, from year 2000 to 2021, and reached to the following conclusions:

- i. The countries mentioned previously were selected because they have been the most exposed to terrorist threats in the world during the last decade. While the overall averages for the studied determinants are; GDPG =3.27%, INF= 10.04%, UEM=7.77%, G=38.96, PS= -2.05, EXI=8.68, and DP=8.61.
- ii. Certain tests have been executed to select amongst the static models of POLS, FEM, and REM. The selected REM for the economic model indicated; as inflation and unemployment increase by 1%, terrorism index rises by 0.03 and 0.28 points, respectively, all other factors being constant. While the selected FEM for the assorted variables (Economic, Political, and Demographic) model showed as each of economic globalization index, and political stability index rises by a point, terrorism index declines by 0.08, and 2.28 points, respectively, other factors being constant. However, both estimated REM and FEM models have certain problems, including heteroskedasticity, autocorrelation, and residual CSD. Alternatively, after assessing the benefits of employing the dynamic structure, MG, DFE, and PMG models were estimated.

- iii. The results of Hausman test for selecting the best model amongst MG, DFE, and PMG models, revealed the appropriateness of the PMG model for both of economic and assorted variables models.
- iv. The long run section of the economic PMG model demonstrates a significant negative relationship between GDP growth rate and terrorism threats. Thus, as GDP growth rate increases by 1%, terrorism decreases by 0.34 points, *ceteris paribus*. However, the results revealed a positive significant relationship between inflation rate and terrorism, thus, as inflation increases by 1% terrorism index rises by 0.13 points. In the short-run section, as economic globalization index rises by one point terrorism decreases by 0.10 points, other factors being constant.
- v. The long run section for the assorted variables PMG model, reveals that as each of inflation rate and demographic pressures rises by 1%, and 1 point, terrorism will rise by 0.05, and 0.75 points, respectively. Whereas, when each of political stability index, external interventions, rises by one point, terrorism index rises by 2, and 0.65 points. Also, GDP growth, has significant inverse relationship with terrorism, thus, when it rises by 1% terrorism drops by 0.8 points. In the short run, Economic globalization has a significant and adverse impact on terrorism. Therefore, as G rises by a point TI drops by 0.09 points, *ceteris paribus*.
- vi. The result of error correction coefficient 0.256 for the assorted variables PMG model, is larger than the economic model's error correction coefficient 0.109. This suggests that a state of equilibrium for the assorted PMG model could be achieved in a shorter period of time, approximately 4 years, whereas the economic model takes a longer time period, more than 9 years.

- vii. The DH test of panel data Granger causality, shows that each of Unemployment, GDP growth, economic globalization, political stability, and demographic pressures Granger cause terrorism in the selected countries under study. Thus, we can conclude that these determinants might participate in future predictions of terrorism index in the selected countries.

5.1.2 Iraq's Time Series Analysis

- i. Iraq's terrorism index reached 10, which is its highest score during years 2014 to 2017, indicating that Iraq suffered from severe terrorism consequences during these four years. Specifically, during the period of ISIS extensive threats on the country. The number of deaths was 13965, the highest in year 2014, which is corresponding to the highest number of incidents 3933 in 2014, as shown in Table 4.2. The Number of terrorist attacks in Iraq decreased significantly in the recent years 2019 and 2020 to reach to 1131, and 495 respectively. Correspondingly, the number of deaths from terrorism decreased to 1054, and 564 for the same years 2019, and 2020.
- ii. Annual growth rates are fluctuating for each indicator comparing to its previous year figure. Considering TI in year 2003 terrorism increased by 60.39%. Iraq's GDP dropped to 36.66% in the same year. In 2014 the year of ISIS attacks, TI raised by 11% comparing with year 2013, and unemployment increased by 14.31%, and inflation raised by 15.79%. And Political stability experienced anticable decrease 8.87% in 2015 comparing to year 2014.

The consequences of terrorism growth in Iraq for the entire period of the study 2000-2020 was 4.36%, associated with 2.62% increase in GDP growth, 2.42% increase in unemployment, and 1.89% increase in the growth

- of political stability, which is a slight increase comparing to period (1), 2000-2002, the era of Bath party authority in Iraq.
- iii. Inflation rate has a positive relationship with terrorism in Iraq in the long run. Therefore, as INF increases by one percent, TI increases by 0.036 points, *ceteris paribus*. And GDP growth, unemployment, income inequality, and Political stability are having inverse relationship with terrorism in the long run. Therefore, if each of these variables increases by one unit, individually, terrorism reduces by 0.03, 0.22, 0.20, and 0.71 points, respectively, *ceteris paribus*. In the long run political stability has a quite high impact on TI in Iraq.
 - iv. Concerning the short run impacts, if inflation rate increases by one percent, terrorism index increases by 0.014 points. While if GINI coefficient increases by one unit, TI will decrease by 0.043 points.
 - v. The coefficient of ECT = 0.819, this means that 81.9% of any activities into disequilibrium are corrected for within one period, which is one year in this study. In another word, the speed of adjustment from previous year's disequilibrium in TI is added to current year's equilibrium by 81.9%.
 - vi. The analysis of variance decomposition results showed that TI explains 100%, 96.54%, and 96.61% of the variances in TI in the first, second, and the third period (year) respectively. Then the variances in TI are declining gradually during the 10-year periods until it reaches to 90.49% and 88.9 % in year 9th, and 10th, respectively. The results show each of the exogenous variables; INF, GINI, UEM, GDPG, and PS are not having any contemporaneous effect on TI, i.e., in the first period. This validates the accuracy of estimating a dynamic model such as ARDL, as previously done. Comparing with other exogenous variables, GINI and INF contribute in explaining greater variations in TI, in the short run (period 2) by 2% and 1.2%, respectively. While UEM and INF are explaining the greater variations in TI in the long run by 4.2% and 3.4%, respectively. Therefore,

we can say that unemployment is having the heaviest weight for explaining the variances in TI comparing to the remaining independent variables in the long run, next comes inflation.

- vii. Impulse Response on Iraq's Terrorism Index TI, which illustrated in Figure 4.7, shows that one standard deviation shock to each economic determinant is affecting the endogenous variable TI significantly at 5% significant level.
- viii. The findings of TI forecasting reveal that terrorism in Iraq will decline over the next eight years, from 2021 to 2028, although at a very slow rate. It is expected to be 7.8 in 2028, which is still considered high. As a result, we may accept that Iraq's high terrorism index will endure in the long run.

5.1.3 Summary of Conclusions

Summing up all conclusions produced from the empirical findings in this study we reach to a point that economic variables have minor impacts on creating terrorism, particularly in the long-run. At the mean time political and demographic factors have more impacts on terrorism, either in the selected countries collectively or in Iraq alone.

5.2 Recommendations

5.2.1 The Selected Countries Panel Data Analysis

This study analyzed upon the macro level; therefore, our recommendations also will be developed on the same level. Based on the econometric findings of this study, the researchers recommend that counterterrorism establishments in the selected countries should focus on implementing reforms related to economic, political, and demographic issues. Some key areas for the improvements include:

- i. **Economic Measures:** Monitoring and promoting GDP growth and economic globalization can be effective in reducing terrorism. Efforts to control inflation and unemployment rates are also crucial to address potential drivers of terrorism.
- ii. **Political Stability:** Recognizing the significant impact of political stability on terrorism, attention should be directed towards stabilizing political affairs both within and outside the countries. This can be achieved through enhancing political freedom and fostering negotiations rather than resorting to violence.
- iii. **Addressing Demographic Pressures:** Acknowledging the influence of demographic pressures on terrorism, strategies to address population-related issues should be considered, such as ensuring access to education, healthcare, employment opportunities, and reducing the factors that cause local and outside country's migrations.
- iv. **Strengthening External Relationships:** Improving a country's external relations through trade, sports, strategic agreements, and diplomatic efforts can help prevent illegal external interference that may exploit vulnerable circumstances within these countries.

v. Since the factor of Economic Globalization (G) has a significant inverse impact on terrorism in the short run, the economic policies of the studied countries should be directed to expanding extent of trade across borders. Increases in the movement of international capital, and the wide and rapid dissemination of technology are all contributing to the growing interdependence of world economies, which ultimately lead to reduce terrorism.

5.2.2 Iraq's Time Series Analysis

Weakness of preventing or slow pace of reducing terrorist activities in Iraq is generally due to shortages in funding and resources, inadequate arrangement and organization, deprived distribution of resources, deficiency of consciousness and education, unintended growth, beliefs and culture (Al-Dahasha Kulatungab and Thayaparan 2018). Sluggish responses to the disasters might not suspend the instant outcome of the disaster, as a result the response might be fragmented, unproductive and useless that leads to augmented number of casualties, deaths, and indirect costs. Therefore, the researcher recommends authorities have to work on reducing the rate of inflation, increasing the GDP growth, making more job opportunities and safeguarding political stability. Also, working on improvements in; policy and administrative decisions, actions, technologies, and reducing the effect of media and rumors regarding spreading the spirits of revenge and violence among people. These factors should be taken into concern in order to reduce terrorist incidents in Iraq.

The results of forecasting's show that terrorism in Iraq Republic will decline in a quite slow pace, indicating the existence of sustainable high levels of terrorism in the long run future, to be more than 7 on scale of 10. This leads to sluggish the sustainable economic development, or worse, might leads to economic deficiency or depression. Hence, the researcher recommendations to

the country's related agencies of counter terrorism, to perform more practical steps toward speed up reducing and combating terrorism actions in Iraq.

5.2.3 Summary of Recommendations

Subsequent to the empirical results of this study, authoritarians in the investigated countries must seek to improve and offer more stable political, demographic, and economic conditions in their countries, solidified by their national or patriotic devotion to their people and country, rather than only safeguarding the interests of certain parties or allies, either in the selected countries jointly or in Iraq alone.

5.3 Limitations and Future Studies

5.3.1 The Selected Countries Panel Data Analysis

The researcher desired to include other economically weak countries into the panel analyses, such as Sudan, Somalia, Burkina Faso, Mali, and others, where terrorist operations have increased in recent years (GTD, 2022). However, due to data collecting challenges, a lack of time, and a lack of sources relevant to the topic throughout the research period, this could not be achieved. Therefore, the researcher suggests including extra countries and extra years in future studies and applying appropriate panel data analysis, and models. Also conduct studies of data related to economically and socially developed countries where terrorist operations are less frequent, in order to make comparisons between the variables that cause terrorism for the two groups countries.

5.3.2 Iraq's Time Series Analysis

Due to the inadequate availability of data in Iraq, the study was limited to the framework in which it is currently located. However, for future studies in order to track the impact of economic variables on terrorism in Iraq, the researcher suggests entering extra variables for a period of more years into the time series to be studied and experimenting the impact of other economic variables such as the per capita GDP, poverty, consumer price index, and others, in addition to political, demographic, ideological, and factional discrimination variables, in order to know their impact in the long term on the one hand and the short term on the other hand. And also constructing econometric models for total cost functions of terrorism in the country.

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1. APPENDICIES RELATED TO THE SELECTED COUNTRIES STUDY

Appendix 1. 1 Raw Panel Data for The Seven Selected Countries in Years 2000-2021.

CID	C	Years	TI	UEM	INF	PS	G	DP	GDPG
1	Iraq	2000	3.7	8.727	5	-1.74	51.493	8.4647	16.9
1	Iraq	2001	4	8.807	16.4	-1.68	50.193	8.4645	1.7
1	Iraq	2002	4.09	8.852	19.3	-1.61	50.652	8.4642	-8.2
1	Iraq	2003	6.56	8.819	33.6	-2.39	50.087	8.4638	-36.66
1	Iraq	2004	8.03	8.608	27	-3.18	49.697	8.4633	53.39
1	Iraq	2005	8.65	8.706	37	-2.69	49.316	8.4626	1.67
1	Iraq	2006	9.1	8.652	53.2	-2.83	47.653	8.9	5.65
1	Iraq	2007	9.45	8.65	-10.1	-2.77	45.094	9	1.89
1	Iraq	2008	9.33	8.484	12.7	-2.47	39.647	9	8.23
1	Iraq	2009	9.33	8.393	6.9	-2.18	43.749	8.7	3.38
1	Iraq	2010	9.22	8.251	2.9	-2.24	41.365	8.5	6.4
1	Iraq	2011	9.11	8.122	5.8	-1.85	40.509	8.3	7.55
1	Iraq	2012	9.56	7.96	6.1	-1.93	40.087	8	14
1	Iraq	2013	9.01	9.264	1.9	-2.01	39.833	8.3	7.62
1	Iraq	2014	10	10.59	2.2	-2.48	40.818	8	0.2
1	Iraq	2015	10	10.725	1.4	-2.26	44.879	8.2	4.72
1	Iraq	2016	9.96	10.82	0.6	-2.31	42.807	8.1	13.79
1	Iraq	2017	10	13.02	0.2	-2.31	42.663	8.6	-1.82
1	Iraq	2018	9.75	12.966	0.4	-2.53	43.05	8.7	2.63
1	Iraq	2019	8.68	12.863	-0.2	-2.6	43.185	8.4	5.5
1	Iraq	2020	8.682	14.088	0.6	-2.53	37.192	8.1	-11.3
1	Iraq	2021	8.511	16.2	6	-2.4	38	8.5	2.8
2	Afghanistan	2000	5.3	10.806	6.0677	-2.44	33.305	8.9328	6.1436
2	Afghanistan	2001	6	10.809	6.0677	-2.15	33.794	8.9328	6.1436
2	Afghanistan	2002	5.7	11.257	6.0677	-2.04	34.071	8.9328	6.1436
2	Afghanistan	2003	6.06	11.141	6.0677	-2.2	32.485	8.9329	8.83
2	Afghanistan	2004	6.38	10.988	6.0677	-2.3	34.02	8.9329	1.41
2	Afghanistan	2005	6.77	11.217	12.7	-2.07	34.635	8.933	11.23
2	Afghanistan	2006	7.31	11.099	6.8	-2.22	31.742	7.9	5.36
2	Afghanistan	2007	7.69	11.301	8.7	-2.41	32.046	8.5	13.83

CID	C	Years	TI	UEM	INF	PS	G	DP	GDPG
2	Afghanistan	2008	8.01	11.093	26.4	-2.69	35.353	9.1	3.93
2	Afghanistan	2009	8.25	11.311	-6.8	-2.71	33.018	9.3	21.39
2	Afghanistan	2010	8.02	11.352	2.2	-2.58	34.708	9.5	14.36
2	Afghanistan	2011	8.05	11.054	11.8	-2.5	39.235	9.1	0.43
2	Afghanistan	2012	8.669	11.341	6.4	-2.42	37.207	8.9	12.75
2	Afghanistan	2013	8.66	11.193	7.4	-2.52	34.021	9.3	5.6
2	Afghanistan	2014	9.39	11.142	4.7	-2.41	34.174	8.8	2.73
2	Afghanistan	2015	9.233	11.127	-0.7	-2.57	33.445	9.3	1.45
2	Afghanistan	2016	9.444	11.158	4.4	-2.67	30.554	9.5	2.26
2	Afghanistan	2017	9.603	11.18	5	-2.8	30.112	9.3	2.64
2	Afghanistan	2018	9.391	11.152	0.6	-2.75	33.213	9.2	1.19
2	Afghanistan	2019	9.603	11.217	2.3	-2.65	31.298	9.3	3.91
2	Afghanistan	2020	9.592	11.71	5.21	-2.479	29.114	9	-2.35
2	Afghanistan	2021	9.109	13.283	9.01	-2.53	30	9.1	-20.7
3	Congo De R	2000	3	2.904	-0.88	-2.48	26.646	9.6227	-6.91
3	Congo De R	2001	3.5	2.888	0.06	-2.187	31.4	9.6227	-2.1
3	Congo De R	2002	3.72	2.871	4.38	-1.98	28.925	9.6227	2.95
3	Congo De R	2003	3.64	2.86	-0.63	-2.03	30.811	9.6227	5.58
3	Congo De R	2004	2.9	2.853	2.43	-2.39	31.291	9.6227	6.74
3	Congo De R	2005	2.23	2.85	3.09	-2.13	33.537	9.6227	6.14
3	Congo De R	2006	1.58	3.083	6.54	-2.25	30.83	9.5	5.32
3	Congo De R	2007	0.4	3.313	2.65	-2.18	32.472	9.4	6.26
3	Congo De R	2008	0.0001	3.547	4.96	-2.01	34.793	9.6	6.23
3	Congo De R	2009	0.0001	3.793	4.42	-2	37.594	9.7	2.86
3	Congo De R	2010	7.08	4.014	0.39	-2.2	38.752	9.9	7.11
3	Congo De R	2011	6.61	4.252	1.76	-2.21	38.594	9.7	6.88
3	Congo De R	2012	6.182	4.49	5.01	-2.09	35.368	9.9	7.09
3	Congo De R	2013	5.86	4.476	4.63	-2.19	37.229	10	8.48
3	Congo De R	2014	5.9	4.464	0.91	-2.17	34.089	9.4	9.47
3	Congo De R	2015	6.487	4.466	3.17	-2.15	34.874	9.5	6.92
3	Congo De R	2016	6.633	4.477	3.19	-2.23	33.511	9.1	2.4
3	Congo De R	2017	7.039	4.465	0.45	-2.35	35.363	9.4	3.73
3	Congo De R	2018	7.055	4.451	1.15	-2.11	36.635	9.6	5.82
3	Congo De R	2019	7.039	4.451	2.21	-1.81	34.014	9.8	4.39
3	Congo De R	2020	7.178	5.266	1.8	-2.156	33.23	9.8	1.74
3	Congo De R	2021	6.733	5.426	1.72	-1.61	34	9.7	6.2

CID	C	Years	TI	UEM	INF	PS	G	DP	GDGP
4	Nigeria	2000	3.5	3.954	6.9	-1.46	47.334	8.7871	5.02
4	Nigeria	2001	3.7	3.935	18.9	-1.582	47.293	8.7985	6
4	Nigeria	2002	3.86	3.882	12.9	-1.63	45.127	8.8108	15.33
4	Nigeria	2003	4.36	3.899	14	-1.63	44.572	8.8241	7.36
4	Nigeria	2004	4.39	3.876	15	-1.75	41.835	8.8384	9.25
4	Nigeria	2005	4.22	3.871	17.9	-1.67	42.675	8.8538	6.44
4	Nigeria	2006	5.83	3.856	8.2	-2.03	44.397	8	6.06
4	Nigeria	2007	5.71	3.837	5.4	-2.01	47.343	8.2	6.6
4	Nigeria	2008	5.79	3.819	11.6	-1.86	45.187	8.2	6.76
4	Nigeria	2009	6.44	3.796	12.6	-2	45	8.5	8.04
4	Nigeria	2010	6.23	3.778	13.7	-2.21	44.07	8.4	8.01
4	Nigeria	2011	6.13	3.77	10.8	-1.96	45.645	8.3	5.31
4	Nigeria	2012	7.242	3.742	12.2	-2.04	45.21	8.4	4.23
4	Nigeria	2013	7.8	3.7	8.5	-2.09	44.627	8.5	6.67
4	Nigeria	2014	8.58	4.56	8.1	-2.13	41.342	8.3	6.31
4	Nigeria	2015	9.213	4.31	9	-1.93	40.433	8.8	2.65
4	Nigeria	2016	9.314	7.06	15.7	-1.88	40.089	9.1	-1.62
4	Nigeria	2017	9.01	8.39	16.5	-2	42.305	9.1	0.81
4	Nigeria	2018	8.66	8.456	12.1	-2.09	44.905	9.1	1.92
4	Nigeria	2019	8.597	8.53	11.4	-1.93	44.066	9.2	1.9
4	Nigeria	2020	8.314	9.714	13.25	-1.844	40.768	9.3	-1.79
4	Nigeria	2021	8.233	9.788	16.95	-1.78	42	9.5	3.6
5	Pakistan	2000	5.8	0.579	4.37	-1.1	33.458	8.4838	4.2601
5	Pakistan	2001	5.9	0.565	3.15	-1.47	35.08	8.4838	3.5544
5	Pakistan	2002	6.19	0.548	3.29	-1.64	37.278	8.4838	2.5083
5	Pakistan	2003	6.12	0.59	2.91	-1.55	35.96	8.4838	5.777
5	Pakistan	2004	6.57	0.613	7.45	-1.58	36.097	8.4838	7.5469
5	Pakistan	2005	6.54	0.593	9.06	-1.75	40.474	8.4838	6.5188
5	Pakistan	2006	6.92	0.58	7.92	-2.03	42.441	9.3	5.899
5	Pakistan	2007	7.74	0.4	7.6	-2.43	43.39	8.2	4.8328
5	Pakistan	2008	8.15	0.42	20.29	-2.57	40.663	8	1.7014
5	Pakistan	2009	8.52	0.54	13.65	-2.64	37.371	8.3	2.8317
5	Pakistan	2010	8.29	0.65	12.94	-2.68	38.658	8.1	1.6067
5	Pakistan	2011	8.44	0.8	11.92	-2.81	36.828	8.8	2.7484
5	Pakistan	2012	9.049	1.847	9.68	-2.68	36.818	8.5	3.507
5	Pakistan	2013	8.67	2.95	7.69	-2.6	36.819	8.9	4.3965

CID	C	Years	TI	UEM	INF	PS	G	DP	GDGP
5	Pakistan	2014	9.37	1.83	7.19	-2.4	36.196	8.8	4.6747
5	Pakistan	2015	9.065	3.57	2.53	-2.48	33.614	9	4.7311
5	Pakistan	2016	8.613	3.779	3.77	-2.48	33.725	8.9	5.5267
5	Pakistan	2017	8.4	3.916	4.09	-2.41	33.764	8.4	5.5543
5	Pakistan	2018	8.181	4.08	5.08	-2.26	33.618	8.1	5.8364
5	Pakistan	2019	7.889	3.542	10.58	-2.25	34.318	7.8	0.9888
5	Pakistan	2020	7.541	4.303	9.74	-1.527	34.287	7.9	0.5255
5	Pakistan	2021	7.825	4.352	9.5	-1.67	35	8.2	6.5
6	Syria	2000	0.07	9.604	-3.8	-0.18	28.676	7.0294	0.6756
6	Syria	2001	0.08	11.63	3	0.1574	28.099	7.0311	1.0473
6	Syria	2002	0.09	10.928	-0.1	0.28	28.116	7.0333	3.9548
6	Syria	2003	0.0001	10.28	5.8	0.06	27.901	7.0359	7.2044
6	Syria	2004	2.28	9.536	4.4	-0.29	28.803	7.0392	6.903
6	Syria	2005	1.62	8.853	7.2	-0.46	31.05	7.0434	6.2151
6	Syria	2006	2.25	8.17	10	-0.28	29.806	7	5.0462
6	Syria	2007	1.6	8.42	3.9	-0.34	32.377	6.5	5.6746
6	Syria	2008	3.47	10.94	15.7	-0.34	32.087	6.5	4.4767
6	Syria	2009	2.77	8.14	2.9	-0.51	33.123	6.1	5.912
6	Syria	2010	2.68	8.61	4.4	-0.81	33.925	5.9	5.1919
6	Syria	2011	2.04	8.697	4.8	-2.01	35.304	5.6	2.85
6	Syria	2012	5.861	8.808	36.7	-2.68	32.345	5.5	-26.34
6	Syria	2013	7.11	8.826	52.785	-2.68	33.416	5.6	-26.3
6	Syria	2014	8.12	8.721	45.933	-2.75	35.092	6	-10.31
6	Syria	2015	8.108	8.712	26.877	-2.97	33.832	8.1	-4.18
6	Syria	2016	8.587	8.725	6.3481	-2.92	33.413	8.4	-6.406
6	Syria	2017	8.006	8.752	-4.921	-2.62	32.52	8.2	-0.723
6	Syria	2018	8.315	8.755	3.8	-2.73	31.897	8.2	1.3932
6	Syria	2019	8.006	8.773	34.52	-2.73	31.895	7.9	1.2207
6	Syria	2020	7.778	10.257	63.1	-0.893	32.532	7.6	-3.874
6	Syria	2021	8.25	10.573	7	-2.66	33	7.3	-3.8
7	Yeman	2000	3.2	11.558	11	-1.14	53.085	9.1638	6.18
7	Yeman	2001	3.3	11.714	11.9	-1.199	52.545	9.1815	3.8
7	Yeman	2002	3.45	11.84	12.2	-1.31	52.271	9.2003	3.94
7	Yeman	2003	3.87	11.971	10.8	-1.48	51.982	9.2201	3.75
7	Yeman	2004	3.17	12.097	12.5	-1.55	51.473	9.2411	3.97
7	Yeman	2005	3.54	12.206	9.9	-1.44	51.485	9.2633	5.6

CID	C	Years	TI	UEM	INF	PS	G	DP	GDPG
7	Yeman	2006	3.71	12.366	10.8	-1.35	55.321	7.8	3.17
7	Yeman	2007	4.2	12.494	7.9	-1.59	55.796	8	3.34
7	Yeman	2008	5.26	12.621	19	-2.01	55.425	8.6	3.65
7	Yeman	2009	5.27	12.749	3.7	-2.33	54.835	8.8	3.87
7	Yeman	2010	5.08	12.831	11.2	-2.42	53.339	8.6	7.7
7	Yeman	2011	6.32	13.235	19.5	-2.43	52.962	8.7	-12.72
7	Yeman	2012	7.31	13.167	9.9	-2.43	50.282	8.8	2.39
7	Yeman	2013	6.83	13.268	11	-2.37	49.659	9.3	4.82
7	Yeman	2014	7.31	13.47	8.1	-2.67	46.46	9.1	-0.2
7	Yeman	2015	7.642	13.77	22	-2.68	36.896	9.2	-28
7	Yeman	2016	8.076	13.433	21.3	-2.79	37	9.5	-9.38
7	Yeman	2017	7.88	13.297	30.4	-2.94	40.971	9.3	-5.1
7	Yeman	2018	7.534	13.145	27.6	-2.99	43.086	9.6	0.75
7	Yeman	2019	7.259	13.056	12	-2.77	44.909	9.7	1.4
7	Yeman	2020	7.581	13.391	23.1	-1.502	45.717	9.8	8.5
7	Yeman	2021	5.87	13.574	45.7	-2.59	46	9.9	-2.1

Appendix 1. 2 Description of the Studied Panel Data

A. Cross-Country Correlation of The Variables Under Study

Variable(s): TI

Panel var: CID

corrMatrix[7,7]

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	.81193865	1	0	0	0	0	0
3	.2471508	.59424501	1	0	0	0	0
4	.74387195	.97113802	.65903119	1	0	0	0
5	.83537461	.85357612	.42348455	.82086965	1	0	0
6	.65988746	.92965944	.67896046	.96363092	.73325401	1	0
7	.67731603	.93425673	.71611362	.94849358	.83325506	.91245615	1

Variable(s): INF

Panel var: CID

corrMatrix[7,7]

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	.21938821	1	0	0	0	0	0
3	.26809763	.17904363	1	0	0	0	0
4	.23324162	.02971478	-.21832989	1	0	0	0
5	-.05917614	.44002185	.36384755	-.07093964	1	0	0
6	-.25079993	-.01560846	.2304323	-.28101138	.16940568	1	0
7	-.24961893	.13316652	-.19115803	.36003815	-.07177073	-.08185894	1

Variable(s): UEM

Panel var: CID

corrMatrix[7,7]

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	.65997828	1	0	0	0	0	0
3	.72230085	.57252076	1	0	0	0	0
4	.95633691	.56017159	.69640523	1	0	0	0
5	.87524093	.45474765	.84300664	.85750111	1	0	0
6	.11528921	.1797011	-.20840302	.07654374	-.10412331	1	0
7	.56738718	.42011465	.92749265	.5192855	.76467649	-.40871092	1

Variable(s): GDPG

Panel var: CID

corrMatrix[7,7]

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	-.06022127	1	0	0	0	0	0
3	.0114808	-.05453637	1	0	0	0	0
4	.04001872	.37106128	.1264616	1	0	0	0
5	.22882051	-.23057251	.16813995	.01091359	1	0	0
6	-.09163961	.11572962	-.2292222	.27055311	.04376461	1	0
7	-.05075091	.3040034	-.20731104	.33530582	-.17784562	.10654197	1

Variable(s): G

Panel var: CID

corrMatrix[7,7]

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	.04941907	1	0	0	0	0	0
3	-.71378536	.2911013	1	0	0	0	0
4	.33496195	.40803485	-.16753483	1	0	0	0
5	.08835139	.25675254	.01641361	.35839561	1	0	0
6	-.8209355	.12730827	.80312807	-.37649623	-.02923489	1	0
7	.29532253	.43201338	-.17178491	.72226314	.70832458	-.35938204	1

Variable(s): PS

Panel var: CID

corrMatrix[7,7]

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	.07364698	1	0	0	0	0	0
3	-.00416209	-.06805319	1	0	0	0	0
4	.24598044	.54810765	-.02633197	1	0	0	0
5	-.0043149	.5854278	-.06603435	.83849022	1	0	0
6	.00133875	.61206278	-.19127121	.54648201	.53134096	1	0
7	.04004467	.78882349	-.26151304	.67895829	.707363	.89265553	1

Variable(s): EXI

Panel var: CID

corrMatrix[7,7]

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	.39498757	1	0	0	0	0	0
3	.3088336	.56325064	1	0	0	0	0
4	.20346957	.53942549	.30748647	1	0	0	0
5	.21902796	.66423277	.61060183	.77533487	1	0	0
6	-.42741212	-.57701517	-.19257288	-.21275257	-.20770887	1	0
7	-.34458071	-.60254809	-.11747297	-.00328134	-.10850207	.92488421	1

Variable(s): DP

Panel var: CID

corrMatrix[7,7]

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	-.3431177	1	0	0	0	0	0
3	-.11933911	.16121654	1	0	0	0	0
4	-.29764788	.46703076	-.03211313	1	0	0	0
5	-.23485757	-.33153492	-.33580363	-.39312474	1	0	0
6	.03790677	.17249707	-.52070014	.71721404	-.12482147	1	0
7	-.51695858	.58692089	.10511966	.90778497	-.32316994	.51139587	1

Appendix 1. 3 Variables Descriptive Statistics

Variable		Mean	Std. dev.	Min	Max	Observations
TI	overall	6.476508	2.591852	.0001	10	N = 154
	between		1.642094	4.413232	8.3965	n = 7
	within		2.09555	1.780008	10.65028	T = 22
GDPG	overall	3.273189	8.501374	-36.66	53.39	N = 154
	between		2.52569	-1.098467	5.220909	n = 7
	within		8.17128	-37.93408	52.11592	T = 22

UEM	overall		7.770721	4.083074	.4	16.2		N =	154
	between			4.113064	1.865773	12.78423		n =	7
	within			1.440896	5.659493	13.89949		T =	22
INF	overall		10.04292	11.20445	-10.1	63.1		N =	154
	between			4.874941	2.427727	15.97727		n =	7
	within			10.24873	-10.46163	58.12742		T =	22
G	overall		38.96275	7.135391	26.64571	55.79638		N =	154
	between			6.731176	31.78225	49.15893		n =	7
	within			3.438594	26.69994	46.27564		T =	22
PS	overall		-2.057546	.6690596	-3.18	.28		N =	154
	between			.3489741	-2.459487	-1.379821		n =	7
	within			.5852975	-3.647725	-.3977254		T =	22
EXI	overall		8.680389	1.370302	5.4	10		N =	154
	between			1.215664	6.124811	9.608336		n =	7
	within			.776357	5.943425	10.44342		T =	22
DP	overall		8.616975	.9170091	5.5	10		N =	154
	between			.845888	6.936924	9.624378		n =	7
	within			.4728516	7.180051	10.08005		T =	22

Appendix 1. 4 Pre-Estimations Tests

A. The Economic-Variables Model

VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria
 Endogenous variables: TI GDPG INF UEM G
 Exogenous variables: C
 Date: 09/03/23 Time: 01:30
 Sample: 2000 2021
 Included observations: 98

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-1479.055	NA	9795785.	30.28684	30.41873	30.34019
1	-1098.754	714.0355*	6954.712*	23.03579*	23.82711*	23.35586*
2	-1082.773	28.37418	8393.576	23.21986	24.67060	23.80665
3	-1065.536	28.84493	9933.336	23.37829	25.48847	24.23182
4	-1048.119	27.36997	11818.15	23.53304	26.30265	24.65329
5	-1027.387	30.46339	13303.42	23.62015	27.04918	25.00712
6	-1006.847	28.08548	15277.12	23.71116	27.79963	25.36486
7	-991.0571	19.97905	19728.06	23.89912	28.64702	25.81955
8	-973.1512	20.82929	25033.17	24.04390	29.45123	26.23106

* indicates lag order selected by the criterion

LR: sequential modified LR test statistic (each test at 5% level)

FPE: Final prediction error

AIC: Akaike information criterion

SC: Schwarz information criterion

HQ: Hannan-Quinn information criterion

B. The Mix-Variables Model

VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria
 Endogenous variables: TI GDPG INF G PS EXI DP
 Exogenous variables: C
 Date: 09/03/23 Time: 01:51
 Sample: 2000 2021
 Included observations: 98

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-1527.280	NA	93591.75	31.31183	31.49647	31.38652
1	-1069.260	841.2615	22.23997*	22.96448*	24.44161*	23.56195*
2	-1045.022	41.05532	37.40009	23.46984	26.23945	24.59009
3	-1009.489	55.11327	51.10983	23.74466	27.80676	25.38770
4	-973.8624	50.16743	72.25256	24.01760	29.37218	26.18342

Modified Phillips-Perron t	3.4334	0.0003
Phillips-Perron t	2.5176	0.0059
Augmented Dickey-Fuller t	3.1002	0.0010

Kao test for cointegration

H0: No cointegration	Number of panels	=	7
Ha: All panels are cointegrated	Number of periods	=	20
Cointegrating vector: Same			
Panel means:	Included	Kernel:	Bartlett
Time trend:	Not included	Lags:	1.57 (Newey-West)
AR parameter:	Same	Augmented lags:	1

	Statistic	p-value
Modified Dickey-Fuller t	-0.4614	0.3223
Dickey-Fuller t	-1.0575	0.1451
Augmented Dickey-Fuller t	-1.2442	0.1067
Unadjusted modified Dickey-Fuller t	-0.7651	0.2221
Unadjusted Dickey-Fuller t	-1.2371	0.1080

ii. The Mix-Variables model

Westerlund test for cointegration

H0: No cointegration	Number of panels	=	7
Ha: All panels are cointegrated	Number of periods	=	22
Cointegrating vector: Panel specific			
Panel means:	Included		
Time trend:	Not included		
AR parameter:	Same		

	Statistic	p-value
Variance ratio	5.1391	0.0000

Pedroni test for cointegration

H0: No cointegration	Number of panels	=	7
Ha: All panels are cointegrated	Number of periods	=	21
Cointegrating vector: Panel specific			
Panel means:	Included	Kernel:	Bartlett
Time trend:	Not included	Lags:	1.00 (Newey-West)
AR parameter:	Panel specific	Augmented lags:	1

	Statistic	p-value
Modified Phillips-Perron t	2.7578	0.0029
Phillips-Perron t	-1.2838	0.0996
Augmented Dickey-Fuller t	-0.9300	0.1762

Kao test for cointegration

H0: No cointegration	Number of panels	=	7
Ha: All panels are cointegrated	Number of periods	=	20
Cointegrating vector: Same			
Panel means:	Included	Kernel:	Bartlett
Time trend:	Not included	Lags:	1.57 (Newey-West)
AR parameter:	Same	Augmented lags:	1

	Statistic	p-value
Modified Dickey-Fuller t	-2.0449	0.0204
Dickey-Fuller t	-1.8038	0.0356
Augmented Dickey-Fuller t	-0.9198	0.1788

Unadjusted modified Dickey-Fuller t	-2.5519	0.0054
Unadjusted Dickey-Fuller t	-2.0083	0.0223

Appendix 1. 5 Static model estimations with related tests for the economic variables

A. POLS Economic variables:

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	154
Model	22.4115424	4	5.6028856	F(4, 149)	=	0.83
Residual	1005.39645	149	6.74762717	Prob > F	=	0.5078
				R-squared	=	0.0218
				Adj R-squared	=	-0.0045
Total	1027.80799	153	6.71769929	Root MSE	=	2.5976

TI	Coefficient	Std. err.	t	P> t	[95% conf. interval]
GDPG	-.0102235	.0270508	-0.38	0.706	-.0636762 .0432292
INF	.0182012	.020795	0.88	0.383	-.0228901 .0592924
UEM	.0599331	.0536806	1.12	0.266	-.0461405 .1660067
G	.0014118	.0315451	0.04	0.964	-.0609216 .0637453
_cons	5.806447	1.184379	4.90	0.000	3.466099 8.146795

vif

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
INF	1.23	0.812380
GDPG	1.20	0.833915
G	1.15	0.870485
UEM	1.09	0.918016
Mean VIF	1.17	

Testing for slope heterogeneity
(Pesaran, Yamagata. 2008. Journal of Econometrics)
H0: slope coefficients are homogenous

	Delta	p-value
	5.519	0.000
adj.	6.472	0.000

Variables partialled out: constant
Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity
Assumption: Normal error terms
Variable: Fitted values of TI
H0: Constant variance
chi2(1) = 2.33
Prob > chi2 = 0.1271

Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data
H0: no first-order autocorrelation

F(1, 6) = 107.297
 Prob > F = 0.0000

Average correlation coefficients & Pesaran (2004) CD test
 Variables series tested: Ui

Group variable: CID
 Number of groups: 7
 Average # of observations: 25.67
 Panel is: unbalanced

Variable	CD-test	p-value	corr	abs(corr)
Ui	5.77	0.000	0.269	0.315

Notes: Under the null hypothesis of cross-section independence CD ~ N(0,1)

Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian multiplier test for random effects

TI[CID,t] = Xb + u[CID] + e[CID,t]

Estimated results:

	Var	SD = sqrt(Var)
TI	6.717699	2.591852
e	3.923954	1.980897
u	3.067673	1.751478

Test: Var(u) = 0

chibar2(01) = 192.44
 Prob > chibar2 = 0.0000

Ramsey RESET test for omitted variables

Omitted: Powers of fitted values of TI

H0: Model has no omitted variables

F(3, 146) = 0.16

Prob > F = 0.9210

B. FEM Economic Variables

Fixed-effects (within) regression

Group variable: CID

R-squared:

Within = 0.1648

Between = 0.0034

Overall = 0.0172

Number of obs = 154

Number of groups = 7

Obs per group:

min = 22

avg = 22.0

max = 22

F(4,143) = 7.06

Prob > F = 0.0000

corr(u_i, Xb) = -0.6311

TI	Coefficient	Std. err.	t	P> t	[95% conf. interval]
GDPG	-.0243462	.0213325	-1.14	0.256	-.066514 .0178216
INF	.0430826	.016705	2.58	0.011	.010062 .0761033
UEM	.3850524	.120173	3.20	0.002	.1475073 .6225974
G	-.0669354	.0509955	-1.31	0.191	-.1677379 .033867
_cons	5.739377	2.433397	2.36	0.020	.9292993 10.54945
sigma_u	2.3777154				
sigma_e	1.9808972				
rho	.5902939	(fraction of variance due to u_i)			

F test that all u_i=0: F(6, 143) = 18.87

Prob > F = 0.0000

Modified Wald test for groupwise heteroskedasticity
in fixed effect regression model
H0: $\sigma(i)^2 = \sigma^2$ for all i
chi2 (7) = 435.46
Prob>chi2 = 0.0000

Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data
H0: no first-order autocorrelation
F(1, 6) = 8.842
Prob > F = 0.0248

Correlation matrix of residuals:

	__e1	__e2	__e3	__e4	__e5	__e6	__e7
__e1	1.0000						
__e2	0.6671	1.0000					
__e3	0.0681	0.5374	1.0000				
__e4	0.7167	0.8775	0.4237	1.0000			
__e5	0.8367	0.5126	-0.0449	0.6981	1.0000		
__e6	0.4684	0.8376	0.6007	0.7475	0.2266	1.0000	
__e7	0.5466	0.8653	0.4672	0.7647	0.4827	0.5884	1.0000

Breusch-Pagan LM test of independence: chi2(21) = 175.463, Pr = 0.0000

Based on 22 complete observations over panel units

C. REM Economic Variables

Random-effects GLS regression	Number of obs	=	154
Group variable: CID	Number of groups	=	7
R-squared:	Obs per group:		
Within = 0.1626	min =		22
Between = 0.0100	avg =		22.0
Overall = 0.0169	max =		22
	Wald chi2(4)	=	23.45
corr(u_i, X) = 0 (assumed)	Prob > chi2	=	0.0001

TI	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]
GDPG	-.0254611	.0214842	-1.19	0.236	-.0675693 .0166471
INF	.0397836	.016801	2.37	0.018	.0068541 .072713
UEM	.2804857	.0987315	2.84	0.004	.0869755 .4739958
G	-.0706299	.0456573	-1.55	0.122	-.1601165 .0188567
__cons	6.732664	2.143801	3.14	0.002	2.53089 10.93444
sigma_u	1.7514775				
sigma_e	1.9808972				
rho	.43876388				(fraction of variance due to u_i)

Average correlation coefficients & Pesaran (2004) CD test

Variables series tested: Ui

Group variable: CID
Number of groups: 7
Average # of observations: 25.67
Panel is: unbalanced

Variable	CD-test	p-value	corr	abs(corr)
Ui	9.71	0.000	0.452	0.452

Notes: Under the null hypothesis of cross-section independence CD ~ N(0,1)

Correlated Random Effects - Hausman Test
 Equation: Untitled
 Test cross-section random effects

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	7.251216	4	0.1232

Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data
 H0: no first-order autocorrelation
 F(1, 6) = 5.399
 Prob > F = 0.0592

Panel Groupwise Heteroscedasticity Tests

Ho: Panel Homoscedasticity - Ha: Panel Groupwise Heteroscedasticity			
- Lagrange Multiplier LM Test	=2301.7014	P-Value > Chi2(6)	0.0000
- Likelihood Ratio LR Test	= 20.6872	P-Value > Chi2(6)	0.0021
- Wald Test	=2393.6185	P-Value > Chi2(7)	0.0000

Appendix 1. 6 Dynamic model estimations with related tests for the economic variables

A. G2SLS random-effects

G2SLS random-effects IV regression
 Group variable: CID

Number of obs = 147
 Number of groups = 7

R-squared:
 Within = 0.8433
 Between = 0.9934
 Overall = 0.8954

Obs per group:
 min = 21
 avg = 21.0
 max = 21

corr(u_i, X) = 0 (assumed)

Wald chi2(5) = 1206.80
 Prob > chi2 = 0.0000

TI	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
TI	.9127457	.0265592	34.37	0.000	.8606907	.9648007
GDPG	-.0133532	.0088416	-1.51	0.131	-.0306824	.0039761
INF	.0073579	.006759	1.09	0.276	-.0058896	.0206053
G	.0094393	.0105749	0.89	0.372	-.0112872	.0301657
UEM	-.0115439	.0178391	-0.65	0.518	-.0465079	.02342
_cons	.4528375	.4306335	1.05	0.293	-.3911887	1.296864
sigma_u	0					
sigma_e	.8254426					
rho	0	(fraction of variance due to u_i)				

Instrumented: L.TI
 Instruments: GDPG INF G UEM L.TI

	D1.		-.0053117	.0074444	-0.71	0.476	-.0199024	.0092789
	G							
	D1.		-.0050851	.0458351	-0.11	0.912	-.0949203	.0847501
	_cons		.3489985	.9066427	0.38	0.700	-1.427989	2.125986

CID_2								
	__ec		-.0755727	.0281291	-2.69	0.007	-.1307048	-.0204407
	GDPG							
	D1.		.0275614	.0093652	2.94	0.003	.009206	.0459168
	UEM							
	D1.		-.3992792	.1430854	-2.79	0.005	-.6797214	-.118837
	INF							
	D1.		-.0004526	.0073267	-0.06	0.951	-.0148127	.0139074
	G							
	D1.		-.0461157	.0276767	-1.67	0.096	-.100361	.0081296
	_cons		.7570768	.6770692	1.12	0.263	-.5699544	2.084108

CID_3								
	__ec		-.2033247	.1125686	-1.81	0.071	-.4239551	.0173056
	GDPG							
	D1.		.1828345	.1191438	1.53	0.125	-.050683	.416352
	UEM							
	D1.		.7759967	1.623973	0.48	0.633	-2.406932	3.958926
	INF							
	D1.		-.223741	.1182977	-1.89	0.059	-.4556002	.0081182
	G							
	D1.		-.186399	.1662947	-1.12	0.262	-.5123307	.1395326

		_cons		- .3555298	1.455909	-0.24	0.807	-3.209059	2.497999

CID_4									
		_ec		- .0737718	.0464953	-1.59	0.113	- .164901	.0173573
		GDPG							
		D1.		- .0196655	.0282314	-0.70	0.486	- .0749981	.035667
		UEM							
		D1.		.051576	.1692034	0.30	0.761	- .2800564	.3832085
		INF							
		D1.		- .0487616	.0230179	-2.12	0.034	- .0938758	- .0036474
		G							
		D1.		- .0627776	.0533966	-1.18	0.240	- .1674331	.0418778
		_cons		- .0348604	.6900711	-0.05	0.960	-1.387375	1.317654

CID_5									
		_ec		- .0782361	.034975	-2.24	0.025	- .1467859	- .0096863
		GDPG							
		D1.		.0501466	.0322376	1.56	0.120	- .0130378	.113331
		UEM							
		D1.		- .2029261	.1167314	-1.74	0.082	- .4317155	.0258632
		INF							
		D1.		- .0081074	.0186575	-0.43	0.664	- .0446754	.0284605
		G							
		D1.		- .0386713	.0358769	-1.08	0.281	- .1089887	.0316462
		_cons		- .0443202	.5492578	-0.08	0.936	-1.120846	1.032205

CID_6									

	__ec		-.1279975	.0569203	-2.25	0.025	-.2395591	-.0164358
	GDPG							
	D1.		-.0264199	.0280306	-0.94	0.346	-.0813589	.0285191
	UEM							
	D1.		.1071931	.1597339	0.67	0.502	-.2058795	.4202658
	INF							
	D1.		-.0102586	.0103793	-0.99	0.323	-.0306017	.0100845
	G							
	D1.		-.2886953	.1445555	-2.00	0.046	-.5720189	-.0053717
	_cons		.2506844	.9808519	0.26	0.798	-1.67175	2.173119

CID_7								
	__ec		-.113264	.057668	-1.96	0.050	-.2262913	-.0002367
	GDPG							
	D1.		.0418675	.0230307	1.82	0.069	-.0032719	.0870069
	UEM							
	D1.		1.335785	1.212178	1.10	0.270	-1.04004	3.71161
	INF							
	D1.		-.0220858	.0168558	-1.31	0.190	-.0551225	.0109509
	G							
	D1.		-.0801656	.0501907	-1.60	0.110	-.1785376	.0182063
	_cons		-.2593493	1.225745	-0.21	0.832	-2.661765	2.143067

Average correlation coefficients & Pesaran (2004) CD test

Variables series tested: Ui

Group variable: CID

Number of groups: 7
Average # of observations: 25.67
Panel is: unbalanced

Variable	CD-test	p-value	corr	abs(corr)
Ui	-0.17	0.861	-0.008	0.254

Notes: Under the null hypothesis of cross-section independence $CD \sim N(0,1)$

Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data

H0: no first-order autocorrelation

F(1, 6) = 0.221
Prob > F = 0.6550

C. MG model full Economic Variables

Mean Group Estimation: Error Correction Form
(Estimate results saved as MG)

D.TI	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
CID_1_ec						
GDPG	-.938752	4.314546	-0.22	0.828	-9.395107	7.517602
UEM	-3.895382	17.78023	-0.22	0.827	-38.74399	30.95323
INF	.5839417	2.348282	0.25	0.804	-4.018606	5.186489
G	.8395592	5.764309	0.15	0.884	-10.45828	12.1374
CID_1SR						
_ec	-.0340113	.1434663	-0.24	0.813	-.3152001	.2471775
GDPG						
D1.	.0189473	.0116911	1.62	0.105	-.0039668	.0418614
UEM						
D1.	.3284047	.3064485	1.07	0.284	-.2722234	.9290328
INF						
D1.	-.0072874	.0134485	-0.54	0.588	-.0336461	.0190713
G						
D1.	-.0054479	.0726395	-0.07	0.940	-.1478187	.1369229
_cons	.4130229	4.532535	0.09	0.927	-8.470583	9.296628
CID_2_ec						
GDPG	-.2622524	.2604658	-1.01	0.314	-.7727559	.2482512
UEM	2.069141	6.873696	0.30	0.763	-11.40306	15.54134
INF	.3172452	.4450937	0.71	0.476	-.5551224	1.189613
G	.0814051	.5205033	0.16	0.876	-.9387626	1.101573
CID_2SR						

__ec		-.07515	.0652918	-1.15	0.250	-.2031197	.0528196
GDPG							
D1.		.0267573	.0189382	1.41	0.158	-.0103609	.0638756
UEM							
D1.		-.6251847	.6952333	-0.90	0.369	-1.987817	.7374475
INF							
D1.		-.0070505	.0129322	-0.55	0.586	-.0323971	.0182962
G							
D1.		-.0398204	.0406065	-0.98	0.327	-.1194076	.0397668
_cons		-1.128902	6.282183	-0.18	0.857	-13.44175	11.18395

CID_3__ec							
GDPG		-.1957648	.2485833	-0.79	0.431	-.6829791	.2914496
UEM		1.438198	.869393	1.65	0.098	-.2657812	3.142177
INF		-.8545294	.3704201	-2.31	0.021	-1.58054	-.1285193
G		.4618027	.3617421	1.28	0.202	-.2471989	1.170804

CID_3SR							
__ec		-.6498987	.2321804	-2.80	0.005	-1.104964	-.1948336
GDPG							
D1.		.1408064	.1306798	1.08	0.281	-.1153213	.3969341
UEM							
D1.		-1.273197	1.815596	-0.70	0.483	-4.8317	2.285306
INF							
D1.		.1160797	.1819856	0.64	0.524	-.2406055	.472765
G							
D1.		-.411055	.1749974	-2.35	0.019	-.7540436	-.0680664
_cons		-8.549083	4.460092	-1.92	0.055	-17.2907	.1925364

CID_4__ec							
GDPG		-.8127564	.5807214	-1.40	0.162	-1.950949	.3254366
UEM		-.8928346	.9896855	-0.90	0.367	-2.832583	1.046913
INF		-.210736	.2825245	-0.75	0.456	-.7644738	.3430018
G		-.3902742	.4220841	-0.92	0.355	-1.217544	.4369955

CID_4SR							
__ec		-.1946059	.1374511	-1.42	0.157	-.464005	.0747933
GDPG							
D1.		.0634014	.0533519	1.19	0.235	-.0411665	.1679692
UEM							
D1.		-.0632647	.2168102	-0.29	0.770	-.4882048	.3616754
INF							
D1.		-.0319685	.0444312	-0.72	0.472	-.119052	.055115
G							
D1.		-.0469721	.0894253	-0.53	0.599	-.2222424	.1282982
_cons		7.101517	4.922568	1.44	0.149	-2.546538	16.74957

CID_5__ec							
GDPG		.1957579	.8952087	0.22	0.827	-1.558819	1.950335
UEM		-.0800292	1.374283	-0.06	0.954	-2.773575	2.613516
INF		.0678509	.4313501	0.16	0.875	-.7775797	.9132815
G		.9230525	1.750856	0.53	0.598	-2.508561	4.354666

CID_5SR							
__ec		-.0756219	.1285153	-0.59	0.556	-.3275073	.1762635
GDPG							
D1.		.0273049	.0664286	0.41	0.681	-.1028926	.1575025
UEM							
D1.		-.2191972	.1511491	-1.45	0.147	-.515444	.0770496
INF							
D1.		-.0126638	.0332025	-0.38	0.703	-.0777395	.0524119
G							
D1.		-.0718421	.0619866	-1.16	0.246	-.1933336	.0496494
_cons		-1.934681	1.944071	-1.00	0.320	-5.74499	1.875629

CID_6__ec							
GDPG		-.2727076	.2713961	-1.00	0.315	-.8046341	.259219
UEM		-1.099855	2.25128	-0.49	0.625	-5.512284	3.312574
INF		.1042036	.1143539	0.91	0.362	-.119926	.3283332
G		-.2498263	1.121902	-0.22	0.824	-2.448713	1.94906

CID_6SR							
__ec		-.1817232	.1038755	-1.75	0.080	-.3853155	.021869
GDPG							
D1.		-.0207175	.0392022	-0.53	0.597	-.0975525	.0561174
UEM							
D1.		.1902989	.3218253	0.59	0.554	-.4404671	.8210649
INF							
D1.		-.0156066	.019125	-0.82	0.414	-.053091	.0218777
G							
D1.		-.2808285	.2301285	-1.22	0.222	-.7318721	.170215
_cons		4.15758	9.060287	0.46	0.646	-13.60026	21.91542

CID_7__ec							
GDPG		-.4108089	.7154209	-0.57	0.566	-1.813008	.9913903
UEM		2.268562	1.225704	1.85	0.064	-.1337734	4.670898
INF		-.0832605	.2019814	-0.41	0.680	-.4791367	.3126156
G		.1243904	.4049653	0.31	0.759	-.6693269	.9181077

CID_7SR							
__ec		-.2330746	.3264258	-0.71	0.475	-.8728574	.4067082
GDPG							
D1.		.077726	.0337448	2.30	0.021	.0115873	.1438647
UEM							
D1.		2.750077	1.777625	1.55	0.122	-.7340035	6.234157
INF							
D1.		-.0105133	.0292081	-0.36	0.719	-.0677602	.0467335
G							
D1.		.0398563	.066465	0.60	0.549	-.0904128	.1701253
_cons		-6.649305	7.306228	-0.91	0.363	-20.96925	7.670638

Average correlation coefficients & Pesaran (2004) CD test

Variables series tested: Ui
 Group variable: CID
 Number of groups: 7
 Average # of observations: 25.67
 Panel is: unbalanced

Variable	CD-test	p-value	corr	abs(corr)
Ui	-0.45	0.650	-0.021	0.153

Notes: Under the null hypothesis of cross-section independence CD ~ N(0,1)

Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data
 H0: no first-order autocorrelation
 F(1, 6) = 0.061
 Prob > F = 0.8133

D.DFE Model:

full option not meaningful with dfe
 ignoring option and continuing...

Dynamic Fixed Effects Regression: Estimated Error Correction Form
 (Estimate results saved as DFE)

	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	

ec						
GDPG	-.2935437	.1181302	-2.48	0.013	-.5250747	-.0620127
UEM	-.1872515	.441795	-0.42	0.672	-1.053154	.6786508
INF	.0519764	.0632391	0.82	0.411	-.0719699	.1759227
G	.418718	.2211006	1.89	0.058	-.0146312	.8520672

SR						
ec	-.136895	.0362311	-3.78	0.000	-.2079066	-.0658834
GDPG						
D1.	.0215546	.0091029	2.37	0.018	.0037132	.039396
UEM						
D1.	.0724818	.1239848	0.58	0.559	-.1705239	.3154875
INF						
D1.	-.0036548	.0080235	-0.46	0.649	-.0193805	.012071
G						
D1.	-.0672115	.0338271	-1.99	0.047	-.1335114	-.0009116
_cons	-.9074003	1.120313	-0.81	0.418	-3.103174	1.288373

Average correlation coefficients & Pesaran (2004) CD test

Variables series tested: Ui
 Group variable: CID
 Number of groups: 7
 Average # of observations: 25.67
 Panel is: unbalanced

Variable	CD-test	p-value	corr	abs(corr)
Ui	-0.31	0.758	-0.014	0.179

Notes: Under the null hypothesis of cross-section independence $CD \sim N(0,1)$

Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data

H0: no first-order autocorrelation

F(1, 6) = 0.047
 Prob > F = 0.8361

hausman pmg dfe

---- Coefficients ----				
	(b)	(B)	(b-B)	sqrt(diag(V_b-V_B))
	pmg1	dfel	Difference	Std. err.
GDPG	-.3391821	-.2935437	-.0456384	.2199018
UEM	-.7496382	-.1872515	-.5623867	1.050363
INF	.1307488	.0519764	.0787724	.1331793
G	.3201144	.418718	-.0986036	.3784501

b = Consistent under H0 and Ha; obtained from xtpmg.
 B = Inconsistent under Ha, efficient under H0; obtained from xtpmg.

Test of H0: Difference in coefficients not systematic

chi2(4) = (b-B)' [(V_b-V_B)^(-1)] (b-B)
 = 0.68
 Prob > chi2 = 0.9533

hausman mg pmg

---- Coefficients ----				
	(b)	(B)	(b-B)	sqrt(diag(V_b-V_B))
	mg1	pmg1	Difference	Std. err.
GDPG	-.3853263	-.3391821	-.0461442	.085973
UEM	-.0274571	-.7496382	.7221812	.6282885
INF	-.0107549	.1307488	-.1415037	.1570043
G	.2557299	.3201144	-.0643845	.

b = Consistent under H0 and Ha; obtained from xtpmg.
 B = Inconsistent under Ha, efficient under H0; obtained from xtpmg.

Test of H0: Difference in coefficients not systematic

chi2(4) = (b-B)' [(V_b-V_B)^(-1)] (b-B)
 = 1.87
 Prob > chi2 = 0.7590

Appendix 1. 7 Static model estimations and the related tests for the model of assorted variables

A. POLS of the Assorted variables

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	154
				F(6, 147)	=	21.57
Model	481.24872	6	80.20812	Prob > F	=	0.0000
Residual	546.559271	147	3.71809028	R-squared	=	0.4682
				Adj R-squared	=	0.4465
Total	1027.80799	153	6.71769929	Root MSE	=	1.9282

TI	Coefficient	Std. err.	t	P> t	[95% conf. interval]	
GDPG	.0096391	.0200617	0.48	0.632	-.0300076	.0492858
INF	-.0018741	.0161281	-0.12	0.908	-.033747	.0299988
G	-.0039306	.0252124	-0.16	0.876	-.0537561	.045895
PS	-2.837086	.2771344	-10.24	0.000	-3.384768	-2.289404
EXI	-.0701916	.1380153	-0.51	0.612	-.342942	.2025588
DP	-.2394636	.2109494	-1.14	0.258	-.6563489	.1774217
_cons	3.452233	1.829313	1.89	0.061	-.1629165	7.067382

vif

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
DP	1.54	0.649418
EXI	1.47	0.679425
PS	1.41	0.706835
INF	1.34	0.744185
G	1.33	0.750870
GDPG	1.20	0.835436

Mean VIF | 1.38

Testing for slope heterogeneity

(Pesaran, Yamagata. 2008. Journal of Econometrics)

H0: slope coefficients are homogenous

	Delta	p-value
	3.635	0.000
adj.	4.557	0.000

Variables partialled out: constant

Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity

Assumption: Normal error terms

Variable: Fitted values of TI

H0: Constant variance

chi2(1) = 0.09

Prob > chi2 = 0.7656

Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data

H0: no first-order autocorrelation

F(1, 6) = 36.921

Prob > F = 0.0009

Average correlation coefficients & Pesaran (2004) CD test

Variables series tested: Ui

Group variable: CID

Number of groups: 7

Average # of observations: 25.67

Panel is: unbalanced

Variable	CD-test	p-value	corr	abs(corr)
Ui	6.95	0.000	0.323	0.372

Notes: Under the null hypothesis of cross-section independence $CD \sim N(0,1)$

Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian multiplier test for random effects

$$TI[CID,t] = Xb + u[CID] + e[CID,t]$$

Estimated results:

	Var	SD = sqrt(Var)
TI	6.717699	2.591852
e	2.365932	1.538159
u	0	0

Test: $\text{Var}(u) = 0$

chibar2(01) = 0.00

Prob > chibar2 = 1.0000

Ramsey RESET test for omitted variables

Omitted: Powers of fitted values of TI

H0: Model has no omitted variables

F(3, 144) = 1.05

Prob > F = 0.3707

B. FEM for the Assorted Variables:

Fixed-effects (within) regression

Number of obs = 154

Group variable: CID

Number of groups = 7

R-squared:

Obs per group:

Within = 0.5035

min = 22

Between = 0.1681

avg = 22.0

Overall = 0.3642

max = 22

F(6,141) = 23.83

corr(u_i, Xb) = -0.2011

Prob > F = 0.0000

TI	Coefficient	Std. err.	t	P> t	[95% conf. interval]	
GDPG	-.0082761	.0168792	-0.49	0.625	-.041645	.0250929
INF	.0014557	.0137626	0.11	0.916	-.0257521	.0286635
G	-.0883623	.0386923	-2.28	0.024	-.1648543	-.0118704
PS	-2.287876	.2430723	-9.41	0.000	-2.768414	-1.807339
EXI	-.0497081	.2225467	-0.22	0.824	-.4896678	.3902515
DP	.6565595	.3429852	1.91	0.058	-.0214987	1.334618
_cons	-.0016649	2.991369	-0.00	1.000	-5.915397	5.912067

sigma_u		1.5892617	
sigma_e		1.5381586	
rho		.51633597	(fraction of variance due to u_i)

F test that all $u_i=0$: F(6, 141) = 15.00

Prob > F = 0.0000

Average correlation coefficients & Pesaran (2004) CD test

Variables series tested: Ui

Group variable: CID

Number of groups: 7

Average # of observations: 25.67

Panel is: unbalanced

```
-----  
Variable |      CD-test  p-value      corr  abs(corr)  
-----+-----  
      Ui |          5.27   0.000    0.245   0.500  
-----
```

Notes: Under the null hypothesis of cross-section
independence $CD \sim N(0,1)$

LR: $F(6, 141) = 15.00$ Prob > F = 0.0000

Modified Wald test for groupwise heteroskedasticity
in fixed effect regression model

H0: $\sigma(i)^2 = \sigma^2$ for all i

chi2 (7) = 380.83

Prob>chi2 = 0.0000

Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data

H0: no first-order autocorrelation

F(1, 6) = 30.770

Prob > F = 0.0015

Correlation matrix of residuals:

	__e1	__e2	__e3	__e4	__e5	__e6	__e7
__e1	1.0000						
__e2	0.7474	1.0000					
__e3	0.4516	0.5617	1.0000				
__e4	0.7205	0.7923	0.6808	1.0000			
__e5	-0.1147	0.2918	0.2220	0.3021	1.0000		
__e6	0.1177	0.4373	0.1031	0.3919	0.6926	1.0000	
__e7	-0.0033	0.2194	-0.2274	-0.0380	0.0764	0.3251	1.0000

Notes: Under the null hypothesis of cross-section
independence $CD \sim N(0,1)$

Correlated Random Effects - Hausman Test

Equation: Untitled

Test cross-section random effects

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	90.012023	6	0.0000

* Panel Groupwise Heteroscedasticity Tests

=====

Ho: Panel Homoscedasticity - Ha: Panel Groupwise Heteroscedasticity

- Lagrange Multiplier LM Test	=4551.8647	P-Value > Chi2(6)	0.0000
- Likelihood Ratio LR Test	= 37.7451	P-Value > Chi2(6)	0.0000
- Wald Test	=6615.4880	P-Value > Chi2(7)	0.0000

Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data

H0: no first-order autocorrelation

F(1, 6) = 8.431
Prob > F = 0.0272

Appendix 1. 8 Dynamic model estimations with the related tests for the model of assorted variables

A. Adding lag of TI to FEM

Fixed-effects (within) IV regression	Number of obs	=	147
Group variable: CID	Number of groups	=	7
R-squared:	Obs per group:		
Within = 0.8584	min =		21
Between = 0.9769	avg =		21.0
Overall = 0.9003	max =		21
corr(u_i, Xb) = 0.2654	Wald chi2(7)	=	10907.13
	Prob > chi2	=	0.0000

TI | Coefficient Std. err. z P>|z| [95% conf. interval]
-----+-----
TI |

L1.		.8077056	.0438209	18.43	0.000	.7218182	.893593
GDPG		-.0135212	.0088325	-1.53	0.126	-.0308327	.0037902
INF		.0018831	.0072269	0.26	0.794	-.0122813	.0160475
G		.029308	.0218429	1.34	0.180	-.0135033	.0721194
PS		-.4686372	.1624687	-2.88	0.004	-.7870701	-.1502044
EXI		.0904495	.1172664	0.77	0.441	-.1393885	.3202875
DP		-.1893507	.1838562	-1.03	0.303	-.5497022	.1710009
_cons		.1892906	1.581406	0.12	0.905	-2.910208	3.288789

sigma_u		.28014638					
sigma_e		.79834632					
rho		.1096364	(fraction of variance due to u_i)				

F test that all u_i=0: F(6,133) =				1.40	Prob > F =		0.2211

Instrumented: L.TI							
Instruments: GDPG INF G PS EXI DP L.TI							

A. PMG model full - Socioeconomic variables

Iteration 0: log likelihood = -92.734609 (not concave)
 Iteration 1: log likelihood = -87.893735 (not concave)
 Iteration 2: log likelihood = -83.663928
 Iteration 3: log likelihood = -82.934975
 Iteration 4: log likelihood = -82.335889
 Iteration 5: log likelihood = -82.328011
 Iteration 6: log likelihood = -82.328007

Pooled Mean Group Regression

(Estimate results saved as PMG)

Panel Variable (i): CID	Number of obs	=	147
Time Variable (t): Years	Number of groups	=	7
	Obs per group: min	=	21
	avg	=	21.0
	max	=	21
	Log Likelihood	=	-82.32801

D.TI	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
__ec						
GDPG	-.0806726	.039619	-2.04	0.042	-.1583245	-.0030207
INF	.0518786	.0253729	2.04	0.041	.0021487	.1016085
G	.0047418	.0469387	0.10	0.920	-.0872564	.09674
PS	-2.036248	.2466158	-8.26	0.000	-2.519607	-1.55289
EXI	-.6514067	.3072597	-2.12	0.034	-1.253625	-.0491887
DP	.7547996	.4642697	1.63	0.104	-.1551522	1.664751

```

-----+-----
CID_1   |
__ec | -.1263177 .0452313 -2.79 0.005 -.2149694 -.037666
      |
GDPG |
D1. | -.0004555 .0055588 -0.08 0.935 -.0113505 .0104396
      |
INF |
D1. | -.0035069 .0060734 -0.58 0.564 -.0154105 .0083966
      |
G |
D1. | .0023424 .0403435 0.06 0.954 -.0767295 .0814143
      |
PS |
D1. | -1.089115 .4003438 -2.72 0.007 -1.873775 -.304456
      |
EXI |
D1. | .3296143 .2252287 1.46 0.143 -.1118258 .7710543
      |
DP |
D1. | -.3956953 .3847444 -1.03 0.304 -1.149781 .3583898
      |
_cons | .5749199 .5176734 1.11 0.267 -.4397014 1.589541
-----+-----

```

```

-----+-----
CID_2   |
__ec | -.06011 .0487034 -1.23 0.217 -.1555669 .0353469
      |
GDPG |
D1. | .0277943 .0091002 3.05 0.002 .0099582 .0456305
      |
INF |
D1. | .0104461 .0075676 1.38 0.167 -.0043861 .0252783
      |
G |
D1. | -.0076048 .0288309 -0.26 0.792 -.0641123 .0489027
      |
PS |
D1. | -.1874855 .4355259 -0.43 0.667 -1.041101 .6661296
-----+-----

```

EXI							
D1.		.2867458	.2268223	1.26	0.206	-.1578178	.7313094
DP							
D1.		-.3212375	.1894495	-1.70	0.090	-.6925517	.0500767
_cons		.365004	.2371012	1.54	0.124	-.0997057	.8297138

CID_3							
__ec		-.1501955	.1276283	-1.18	0.239	-.4003424	.0999515
GDPG							
D1.		.177706	.1141291	1.56	0.119	-.0459829	.401395
INF							
D1.		-.2489522	.1201939	-2.07	0.038	-.4845279	-.0133764
G							
D1.		-.1906889	.1664625	-1.15	0.252	-.5169494	.1355716
PS							
D1.		-1.296904	1.44299	-0.90	0.369	-4.125113	1.531305
EXI							
D1.		.9746374	1.431807	0.68	0.496	-1.831653	3.780928
DP							
D1.		2.330227	1.475097	1.58	0.114	-.5609089	5.221363
_cons		.1422341	.6241273	0.23	0.820	-1.081033	1.365501

CID_4							
__ec		-.0390914	.0697766	-0.56	0.575	-.1758512	.0976683
GDPG							
D1.		-.0446076	.0271833	-1.64	0.101	-.0978858	.0086707

INF							
D1.		-.0288912	.024831	-1.16	0.245	-.0775592	.0197767
G							
D1.		-.0582369	.0504321	-1.15	0.248	-.1570821	.0406082
PS							
D1.		-1.140277	.8722191	-1.31	0.191	-2.849795	.5692408
EXI							
D1.		-.2500778	.3738096	-0.67	0.503	-.9827312	.4825755
DP							
D1.		-.1337911	.5100661	-0.26	0.793	-1.133502	.8659201
_cons		.1845912	.1762879	1.05	0.295	-.1609268	.5301092

CID_5							
_ec		-.4044347	.1106374	-3.66	0.000	-.6212799	-.1875895
GDPG							
D1.		.0736414	.0306071	2.41	0.016	.0136527	.1336301
INF							
D1.		.0006237	.0179374	0.03	0.972	-.0345329	.0357803
G							
D1.		-.0145961	.0354004	-0.41	0.680	-.0839797	.0547875
PS							
D1.		.2146729	.323086	0.66	0.506	-.4185641	.8479098
EXI							
D1.		-.1325884	.2582006	-0.51	0.608	-.6386523	.3734754
DP							
D1.		-.2873907	.1899768	-1.51	0.130	-.6597384	.084957

	_cons		1.125216	1.5197	0.74	0.459	-1.853342	4.103774

CID_6								
	__ec		-.3413951	.1234298	-2.77	0.006	-.583313	-.0994771
	GDPG							
	D1.		-.0003687	.0352458	-0.01	0.992	-.0694492	.0687119
	INF							
	D1.		-.0129788	.0143728	-0.90	0.367	-.041149	.0151913
	G							
	D1.		-.2973727	.172743	-1.72	0.085	-.6359428	.0411975
	PS							
	D1.		.2993944	.4162538	0.72	0.472	-.5164481	1.115237
	EXI							
	D1.		.2530678	.25694	0.98	0.325	-.2505254	.756661
	DP							
	D1.		-.38766	.4605296	-0.84	0.400	-1.290281	.5149614
	_cons		.6013337	1.033056	0.58	0.561	-1.423419	2.626086

CID_7								
	__ec		-.6710362	.1698036	-3.95	0.000	-1.003845	-.3382273
	GDPG							
	D1.		.0349501	.0137467	2.54	0.011	.0080071	.0618931
	INF							
	D1.		-.0117575	.0157562	-0.75	0.456	-.0426391	.0191241
	G							
	D1.		-.1005234	.0503175	-2.00	0.046	-.1991439	-.0019028
	PS							

D1.		1.830607	.3689366	4.96	0.000	1.107504	2.553709
EXI							
D1.		-.6176921	.3747477	-1.65	0.099	-1.352184	.1167998
DP							
D1.		.4645124	.3944804	1.18	0.239	-.3086549	1.23768
_cons		-.3553516	2.735752	-0.13	0.897	-5.717328	5.006625

Average correlation coefficients & Pesaran (2004) CD test

Variables series tested: Ui

Group variable: CID

Number of groups: 7

Average # of observations: 25.67

Panel is: unbalanced

Variable		CD-test	p-value	corr	abs(corr)
Ui		1.51	0.132	0.070	0.359

Notes: Under the null hypothesis of cross-section independence $CD \sim N(0,1)$

Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data

H0: no first-order autocorrelation

F(1, 6) = 1.712

Prob > F = 0.2386

B. MG Model Mix Variables

Mean Group Estimation: Error Correction Form

(Estimate results saved as MG)

D.TI		Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]
CID_1__ec						

GDPG		.0596267	.0384491	1.55	0.121	-.0157322	.1349855
INF		.0368354	.0375209	0.98	0.326	-.0367041	.110375
G		-.4816159	.1056971	-4.56	0.000	-.6887784	-.2744534
PS		-1.880193	.9352423	-2.01	0.044	-3.713235	-.0471523
EXI		1.496492	.8676081	1.72	0.085	-.2039884	3.196973
DP		-.9799007	1.883232	-0.52	0.603	-4.670968	2.711167
-----+-----							
CID_1SR							
__ec		-.5546668	.2485388	-2.23	0.026	-1.041794	-.0675396
GDPG							
D1.		-.0297881	.0192572	-1.55	0.122	-.0675314	.0079553
INF							
D1.		-.0128684	.0114487	-1.12	0.261	-.0353074	.0095707
G							
D1.		.1563009	.0931426	1.68	0.093	-.0262553	.3388571
PS							
D1.		-1.799243	.8516291	-2.11	0.035	-3.468405	-.1300804
EXI							
D1.		.4732641	.5621064	0.84	0.400	-.6284441	1.574972
DP							
D1.		-.0294964	.7067511	-0.04	0.967	-1.414703	1.35571
_cons		10.72588	6.245438	1.72	0.086	-1.514953	22.96671
-----+-----							
CID_2__ec							
GDPG		-.1000084	.0458147	-2.18	0.029	-.1898035	-.0102132
INF		.0104164	.0566779	0.18	0.854	-.1006701	.121503
G		.0209876	.1384058	0.15	0.879	-.2502828	.292258
PS		-4.475834	1.771111	-2.53	0.011	-7.947148	-1.00452
EXI		1.43945	.7868618	1.83	0.067	-.1027705	2.981671
DP		-1.547609	.9487167	-1.63	0.103	-3.407059	.3118418
-----+-----							

CID_2SR							
__ec		-.3819245	.1324614	-2.88	0.004	-.6415441	-.122305
GDPG							
D1.		.0262293	.0144901	1.81	0.070	-.0021708	.0546294
INF							
D1.		.0123363	.0145276	0.85	0.396	-.0161372	.0408098
G							
D1.		-.0996735	.0504061	-1.98	0.048	-.1984677	-.0008793
PS							
D1.		1.040948	.6926737	1.50	0.133	-.3166679	2.398563
EXI							
D1.		-.6745259	.4933976	-1.37	0.172	-1.641567	.2925157
DP							
D1.		-.193885	.265602	-0.73	0.465	-.7144553	.3266853
_cons		-.9860795	2.790536	-0.35	0.724	-6.45543	4.483271

CID_3__ec							
GDPG		-.5530858	.6280402	-0.88	0.379	-1.784022	.6778504
INF		-1.179614	.8324312	-1.42	0.156	-2.81115	.4519208
G		1.643718	1.170195	1.40	0.160	-.6498229	3.937259
PS		16.94175	21.74776	0.78	0.436	-25.68308	59.56659
EXI		12.16184	16.09084	0.76	0.450	-19.37564	43.69931
DP		-5.297489	9.636546	-0.55	0.583	-24.18477	13.58979

CID_3SR							
__ec		-.314764	.1873594	-1.68	0.093	-.6819817	.0524538
GDPG							
D1.		.3616495	.2158336	1.68	0.094	-.0613765	.7846755
INF							

D1.		.1209894	.2147581	0.56	0.573	-.2999288	.5419076
G							
D1.		-.2934221	.2477772	-1.18	0.236	-.7790566	.1922123
PS							
D1.		-4.520352	3.425273	-1.32	0.187	-11.23376	2.193059
EXI							
D1.		-1.975411	3.316853	-0.60	0.551	-8.476323	4.525501
DP							
D1.		1.010036	1.935992	0.52	0.602	-2.784439	4.804511
_cons		-23.68911	43.2273	-0.55	0.584	-108.4131	61.03484

CID_4__ec							
GDPG		.1466843	.746578	0.20	0.844	-1.316582	1.60995
INF		-.0955632	.8156506	-0.12	0.907	-1.694209	1.503083
G		.3112729	1.283077	0.24	0.808	-2.203512	2.826058
PS		-17.2779	25.25707	-0.68	0.494	-66.78086	32.22505
EXI		-1.739769	6.481238	-0.27	0.788	-14.44276	10.96322
DP		10.18857	16.18517	0.63	0.529	-21.53377	41.91091

CID_4SR							
_ec		.1898334	.4350512	0.44	0.663	-.6628512	1.042518
GDPG							
D1.		-.0161977	.0659068	-0.25	0.806	-.1453726	.1129772
INF							
D1.		-.0341467	.1015011	-0.34	0.737	-.2330852	.1647919
G							
D1.		-.029849	.1132211	-0.26	0.792	-.2517582	.1920602
PS							
D1.		-1.641017	1.557545	-1.05	0.292	-4.69375	1.411715

EXI							
D1.		-1.057038	.6983771	-1.51	0.130	-2.425832	.3117557
DP							
D1.		.3933119	.9939246	0.40	0.692	-1.554745	2.341368
_cons		22.5121	17.04357	1.32	0.187	-10.89269	55.91689

CID_5__ec							
GDPG		.0494168	.1113129	0.44	0.657	-.1687525	.267586
INF		.2484583	.1336424	1.86	0.063	-.0134761	.5103927
G		-.2167703	.0841568	-2.58	0.010	-.3817147	-.051826
PS		-1.036035	.897862	-1.15	0.249	-2.795812	.7237423
EXI		-1.088638	.7415105	-1.47	0.142	-2.541972	.364696
DP		2.815954	1.287856	2.19	0.029	.2918032	5.340104

CID_5SR							
_ec		-.5742713	.2415832	-2.38	0.017	-1.047766	-.100777
GDPG							
D1.		-.0084986	.0612967	-0.14	0.890	-.128638	.1116408
INF							
D1.		-.0467619	.0306683	-1.52	0.127	-.1068707	.013347
G							
D1.		-.0176803	.0571187	-0.31	0.757	-.1296308	.0942703
PS							
D1.		.3998491	.5564048	0.72	0.472	-.6906843	1.490382
EXI							
D1.		-.1354307	.5518144	-0.25	0.806	-1.216967	.9461056
DP							
D1.		-1.071017	.3734295	-2.87	0.004	-1.802926	-.3391087

_cons		-1.432467	6.353822	-0.23	0.822	-13.88573	11.02079
-----+-----							
CID_6__ec							
GDPG		-.0290287	.1863027	-0.16	0.876	-.3941753	.3361179
INF		.0776119	.0514723	1.51	0.132	-.023272	.1784957
G		.2873292	.9132818	0.31	0.753	-1.50267	2.077329
PS		-1.231867	2.335621	-0.53	0.598	-5.8096	3.345865
EXI		-.0983823	.9932741	-0.10	0.921	-2.045164	1.848399
DP		1.426911	2.21755	0.64	0.520	-2.919408	5.77323
-----+-----							
CID_6SR							
__ec		-.7373534	.4929964	-1.50	0.135	-1.703608	.2289018
GDPG							
D1.		.0274764	.0961811	0.29	0.775	-.161035	.2159878
INF							
D1.		-.0244689	.0437215	-0.56	0.576	-.1101615	.0612236
G							
D1.		-.4024653	.3963452	-1.02	0.310	-1.179288	.3743571
PS							
D1.		.0566052	1.662599	0.03	0.973	-3.20203	3.31524
EXI							
D1.		.2062835	.5933148	0.35	0.728	-.9565921	1.369159
DP							
D1.		-1.102877	1.101487	-1.00	0.317	-3.261752	1.055998
_cons		-12.08767	32.45076	-0.37	0.710	-75.68999	51.51466
-----+-----							
CID_7__ec							
GDPG		-.1818239	.1606764	-1.13	0.258	-.4967439	.1330961
INF		-.0809292	.1128204	-0.72	0.473	-.3020531	.1401948
G		.1168938	.247327	0.47	0.636	-.3678583	.6016459
PS		-2.991355	1.190795	-2.51	0.012	-5.325271	-.6574396

EXI		-.0787145	1.136982	-0.07	0.945	-2.307159	2.14973
DP		.7909841	1.615981	0.49	0.625	-2.376281	3.958249
-----+-----							
CID_7SR							
__ec		-.5465858	.3115258	-1.75	0.079	-1.157165	.0639936
GDPG							
D1.		.0509138	.0293375	1.74	0.083	-.0065866	.1084143
INF							
D1.		.0438288	.0429846	1.02	0.308	-.0404194	.128077
G							
D1.		-.065213	.0967155	-0.67	0.500	-.2547719	.124346
PS							
D1.		1.673759	.5905022	2.83	0.005	.5163955	2.831122
EXI							
D1.		-1.310514	.822342	-1.59	0.111	-2.922275	.3012465
DP							
D1.		1.105647	.7277789	1.52	0.129	-.3207732	2.532068
_cons		-6.226456	10.81262	-0.58	0.565	-27.41881	14.96589

Average correlation coefficients & Pesaran (2004) CD test

Variables series tested: Ui

Group variable: CID

Number of groups: 7

Average # of observations: 25.67

Panel is: unbalanced

Variable		CD-test	p-value	corr	abs(corr)
Ui		2.87	0.004	0.134	0.301

Notes: Under the null hypothesis of cross-section
independence $CD \sim N(0,1)$

Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data

H0: no first-order autocorrelation

F(1, 6) = 5.095
Prob > F = 0.0648

C. DFE Model for the Assorted Variables

full option not meaningful with dfe

ignoring option and continuing...

Dynamic Fixed Effects Regression: Estimated Error Correction Form

(Estimate results saved as DFE)

		Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	

Dynamic Fixed Effects Regression: Estimated Error Correction Form							
(Estimate results saved as DFE)							

		Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	

__ec							
	GDPG	-.1612828	.0836631	-1.93	0.054	-.3252595	.0026939
	INF	-.001461	.0517848	-0.03	0.977	-.1029574	.1000355
	G	.254254	.1572744	1.62	0.106	-.0539981	.5625061
	PS	-1.922792	.8457397	-2.27	0.023	-3.580411	-.2651725
	EXI	.3496796	.7717084	0.45	0.650	-1.162841	1.8622
	DP	-.8376513	1.247835	-0.67	0.502	-3.283363	1.60806

SR							
	__ec	-.1864977	.0477642	-3.90	0.000	-.2801138	-.0928817
	GDPG						
	D1.	.0161718	.0092893	1.74	0.082	-.0020349	.0343785
	INF						
	D1.	.0008165	.0084266	0.10	0.923	-.0156992	.0173323
	G						
	D1.	-.0538488	.0342717	-1.57	0.116	-.12102	.0133225

PS							
D1.		.0493939	.2361448	0.21	0.834	-.4134414	.5122291
EXI							
D1.		.1064153	.1920382	0.55	0.579	-.2699726	.4828032
DP							
D1.		.0091951	.2320854	0.04	0.968	-.4456838	.4640741
_cons		-.3133236	1.750346	-0.18	0.858	-3.743938	3.117291

Average correlation coefficients & Pesaran (2004) CD test

Variables series tested: Ui

Group variable: CID

Number of groups: 7

Average # of observations: 25.67

Panel is: unbalanced

Variable	CD-test	p-value	corr	abs(corr)
Ui	2.33	0.020	0.108	0.306

Notes: Under the null hypothesis of cross-section independence $CD \sim N(0,1)$

Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data

H0: no first-order autocorrelation

F(1, 6) = 0.216
 Prob > F = 0.6583

hausman dfe pmg

---- Coefficients ----				
	(b)	(B)	(b-B)	sqrt(diag(V_b-V_B))
	dfe2	pmg2	Difference	Std. err.
GDPG	-.1612828	-.0806726	-.0806102	.0736875
INF	-.001461	.0518786	-.0533395	.045143
G	.254254	.0047418	.2495123	.1501066
PS	-1.922792	-2.036248	.1134565	.8089847
EXI	.3496796	-.6514067	1.001086	.707902

DP | -.8376513 .7547996 -1.592451 1.158251

b = Consistent under H0 and Ha; obtained from xtpmg.

B = Inconsistent under Ha, efficient under H0; obtained from xtpmg.

Test of H0: Difference in coefficients not systematic

$$\begin{aligned} \text{chi2}(6) &= (b-B)' [(V_b-V_B)^{-1}] (b-B) \\ &= 4.51 \end{aligned}$$

Prob > chi2 = 0.6086

hausman mg pmg

---- Coefficients ----

	(b)	(B)	(b-B)	sqrt(diag(V_b-V_B))
	mg22	pmg2	Difference	Std. err.
GDPG	-.0868884	-.0806726	-.0062158	.1711437
INF	-.1403978	.0518786	-.1922764	.3558773
G	.2402593	.0047418	.2355175	.5111415
PS	-1.707348	-2.036248	.3289005	7.551643
EXI	1.727468	-.6514067	2.378875	3.57748
DP	1.056774	.7547996	.3019747	3.592936

b = Consistent under H0 and Ha; obtained from xtpmg.

B = Inconsistent under Ha, efficient under H0; obtained from xtpmg.

Test of H0: Difference in coefficients not systematic

$$\begin{aligned} \text{chi2}(6) &= (b-B)' [(V_b-V_B)^{-1}] (b-B) \\ &= 5.36 \end{aligned}$$

Prob > chi2 = 0.4987

2. APPENDICIES OF IRAQ'S TIME SERIES STUDY

Appendix 2. 1 Iraq Time Series Raw Data 2000-2020

Years	TI	GDPG%	INF%	GINI%	UEM%	PS
2000	3.7	16.9	5	57	8.727	-1.74
2001	4	1.7	16.4	58	8.807	-1.68
2002	4.09	-8.2	19.3	59	8.852	-1.61
2003	6.56	-36.66	33.6	35	8.819	-2.39
2004	8.03	53.39	27	41	8.608	-3.18
2005	8.65	1.67	37	42	8.706	-2.69
2006	9.1	5.65	53.2	38	8.652	-2.83
2007	9.45	1.89	-10.1	31	8.65	-2.77
2008	9.33	8.23	12.7	31	8.484	-2.47
2009	9.33	3.38	6.9	32	8.393	-2.18
2010	9.22	6.4	2.9	32	8.251	-2.24
2011	9.11	7.55	5.8	31	8.122	-1.85
2012	9.56	14	6.1	29	7.96	-1.93
2013	9.01	7.62	1.9	27	9.264	-2.01
2014	10	0.2	2.2	25	10.59	-2.48
2015	10	4.72	1.4	23	10.725	-2.26
2016	9.96	13.79	0.6	24	10.82	-2.31
2017	10	-1.82	0.2	27	13.02	-2.31
2018	9.75	2.63	0.4	29	12.966	-2.53
2019	8.68	5.96	-0.2	31	12.863	-2.6
2020	8.682	-15.67	0.6	30	14.088	-2.53

Appendix 2. 2 Description of Iraq Time Series Data

A. Raw Data Graph

B. Differenced Data Graph

Appendix 2. 3 Model Estimation

A. The ARDL Model:

Dependent Variable: TI
 Method: ARDL
 Date: 06/22/22 Time: 00:24
 Sample (adjusted): 2001 2020
 Included observations: 20 after adjustments
 Maximum dependent lags: 1 (Automatic selection)
 Model selection method: Akaike info criterion (AIC)
 Dynamic regressors (1 lag, automatic): GDPG INF UEM GINI PS
 Fixed regressors: C
 Number of models evaluated: 32
 Selected Model: ARDL(1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
TI(-1)	0.180697	0.129800	1.392110	0.1914
GDPG	-0.024724	0.011143	-2.218717	0.0485
INF	0.014657	0.006473	2.264286	0.0448
INF(-1)	0.015327	0.007610	2.014131	0.0691
UEM	-0.183912	0.067927	-2.707496	0.0204
GINI	-0.043148	0.02143589	-2.0129203	0.069252
GINI(-1)	-0.1220573	0.04382969	-2.784808	0.017750
PS	-0.587544	0.322169	-1.823715	0.0955
C	13.04882	2.529024	5.159627	0.0003
R-squared	0.986293	Mean dependent var	8.625600	
Adjusted R-squared	0.976324	S.D. dependent var	1.759392	
S.E. of regression	0.270718	Akaike info criterion	0.526687	
Sum squared resid	0.806172	Schwarz criterion	0.974766	
Log likelihood	3.733132	Hannan-Quinn criter.	0.614157	
F-statistic	98.93715	Durbin-Watson stat	2.528723	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

*Note: p-values and any subsequent tests do not account for model selection.

B. Estimation Equation:

=====

Estimation Equation:

=====

$$\text{TI} = \text{C}(1) \cdot \text{TI}(-1) + \text{C}(2) \cdot \text{INF} + \text{C}(3) \cdot \text{INF}(-1) + \text{C}(4) \cdot \text{GDPG} + \text{C}(5) \cdot \text{UEMP} + \text{C}(6) \cdot \text{GINI} + \text{C}(7) \cdot \text{GINI}(-1) + \text{C}(8) \cdot \text{PS} + \text{C}(9)$$

Substituted Coefficients:

=====

$$TI = 0.180696513387*TI(-1) + 0.014657083034*INF + 0.0153265315209*INF(-1) - 0.0247239406213*GDPG - 0.183912475563*UEMP - 0.0431487463153*GINI - 0.122057302817*GINI(-1) - 0.587543850175*PS + 13.0488223968$$

Cointegrating Equation:

$$EC = TI(-1) - (0.036596*INF(-1) - 0.030177*GDPG - 0.224474*UEMP - 0.201642*GINI(-1) - 0.717126*PS + 15.926726)$$

C. Akaike Information Criteria for the ARDL Model Lags

Akaike Information Criteria (top 20 models)

D. Fitted , Actual, Residual Graph for the constructed model

E. ARDL Long Run Form and Bounds Test

Variable *	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
INF(-1)	0.0366	0.0130	2.8121	0.0138
GDPG	-0.0302	0.0111	-2.7150	0.0168
UEMP	-0.2245	0.0737	-3.0477	0.0087
GINI(-1)	-0.2016	0.0142	-14.1927	0.0000
PS	-0.7171	0.4028	-1.7802	0.0968
C	15.9267	1.0586	15.0447	0.0000
Note: * Coefficients derived from the CEC regression.				

F. F-Bounds Test

Null hypothesis: No levels relationship
 Number of cointegrating variables: 5
 Trend type: Rest. constant (Case 2)
 Sample size: 20

Test Statistic	Value
F-statistic	12.1252916783

Sample Size	10%		5%		1%	
	I(0)	I(1)	I(0)	I(1)	I(0)	I(1)
30	2.407	3.517	2.91	4.193	4.134000	5.761
Asymptotic	2.08	3	2.39	3.38	3.06	4.1500

* I(0) and I(1) are respectively the stationary and non-stationary bounds.

G. Short-Run ARDL Error Correction Regression

ARDL Error Correction Regression

Dependent Variable: D(TI)

Date: 06/22/22 Time: 00:51

Sample: 2000 2020

Included observations: 20

ECM Regression

Case 3: Unrestricted Constant and No Trend

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	13.04882	1.203225	10.84487	0.0000
D(INF)	0.014657	0.003215	4.558866	0.0008
D(GINI)	-0.043148	0.911152	-4.735624	0.0006
CointEq(-1)*	-0.819303	0.076346	-10.73139	0.0000
R-squared	0.923677	Mean dependent var	0.249100	
Adjusted R-squared	0.909366	S.D. dependent var	0.745604	
S.E. of regression	0.224468	Akaike info criterion	0.026687	
Sum squared resid	0.806172	Schwarz criterion	0.225833	
Log likelihood	3.733132	Hannan-Quinn criter.	0.065562	
F-statistic	64.54480	Durbin-Watson stat	2.528723	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Appendix 2. 4 Post Estimation Tests of Model robustness

A. Variance Inflation Factors

Date: 06/22/22 Time: 00:48

Sample: 2000 2020

Included observations: 20

Variable	Coefficient Variance	Uncentered VIF	Centered VIF
TI(-1)	0.016848	341.4179	18.81201
GDPG	0.000124	8.874575	8.379702
INF	4.19E-05	4.059452	2.702133
INF(-1)	5.79E-05	5.629266	3.677058
UEM	0.004614	126.2139	4.493017
GINI	4.594975	154.3668	11.53472
GINI(-1)	19.21042	706.9402	61.06894
PS	0.103793	159.6186	4.193682
C	6.395964	1745.424	NA

B. Wald Test:

Equation: Untitled

Test Statistic	Value	df	Probability
F-statistic	98.93715	(8, 11)	0.0000
Chi-square	791.4972	8	0.0000

C. Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:

F-statistic	2.356982	Prob. F(2,9)	0.1503
Obs*R-squared	6.874692	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.0321

D. Heteroskedasticity Test: ARCH

F-statistic	3.081206	Prob. F(1,17)	0.0972
Obs*R-squared	2.915309	Prob. Chi-Square(1)	0.0877

E. Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey

F-statistic	0.887372	Prob. F(8,11)	0.5562
Obs*R-squared	7.844618	Prob. Chi-Square(8)	0.4488
Scaled explained SS	2.821438	Prob. Chi-Square(8)	0.9451

F. Normality test of the Residuals

G. Ramsey RESET Test

Equation: UNTITLED

Specification: TI TI(-1) GDPG INF INF(-1) UEM GINI GINI(-1) PS C

Omitted Variables: Squares of fitted values

	Value	df	Probability
t-statistic	0.024458	10	0.9810
F-statistic	0.000598	(1, 10)	0.9810

Appendix 2.5 VAR Analyses OF Iraq Time Series Analysis

Vector Autoregression Estimates

Date: 03/03/24 Time: 20:51

Sample (adjusted): 2001 2020

Included observations: 20 after adjustments

Standard errors in () & t-statistics in []

	TI	INF	GINI	UEM	GDPG	PS
TI(-1)	0.612496 0.249955 [2.45042]	-1.056148 5.3179802 [-0.19860]	-4.14079 2.177347 [-1.90176]	-0.30605 0.249305 [-1.22760]	-10.8059 4.687872 [-2.30508]	0.094475 0.091786 [1.02930]
INF(-1)	0.017135 0.014046 [1.21996]	-0.085405 0.2988284 [-0.28580]	-0.04036 0.12235 [-0.32986]	0.012966 0.014009 [0.92555]	0.196624 0.263421 [0.74643]	-0.01113 0.005158 [-2.15754]
GINI(-1)	-0.0484 0.047526 [-1.01830]	0.84454 1.0111597 [0.83522]	0.115992 0.414 [0.28017]	-0.08542 0.047403 [-1.80193]	-2.61304 0.891351 [-2.93155]	0.02064 0.017452 [1.18268]
UEM(-1)	-0.07879 0.105011 [-0.75028]	-2.231681 2.2341901 [-0.99888]	-0.24497 0.914747 [-0.26780]	1.10078 0.104738 [10.5099]	-4.24516 1.969469 [-2.15548]	-0.04796 0.038561 [-1.24379]
GDPG(-1)	-0.00508 0.011461 [-0.44298]	-0.144896 0.2438407 [-0.59423]	0.060719 0.099836 [0.60818]	0.024266 0.011431 [2.12276]	-0.27707 0.214949 [-1.28902]	0.007939 0.004209 [1.88627]
PS(-1)	-0.00707 0.539666 [-0.01309]	-18.12677 11.481786 [-1.57874]	-6.01473 4.701002 [-1.27946]	0.702452 0.538261 [1.30504]	-15.0159 10.12135 [-1.48359]	0.593417 0.19817 [2.99448]
C	5.768209 3.712338 [1.55379]	-28.56485 78.982633 [-0.36166]	52.97268 32.33796 [1.63810]	6.207293 3.702672 [1.67644]	191.3983 69.62427 [2.74902]	-1.95258 1.363205 [-1.43235]
R-squared	0.911393	0.5008807	0.78506	0.927357	0.629371	0.762694
Adj. R-squared	0.870498	0.270518	0.685857	0.893829	0.458311	0.653168
Sum sq. resids	5.211292	2358.9223	395.4355	5.184189	1833.039	0.702704
S.E. equation	0.633142	13.470544	5.515262	0.631493	11.87447	0.232496
F-statistic	22.28595	2.174313	7.913674	27.65953	3.679249	6.963602
Log likelihood	-14.9297	-76.08105	-58.2213	-14.8776	-73.5588	5.106743
Akaike AIC	2.192973	8.308105	6.522133	2.187758	8.055875	0.189326

Schwarz SC	2.541479	8.6566112	6.870639	2.536265	8.404382	0.537832
Mean dependent	8.6256	10.895	33.75	9.832	3.8215	-2.3425
S.D. dependent	1.759392	15.771676	9.84017	1.938057	16.1339	0.39478
Determinant resid covariance (dof adj.)			78.3089			
Determinant resid covariance			5.90597			
Log likelihood			-188.03			
Akaike information criterion			23.0032			
Schwarz criterion			25.0943			
Number of coefficients			42			

A. Inverse Roots of AR

Inverse Roots of AR Characteristic Polynomial

B. Roots of Characteristic Polynomial

Roots of Characteristic Polynomial

Endogenous variables: TI INF GINI UEM GDPG PS

Exogenous variables: C

Lag specification: 1 1

Date: 03/03/24 Time: 21:43

Root	Modulus
0.938723 - 0.178870i	0.9556123536899304

0.938723 + 0.178870i	0.9556123536899304
0.728614	0.7286141237689906
-0.185540 - 0.541349i	0.5722617065577912
-0.185540 + 0.541349i	0.5722617065577912
-0.174773	0.1747729917081435

No root lies outside the unit circle.
VAR satisfies the stability condition.

C. The Impulse Response of Cholesky for all Variables:

Response of TI:

Period	TI	INF	GINI	UEM	GDPG	PS
1	0.633	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	0.100	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
2	0.726	0.110	-0.142	-0.024	-0.025	-0.001
	0.175	0.170	0.122	0.074	0.059	0.072
3	0.511	0.066	-0.017	-0.043	-0.045	-0.001
	0.201	0.183	0.167	0.137	0.064	0.109
4	0.356	0.083	0.037	-0.084	-0.017	-0.017
	0.186	0.152	0.120	0.181	0.044	0.112
5	0.303	0.074	0.027	-0.102	-0.008	-0.043
	0.166	0.139	0.117	0.219	0.042	0.111
6	0.230	0.073	0.051	-0.106	-0.008	-0.056
	0.150	0.134	0.142	0.250	0.045	0.112
7	0.156	0.079	0.073	-0.111	0.000	-0.067
	0.138	0.126	0.158	0.271	0.042	0.115
8	0.108	0.081	0.076	-0.109	0.008	-0.079
	0.126	0.119	0.172	0.283	0.040	0.121
9	0.066	0.081	0.078	-0.100	0.011	-0.086
	0.119	0.119	0.184	0.287	0.039	0.133
10	0.027	0.081	0.080	-0.088	0.015	-0.089
	0.116	0.123	0.193	0.284	0.039	0.147

Response of INF:

Period	TI	INF	GINI	UEM	GDPG	PS
1	5.203	12.425	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	2.898	1.965	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
2	-1.175	0.720	1.826	-0.224	0.757	-2.430
	2.786	3.594	2.624	1.671	1.364	1.587
3	-0.202	2.090	0.339	0.211	0.672	-1.833
	2.644	1.870	1.964	1.460	0.842	0.967
4	-1.016	1.292	0.385	0.693	0.455	-1.452

	1.751	1.134	1.338	1.648	0.508	0.922
5	-1.629	1.070	0.291	0.961	0.477	-1.040
	1.196	1.057	1.111	1.803	0.438	0.823
6	-1.630	0.682	-0.155	1.221	0.436	-0.717
	1.135	1.014	1.205	1.892	0.371	0.863
7	-1.590	0.332	-0.426	1.470	0.318	-0.352
	1.077	0.988	1.293	1.954	0.310	0.923
8	-1.547	0.049	-0.606	1.626	0.237	-0.005
	1.055	1.032	1.349	1.976	0.284	1.020
9	-1.343	-0.213	-0.823	1.712	0.160	0.292
	1.078	1.112	1.407	1.963	0.306	1.136
10	-1.072	-0.444	-0.990	1.744	0.070	0.557
	1.132	1.198	1.456	1.929	0.347	1.245

Response of GINI:

Period	TI	INF	GINI	UEM	GDPG	PS
1	-4.491	1.617	2.764	0.000	0.000	0.000
	1.008	0.669	0.437	0.000	0.000	0.000
2	-2.886	0.372	0.478	-0.281	0.792	-0.806
	1.226	1.471	1.076	0.693	0.555	0.643
3	-1.217	0.015	-0.450	0.379	0.192	-0.615
	1.194	0.890	0.975	0.826	0.354	0.594
4	-1.982	0.085	0.334	0.611	0.095	-0.216
	0.951	0.657	0.608	0.915	0.237	0.504
5	-1.767	0.070	0.014	0.622	0.254	-0.122
	0.844	0.719	0.692	1.130	0.259	0.547
6	-1.172	-0.137	-0.404	0.778	0.149	-0.003
	0.800	0.708	0.820	1.283	0.247	0.574
7	-1.049	-0.231	-0.382	0.879	0.055	0.193
	0.742	0.655	0.835	1.367	0.210	0.591
8	-0.888	-0.296	-0.445	0.882	0.045	0.326
	0.697	0.657	0.910	1.438	0.203	0.639
9	-0.596	-0.387	-0.573	0.874	0.003	0.424
	0.682	0.684	0.971	1.475	0.214	0.708
10	-0.380	-0.452	-0.602	0.842	-0.049	0.517
	0.691	0.714	1.018	1.471	0.225	0.784

Response of UEM:

Period	TI	INF	GINI	UEM	GDPG	PS
1	0.088	-0.002	-0.132	0.611	0.000	0.000
	0.141	0.140	0.138	0.097	0.000	0.000
2	0.063	0.099	-0.284	0.541	0.063	0.094
	0.189	0.216	0.178	0.116	0.063	0.074
3	0.146	-0.073	-0.406	0.545	0.009	0.148
	0.229	0.220	0.205	0.154	0.064	0.099

4	0.075	-0.133	-0.347	0.525	-0.029	0.233
	0.240	0.241	0.196	0.211	0.076	0.129
5	0.067	-0.175	-0.341	0.470	-0.031	0.278
	0.254	0.245	0.210	0.269	0.088	0.149
6	0.133	-0.218	-0.360	0.419	-0.048	0.304
	0.263	0.251	0.227	0.326	0.095	0.164
7	0.175	-0.241	-0.336	0.362	-0.066	0.324
	0.267	0.256	0.248	0.382	0.101	0.180
8	0.213	-0.246	-0.304	0.294	-0.074	0.329
	0.267	0.254	0.273	0.433	0.103	0.194
9	0.260	-0.242	-0.275	0.224	-0.080	0.318
	0.263	0.249	0.296	0.476	0.101	0.209
10	0.298	-0.229	-0.236	0.154	-0.084	0.298
	0.258	0.245	0.320	0.509	0.097	0.227

Response of GDPG:

Period	TI	INF	GINI	UEM	GDPG	PS
1	-7.489	5.043	3.593	-4.680	4.967	0.000
	2.377	1.900	1.628	1.335	0.785	0.000
2	9.971	-2.224	-7.889	-0.915	-0.153	-2.013
	3.419	3.623	2.614	1.464	1.187	1.394
3	0.148	-0.285	2.513	0.132	-1.746	0.603
	3.553	4.084	2.974	1.461	1.518	1.430
4	-2.310	1.145	2.646	-1.530	0.615	-0.095
	2.942	1.849	2.419	0.949	0.783	0.733
5	1.590	0.264	-0.708	-1.227	0.342	-0.907
	2.004	1.187	1.968	1.091	0.826	0.700
6	0.653	0.265	0.565	-0.711	-0.254	-0.566
	1.623	0.947	1.395	1.101	0.599	0.581
7	-0.575	0.667	1.215	-0.868	0.123	-0.560
	1.198	0.690	1.161	1.097	0.334	0.550
8	-0.106	0.585	0.538	-0.804	0.234	-0.758
	0.896	0.714	0.982	1.189	0.385	0.572
9	-0.151	0.511	0.518	-0.569	0.113	-0.721
	0.802	0.622	0.926	1.229	0.274	0.594
10	-0.531	0.554	0.656	-0.448	0.154	-0.659
	0.663	0.594	0.857	1.249	0.222	0.628

Response of PS:

Period	TI	INF	GINI	UEM	GDPG	PS
1	-0.157	-0.063	0.016	-0.025	-0.081	0.134
	0.046	0.037	0.036	0.035	0.033	0.021
2	-0.247	-0.102	0.101	-0.082	-0.009	0.080
	0.073	0.072	0.053	0.035	0.028	0.029
3	-0.049	-0.073	-0.013	-0.087	-0.004	0.037

	0.078	0.080	0.070	0.055	0.028	0.043
4	-0.009	-0.059	0.017	-0.075	-0.024	0.027
	0.070	0.054	0.048	0.061	0.019	0.036
5	-0.023	-0.024	0.054	-0.085	-0.013	0.014
	0.057	0.047	0.046	0.069	0.014	0.033
6	0.006	-0.007	0.042	-0.090	-0.004	-0.007
	0.049	0.046	0.050	0.077	0.015	0.034
7	0.018	0.005	0.045	-0.087	-0.005	-0.021
	0.048	0.045	0.054	0.081	0.014	0.036
8	0.008	0.019	0.056	-0.085	-0.001	-0.031
	0.047	0.046	0.057	0.083	0.014	0.040
9	0.003	0.028	0.057	-0.081	0.004	-0.041
	0.048	0.049	0.060	0.086	0.016	0.045
10	-0.003	0.035	0.056	-0.074	0.006	-0.048
	0.050	0.051	0.063	0.088	0.017	0.050

Cholesky One S.D. (d.f. adjusted) Innovations

Cholesky ordering: TI INF GINI UEM GDPG PS

Standard errors: Analytic standard deviations under the periods.

D. Variance Decomposition in VAR

Variance
Decomposition
of TI:

Period	S.E.	TI	INF	GINI	UEM	GDPG	PS
1	0.633	100.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
2	0.981	96.539	1.250	2.087	0.061	0.063	0.000
		7.910	6.960	3.572	1.739	1.009	1.136
3	1.110	96.613	1.328	1.654	0.194	0.211	0.000
		11.238	9.377	4.669	3.267	1.868	2.567
4	1.172	95.813	1.692	1.579	0.685	0.210	0.022
		13.743	10.451	5.815	5.529	2.174	3.181
5	1.218	94.876	1.935	1.510	1.336	0.198	0.145
		15.666	10.509	6.427	7.652	2.153	3.219
6	1.249	93.689	2.183	1.602	1.996	0.193	0.337
		17.016	10.526	7.054	9.326	2.335	3.332
7	1.270	92.137	2.497	1.881	2.690	0.187	0.607
		18.402	10.473	7.851	10.685	2.514	3.627
8	1.286	90.499	2.828	2.182	3.334	0.186	0.971
		19.525	10.184	8.606	11.908	2.695	3.943
9	1.299	88.903	3.158	2.502	3.857	0.189	1.391
		20.724	10.439	9.076	12.924	2.796	4.342
10	1.311	87.406	3.484	2.834	4.244	0.199	1.832
		21.427	10.159	9.472	13.812	2.900	4.672

Variance
Decomposition
of TI:

Period	S.E.	TI	INF	GINI	UEM	GDPG	PS
1	0.633	100.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
2	0.981	96.539	1.250	2.087	0.061	0.063	0.000
		7.910	6.960	3.572	1.739	1.009	1.136
3	1.110	96.613	1.328	1.654	0.194	0.211	0.000
		11.238	9.377	4.669	3.267	1.868	2.567
4	1.172	95.813	1.692	1.579	0.685	0.210	0.022
		13.743	10.451	5.815	5.529	2.174	3.181
5	1.218	94.876	1.935	1.510	1.336	0.198	0.145
		15.666	10.509	6.427	7.652	2.153	3.219
6	1.249	93.689	2.183	1.602	1.996	0.193	0.337
		17.016	10.526	7.054	9.326	2.335	3.332
7	1.270	92.137	2.497	1.881	2.690	0.187	0.607
		18.402	10.473	7.851	10.685	2.514	3.627
8	1.286	90.499	2.828	2.182	3.334	0.186	0.971
		19.525	10.184	8.606	11.908	2.695	3.943
9	1.299	88.903	3.158	2.502	3.857	0.189	1.391
		20.724	10.439	9.076	12.924	2.796	4.342
10	1.311	87.406	3.484	2.834	4.244	0.199	1.832
		21.427	10.159	9.472	13.812	2.900	4.672

Variance
Decomposition
of INF:

Period	S.E.	TI	INF	GINI	UEM	GDPG	PS
1	13.471	14.919	85.081	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
		16.329	16.329	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
2	13.900	14.726	80.168	1.726	0.026	0.296	3.057
		14.474	15.101	6.344	2.492	1.844	3.163
3	14.199	14.134	79.002	1.712	0.047	0.508	4.597
		13.945	14.679	6.726	2.953	1.958	3.588
4	14.396	14.247	77.655	1.737	0.278	0.595	5.489
		13.817	14.613	6.640	3.447	1.856	3.879
5	14.607	15.082	75.966	1.727	0.703	0.684	5.839
		13.639	14.889	6.979	4.481	2.022	3.937
6	14.789	15.928	74.324	1.695	1.367	0.754	5.932
		13.614	14.888	7.501	5.618	2.216	3.964
7	14.964	16.687	72.645	1.737	2.301	0.782	5.849
		13.696	15.227	7.118	6.835	2.339	3.889
8	15.145	17.332	70.916	1.856	3.398	0.787	5.710
		13.917	15.624	7.305	8.047	2.317	3.792

9	15.328	17.689	69.255	2.100	4.565	0.780	5.611
		14.015	16.234	7.546	9.249	2.291	3.769
10	15.512	17.749	67.702	2.458	5.721	0.763	5.607
		14.451	16.901	7.613	10.239	2.310	3.898

Variance
Decomposition
of GINI:

Period	S.E.	TI	INF	GINI	UEM	GDPG	PS
1	5.515	66.299	8.591	25.110	0.000	0.000	0.000
		13.548	9.729	8.893	0.000	0.000	0.000
2	6.361	70.414	6.799	19.437	0.195	1.548	1.607
		13.752	11.980	7.865	2.366	2.890	3.310
3	6.535	70.184	6.442	18.890	0.521	1.553	2.409
		14.526	12.662	8.135	3.178	2.930	3.667
4	6.869	71.853	5.846	17.334	1.262	1.425	2.280
		15.116	12.879	7.997	4.838	3.045	3.699
5	7.126	72.918	5.442	16.108	1.933	1.451	2.147
		15.716	13.256	7.930	6.773	2.881	3.373
6	7.278	72.506	5.253	15.752	2.996	1.433	2.059
		16.333	12.924	8.435	8.588	3.211	3.308
7	7.421	71.724	5.149	15.413	4.282	1.384	2.048
		17.076	12.794	8.915	10.152	3.321	3.222
8	7.552	70.642	5.125	15.231	5.498	1.340	2.164
		17.672	12.779	9.355	11.575	3.294	3.215
9	7.669	69.113	5.225	15.328	6.630	1.299	2.404
		18.241	13.100	9.402	12.696	3.429	3.421
10	7.778	67.421	5.417	15.499	7.617	1.267	2.779
		18.741	13.027	9.727	13.584	3.466	3.725

Variance
Decomposition
of UEM:

Period	S.E.	TI	INF	GINI	UEM	GDPG	PS
1	0.631	1.951	0.001	4.388	93.660	0.000	0.000
		9.334	8.767	9.687	13.908	0.000	0.000
2	0.894	1.464	1.225	12.256	83.443	0.502	1.111
		8.377	10.446	11.449	14.368	1.616	1.645
3	1.144	2.518	1.152	20.082	73.576	0.313	2.359
		10.609	9.816	13.290	15.154	1.410	3.250
4	1.336	2.164	1.832	21.500	69.453	0.276	4.776
		12.247	10.314	13.959	16.443	1.606	5.108
5	1.495	1.929	2.840	22.356	65.335	0.263	7.277
		13.484	11.408	14.044	17.318	1.852	6.851
6	1.643	2.254	4.118	23.301	60.569	0.303	9.455
		14.428	12.501	14.055	17.785	2.111	8.326
7	1.773	2.914	5.387	23.609	56.216	0.401	11.473

		15.027	13.065	14.068	18.092	2.419	9.227
8	1.882	3.866	6.488	23.561	52.341	0.512	13.233
		15.546	13.581	13.845	18.312	2.689	9.783
9	1.975	5.248	7.393	23.326	48.800	0.628	14.605
		16.071	14.019	13.640	18.282	2.881	10.074
10	2.054	6.964	8.077	22.895	45.701	0.749	15.615
		16.633	14.020	13.476	18.136	3.013	10.194

Variance
Decomposition
of GDPG:

Period	S.E.	TI	INF	GINI	UEM	GDPG	PS
1	11.874	39.773	18.039	9.157	15.532	17.499	0.000
		18.593	13.617	8.702	9.115	6.643	0.000
2	17.678	49.756	9.721	24.048	7.276	7.903	1.297
		15.780	10.312	11.460	4.172	3.682	1.818
3	17.955	48.243	9.449	25.273	7.059	8.607	1.370
		14.671	11.118	10.831	4.298	3.712	1.945
4	18.405	47.486	9.380	26.118	7.408	8.302	1.307
		15.146	12.040	11.082	4.543	3.262	1.991
5	18.555	47.455	9.249	25.842	7.727	8.203	1.525
		15.232	12.259	11.016	5.217	3.372	2.013
6	18.601	47.344	9.224	25.807	7.835	8.181	1.610
		15.477	12.634	10.897	5.928	3.246	2.051
7	18.690	46.987	9.263	25.983	7.976	8.107	1.684
		15.613	12.931	11.076	6.916	3.277	2.061
8	18.742	46.733	9.310	25.924	8.116	8.078	1.838
		15.914	12.885	10.979	7.800	3.291	2.191
9	18.779	46.553	9.347	25.896	8.176	8.050	1.979
		16.030	13.065	11.037	8.596	3.300	2.286
10	18.824	46.412	9.389	25.895	8.194	8.018	2.092
		16.143	13.105	11.017	9.359	3.345	2.398

Variance
Decomposition
of PS:

Period	S.E.	TI	INF	GINI	UEM	GDPG	PS
1	0.232	45.477	7.342	0.448	1.199	12.276	33.257
		16.522	9.583	4.684	3.839	8.902	10.006
2	0.386	57.594	9.664	7.027	4.900	4.506	16.309
		15.604	11.307	7.531	5.052	5.128	7.090
3	0.407	53.167	11.894	6.414	8.988	4.058	15.480
		15.656	12.736	7.329	7.230	4.803	6.753
4	0.420	49.949	13.121	6.186	11.651	4.145	14.949
		15.659	11.622	7.165	8.428	4.743	6.413
5	0.434	47.151	12.621	7.345	14.773	3.977	14.133
		15.998	11.205	7.679	9.745	4.670	6.170

6	0.446	44.769	12.006	7.872	18.129	3.784	13.439
		16.222	10.842	7.935	11.093	4.514	6.037
7	0.457	42.700	11.421	8.452	20.845	3.607	12.976
		16.320	11.143	8.106	12.256	4.427	5.869
8	0.470	40.473	10.974	9.438	22.980	3.417	12.718
		16.564	11.183	8.374	13.222	4.375	5.742
9	0.482	38.345	10.744	10.334	24.574	3.243	12.759
		16.722	11.442	8.883	13.813	4.195	5.597
10	0.495	36.457	10.703	11.099	25.579	3.099	13.062
		16.922	11.465	8.868	14.427	4.001	5.600

Cholesky One S.D. (d.f. adjusted) Innovations
Cholesky ordering: TI INF GINI UEM GDPG PS
Standard errors: Monte Carlo (100 repetitions) standard deviations under the periods.

E. Impulse Response Graph

**LETTERS OF ACCEPTANCE OF PUBLICATIONS
DERIVED FROM THE DISSERTATION TOPIC
Publication 1 The Impact of Economic Determinants on Terrorism in
Iraq During the Period 2000-2020**

Faculty of Economics
University of Tehran

2 October 2022

Dear Ms. Sarah Ahmed Chawsheen (Corresponding Author)

The editorial board of the Iranian Economic Review (IER) journal is pleased to inform you that your manuscript (IER-202207-1007505) with **Dr. Zaki Husain Qadir**, entitled “**The Impact of Economic Determinants on Terrorism in Iraq During the Period 2000-2020**” will be published in the next issues of the IER journal, according to the publishing priorities.

Regards,

H. Abbasinejad

Hossein Abbasinejad

Iranian Economic Review (IER) Journal

Publication 2 Analyzing the Relationship Between Some Economic Indicators and Iraq Terrorism Index, and Forecasting it Using the ARMA Model

REPUBLIC OF IRAQ MINISTRY OF HIGHER EDUCATION & SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH Mustansiriyah University Administration & Economics Faculty IRAQI JOURNAL FOR ECONOMICS SCIENCES		جمهورية العراق وزارة التعليم العالي والبحث العلمي جامعة المستنصرية كلية الإدارة والاقتصاد المجلة العراقية للعلوم الاقتصادية
مجلة فصلية متخصصة محكمة تعنى بالعلوم الاقتصادية بكافة تخصصاتها رقم التصنيف الدولي / ISSN:-1812-8742		

العدد: 5
التاريخ: 2024/1/8

إلى / م. سارذ احمد حسن جاوشين المحترمة
أ.م. د زكي حسين قادر المحترم
كلية الادارة والاقتصاد / جامعة صلاح الدين / اربيل

م / قبول نشر

لهديكم أطيب تحياتنا.....

يسرنا أن نعلمكم بموافقة هيئة تحرير المجلة على نشر بحثكم الموسوم :

Analyzing the Relationship Between Some Economic Indicators and Iraq Terrorism Index, and Forecasting it Using the ARMA Model

ضمن أعداد المجلة المقبلة لاستيفائه للشروط العلمية والفنية شاكرين تعاونكم العلمي معنا ونتمنى استمرار هذا التعاون مستقبلا.
مع التقدير

أ.د. فادح خلف علي
رئيس التحرير
2024/1/8

نسخة منه الى / - سكرتارية تحرير المجلة مع الاوليات

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العراق - بغداد - الطالبيية
ص.ب (٤٦٠٨٩) بريد المستنصرية - بغداد - العراق

Publication 3 The Influence of Some Economic and Non-Economic Factors on Terrorism in the Seven Most Affected Countries During the Years 2000-2021

REPUBLIC OF IRAQ MINISTRY OF HIGHER EDUCATION & SCIENTFC RESEARCH Mustansiriyah University Administration & Economics Faculty IRAQI JOURNAL FOR ECONOMICS SCIENCES		جمهورية العراق وزارة التعليم العالي والبحث العلمي جامعة المستنصرية كلية الإدارة والاقتصاد المجلة العراقية للعلوم الاقتصادية
مجلة فصلية متخصصة محكمة تعنى بالعلوم الاقتصادية بكافة تخصصاتها رقم التصنيف الدولي / ISSN:-1812-8742		

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أ. د زكي حسين قادر المحترم
كلية الادارة والاقتصاد / جامعة صلاح الدين / اربيل
م / قبول نشر

لهديكم اطيب تحياتنا.....

يسرنا أن نعلمكم بموافقة هيئة تحرير المجلة على نشر بحثكم الموسوم :

The Influence of Some Economic and Non-Economic Factors on Terrorism in the Seven Most Affected Countries During the Years 2000–2021

(بحث مستل)

ضمن أعداد المجلة المقبلة لاستيفائه للشروط العلمية والفنية شاكرين تعاونكم العلمي معنا ونتمنى استمرار هذا التعاون مستقبلا.

مع التقدير

أ.د. فلاح خلف علي

رئيس التحرير

2024/2/4

نسخة منه الى /- سكرتارية تحرير المجلة مع الاذيات

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العراق - بغداد - الطالبيية
ص.ب(٤٦٠٨٩) بريد المستنصرية- بغداد - العراق

پوخته

ئەم توۋىژىنەۋەيە بەدواداچوون بۇ كارىگەرىيە ھەندىك لە گۇرپاۋە ئابورى و نئابورىيەكان دەكات لەسەر تىرۆر لە ھەوت ولاتى ھەلبۇزىردراودا، بە گرنگىدانىكى تايبەت بە عىراق، لە ماۋەى سالانى ۲۰۰۰ تا ۲۰۲۱، كە سى تەۋەرى سەرەكى لەخۇدەگرىت: (۱) تىورى ئابورى و چەمكەكانى پەيوەست بە تىرۆر. (2) شىكردنەۋەى داتاكانى پانىل بۇ ديارىكردنى كارىگەرى ھەندىك لە گۇرپاۋە ئابورى و سىياسى و دىمۇگرافىيەكان لەسەر تىرۆر. (3) مۇدىلى زنجىرە كاتىبە خەملىنراۋەكانى ARDL، و مۇدىلى خەملىنراۋى ARMA بۇ پىشېبىنىكردنى پىئوەرەكانى تىرۆر لە عىراق.

مۇدىلى دواكەۋتنى دابەشكراۋى خۇپاشكەۋتن ARDL، لەۋانەش مامناۋەندى گروپى كۇكراۋەى PMG، مامناۋەندى گروپى MG، و كارىگەرى جىگىر دىنامىكى DFE، لە شىكارى داتاكانى پانىلدا بەكارھىنراون. مۇدىلى PMG كە بۇ گۇرپاۋە ئابورىيەكان ھەلبۇزىردراۋە، پەيوەندىيەكى درىژخايەنى نەرىنى لە نىۋان رىژەى گەشەى بەرھەمى ناوخۆبى و تىرۆر ئاشكرا دەكات، لە كاتىكدا پەيوەندىيەكى نەرىنى لە نىۋان ھەلاۋسانى نرخ و تىرۆردا ھەيە. لە لايەكى دىكەۋە، مۇدىلى PMG بۇ گۇرپاۋە جۇراۋجۇرەكان نىشانىدا كە سەقامگىرى سىياسى، دەستىۋەردانەكانى دەرەكى و گەشەى بەرھەمى ناوخۆبى پەيوەندىيەكى درىژخايەنى نەرىنىيان لەگەل تىرۆردا ھەيە. بەلام پەيوەندىيەكى نەرىنى درىژخايەن لە نىۋان ھەلاۋسانى نرخ و فشارى دىمۇگرافىدا ھەيە. لە ماۋەى كورتخايەندا جىھانگىرى ئابورى پەيوەندىيەكى پىچەۋانەى لەگەل تىرۆردا ھەيە. توۋىژىنەۋەكە ئاشكراى دەكات كە گۇرپاۋە ئابورىيەكان بەتەنھا كارىگەرى درىژخايەنىيان لەسەر تىرۆر ھەيە لە ولاتانى ھەلبۇزىردراودا، نىزىكەى ۹ سال دەخايەنىت، لەكاتىكدا گۇرپاۋە تىكەلەكان پىكەۋە كە ھۆكارە ئابورى و نئابورىيەكان لەخۇدەگرن، تىكراى كارىگەرىيان نىزىكەى ۴ سال دەخايەنىت.

ئەم توۋىژىنەۋەيە ئاشكراى دەكات كە ھەلاۋسانى نرخەكان كارىگەرى نەرىنى لەسەر تىرۆر لە عىراق ھەيە، لە كاتىكدا گەشەى بەرھەمى ناوخۆبى و بىكارى و نايەكسانى داھات و سەقامگىرى سىياسى كارىگەرى نەرىنى درىژخايەنىيان ھەيە. تىكراى خىراى خۇگونجاندىن لە ناھاۋسەنگى سالى پىشوو بۇ بالانسى سالى ئىستا 81.9% يە، ئەمەش ئامازەيە بۇ كارىگەرىيەك كە بۇ ماۋەى 1.2 سال بەردەوام دەبىت. مۇدىلى ARMA پىشېبىنى دابەزىنىكى خاۋ و بەردەۋامى پىئوەرەكانى تىرۆرى عىراق دەكات.

زانکۆی سه‌لاحه‌ددین - هه‌ولێر
Salahaddin University – Erbil

کاربگه‌ری هه‌ندیک له‌ گۆراوه‌ ئابوورییه‌کان له‌ سه‌ر تیروۆر له‌ ولاتانی هه‌لبژێردراودا به‌ ئاماژه‌یه‌کی تایبه‌ت به‌ عێراق بۆ ماوه‌ی ۲۰۲۱-۲۰۰۰

تیزیک پێشکەش کراوه‌ به‌ ئه‌نجومه‌نی کۆلیژی به‌ریوه‌بردن و ئابووری له‌
زانکۆی سه‌لاحه‌ددین - هه‌ولێر وه‌ک به‌شێک له‌ پێداویسته‌یه‌کانی به‌ده‌سته‌ینانی
پله‌ی دکتۆرای فله‌سه‌فه‌ له‌ ئابووری

له‌ لایه‌ن

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